

BIOcean5D

**MARINE BIODIVERSITY ASSESSMENT AND
PREDICTION ACROSS SPATIAL, TEMPORAL
AND HUMAN SCALES**

**D6.1. Natural capital accounting and
Deliberative Monetary Value of marine
ecosystem services**

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Table of content

- Table of content 2
- List of Tables 6
- List of Figures 6
- Version history 8
- List of Acronyms 9
- Executive summary 10
- Introduction 16
- 1. Natural capital accounting of selected habitats, functions, and services (Task 6.2)..... 18
 - 1.1 General overview: Identification of the ecosystem services derived from coastal and marine communities 18
 - 1.1.1 Introduction 18
 - 1.1.2 Material and Methods 19
 - 1.1.2.1 Bibliographic data acquisition 19
 - 1.1.2.2 Topic modeling 20
 - 1.1.2.3 Labelling topics 20
 - 1.1.2.4 Analysis of topics 21
 - 1.1.3 Results 21
 - 1.1.3.1 Topic modelling interpretation 21
 - 1.1.3.2 Topics' proportion, aggregation, and temporal 24
 - 1.1.4 References 26
 - 1.2 Applied Natural Accounting: the role of marine plankton in providing ecosystem services based on its special role in marine ecosystems 29
 - 1.2.1 Introduction 29
 - 1.2.2 Material and Methods 31
 - 1.2.2.1 Literature Search of Global Plankton Ecosystem Services 31
 - 1.2.2.2 Spatiotemporal Network Analysis of Plankton Ecosystem Services at a Regional Scale 32
 - 1.2.3 Results 33
 - 1.2.3.1 Plankton Ecosystem Services 33
 - 1.2.3.2 Regulating and Maintenance Ecosystem Services 34
 - 1.2.3.3 Provisioning Ecosystem Services 36
 - 1.2.3.4 Cultural Ecosystem Services 38
 - 1.2.3.5 Spatiotemporal Variability of Plankton Ecosystem Services 39
 - 1.2.4 References 43

- 1.3 Applied Natural Accounting to ecosystem services in the water column. From coastal to deep sea ecosystems, from microbes to tuna fishes 51
 - 1.3.1 Introduction 51
 - 1.3.2 Material and Methods 52
 - 1.3.2.1. Case Studies overview 52
 - 1.3.2.2. Identification of ecosystem services following a participatory approach.... 53
 - 1.3.2.3. Methods to assess economically ecosystem services: an overview 55
 - Direct market valuation approaches 56
 - Revealed preference approaches 57
 - Stated preferences approaches 58
 - Environmental benefit transfers..... 58
 - 1.3.3 Results: a holistic ES economic/monetary valuation 58
 - 1.3.3.1. Identified ecosystem services following a participatory approach 58
 - 1.3.3.2. Material and methods for biophysical characterization and economic assessment 62
 - 1.3.3.2.1. CS 1: Mesopelagic fisheries in Bay of Biscay 64
 - 1.3.3.2.2. CS 2: Diadromous fishes in EU Atlantic Area 64
 - 1.3.3.2.3. CS 3: Tunas in Tropical Atlantic Ecoregion..... 65
 - 1.3.3.2.4. CS 4: Atlantic Bluefin Tuna in Skagerrak 66
 - 1.3.3.2.5. CS 5: System seagrass-lucinids-bacteria along the Slovenian coast.. 67
 - 1.3.3.2.6. CS 6: Holobionts Sponges-microbes in Catalan Sea 67
 - 1.3.3.2.7. CS 7: Plankton in three Gulfs in Italy 68
 - 1.3.3.3. Economic and monetary estimations of identified ecosystem services 68
 - 1.3.3.3.1. CS 1: Mesopelagic fisheries in Bay of Biscay 72
 - 1.3.3.3.2. CS 2: Diadromous fishes in the EU Atlantic area..... 72
 - 1.3.3.3.3. CS 3: Tunas in Tropical Atlantic Ecoregion..... 73
 - 1.3.3.3.4. CS 4: Atlantic bluefin tuna in Skagerrak 73
 - 1.3.3.3.5. CS 5: System seagrass-lucinids-bacteria along the Slovenian coast.. 74
 - 1.3.3.3.6. CS 6: Holobionts Sponges-microbes in Catalan Sea 74
 - 1.3.3.3.7. CS 7: Plankton in three Gulfs in Italy 74
 - 1.3.4. References 74
- 2. Deliberative Monetary Valuation of marine biodiversity [Task 6.3]..... 81
 - 2.1 Introduction 81
 - 2.2 Material and Methods 81
 - 2.2.1 Workshop design and implementation 81

- 2.2.2 Discrete Choice Experiment..... 83
- 2.2.3 Econometric model 85
- 2.3 Results from Deliberative Monetary Valuation..... 86
- 2.4. References 88
- 3. Discussion 90
- 3.1 Natural Capital Accounting [Task 6.2] 90
 - 3.1.1. General overview: Identification of the ecosystem services derived from coastal and marine communities 90
 - 3.1.1.1 Temporal trends of marine ecosystem services..... 90
 - 3.1.1.2 References..... 91
 - 3.1.2. Applied Natural Accounting: the role of marine plankton in providing ecosystem services based on its special role in marine ecosystems..... 93
 - 3.1.2.1 References..... 95
 - 3.1.3. Applied Natural Accounting: a collection of case studies..... 96
 - 3.1.3.1. Economic estimation as an indicator of biological/ecological conditions? . 96
 - 3.1.3.2. Critical uncertainties and gaps in the estimation of the ecosystem services economic assessment..... 97
 - 3.1.3.3. Barriers preventing the economic valuation of ecosystem services 98
 - 3.1.3.4. The benefits of a multidisciplinary/interdisciplinary team 99
 - 3.1.3.5. A step forward: the adoption of an ecosystem services approach in decision making..... 100
 - 3.1.3.6. References 102
- 3.2 Deliberative monetary valuation [Task 6.3] 105
- Conclusion 106
- References 107
- Annexes..... 111
 - A. Natural Capital Accounting [Task 6.2] 111
 - A.1. Applied Natural Accounting: a collection of case studies..... 111
 - A.1.1. CS descriptions..... 111
 - A.1.1.1. CS 1: Mesopelagic fishes in Bay of Biscay 111
 - A.1.1.2. CS 2: Diadromous fishes in EU Atlantic Area 111
 - A.1.1.3. CS 3: Tunas in Tropical Atlantic Ecoregion 112
 - A.1.1.4. CS 4: Atlantic Bluefin Tuna in Skagerrak (Denmark) 112
 - A.1.1.5. CS 5: System seagrass-lucinids-bacteria along the Slovenian coast.. 113
 - A.1.1.6. CS 6: Holobionts Sponges-microbes in Catalan Sea 114
 - A.1.1.7. CS 7: Plankton in three Gulfs in Italy 114

A.1.1.8.	References.....	115
A.1.2.	FG and fleets for CS 1	119
A.1.3.	FG and fleets for CS 3	122
A.1.4.	FG for CS 7.....	125
A.1.5.	Parameters of ZTCM for CS 4.....	127

List of Tables

Table 1. Uncovered topics from 9,048 papers about marine ES published between January 1990 and December 2024 with assigned labels, 20 top words (i.e., words with the highest probability), and a short topic description.	22
Table 2: Numbers of experts consulted and meetings (including interviews conducted and workshops) for each CS.....	55
Table 3: ES identified for each CS. “Regulating and Maintenance” CICES category is denoted by “Regulating” with key ES blue-coloured	60
Table 4: ES economically assessed with valuation methods, data needed for biophysical characterizations and their origin	62
Table 5: Economic data needed and references.....	63
Table 6: Average present value of ecosystem services once the mesopelagic fishery starts exploiting (CS1)	69
Table 7: Economic and monetary values of ecosystem services delivered by diadromous fishes, tuna, seagrass, sponges and plankton in epipelagic, benthic and freshwaters ecosystems (CS 2 - CS 7). Lines in blue are used to obtain an overall value.	69
Table 8. Selected socio-demographic variables of workshops participants and comparison with the corresponding actual EU data.....	86
Table 9. Conditional and mixed logit models result	87
Table 10: Status baseline of management processes for each case study, as well as propositions to introduce ecosystem services concept into them.	100
Table 11: Functional groups of EwE for CS 1	119
Table 12: Fleets of EwE for CS 1.....	121
Table 13: Functional groups of EwE for CS 3.	122
Table 14: Fleets of EwE for CS 3. Acronyms used for gears are based on ICCAT Data Code System: PS: Purse Seine, FAD: Fish Aggregating Device, FSC: Free School Catching, BB: Bait Boat, LL: Longline, HL: Hand Line, GN: Gillnet, TW: Trawl, TP: Trap, TR: Trolling Line, HS: Haul Seine, RR: Rod and Reel, UN: Unknown Gear	124
Table 15: FG of Ecopath for CS 7. Notations (s) and (d) stand for surface layer (from 0 to 10m of depth) and deep layer (more than 10m of depth), respectively.	125
Table 16: Summary of regression model diagnostics.....	127
Table 17: Estimated regression coefficients with their Generalized Variance Inflation Factor scaled by degrees of freedom, $GVIF^{1/(2 \times Df)}$. Significance levels are indicated using R's standard codes: (***) $p < 0.001$, (**) $p < 0.01$, (*) $p < 0.05$	127

List of Figures

Figure 1. Alluvial showing main ES (center) characterizing the topics derived (left), with colors following the corresponding ES category (right) of each identified marine ES, based on Liqueste et al., (2013) classification.....	23
Figure 2. Topic modeling results from semantic analyses of the dataset. A: Proportion of papers associated with topics. B: Cluster analysis (hierarchical clustering, Ward's method) of topics based on the document-term matrix.....	24
Figure 3. Temporal dynamics of the yearly paper publication associated with each topic. A: Annual number of papers for each topic (topic frequency). B: Annual proportion	

of papers in each topic on the total number of papers (topic proportion). Straight lines represent “hot topics”, dashed lines are “cold topics”, dotted lines represent topics with no significant changes. Color coding in A and B indicates the topic as illustrated in the legend. 25

Figure 4. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram showing the screening of identified records for systematic review..... 32

Figure 5. An alluvial diagram showing ES (center, based on the CICES classification (Haines-Young and Potschin-Young, 2018)) identified from the systematic review of the literature for plankton groups (left), with colors following the corresponding ES category (right) of each identified planktonic ES..... 34

Figure 6. Median inDegree values of each ES category within each gulf and sampling survey (indicated with numbers next to the colored circles, see Supplementary Tables S4, S6 and S7 from Russo et al., 2025a). 1 = autumn; 2 = summer. 40

Figure 7. Median trophic level values of each ES category within each gulf and sampling survey (indicated with numbers next to the colored circles, see Supplementary Tables S4, S6 and S7 from Russo et al., 2025a). 1 = autumn; 2 = summer. 42

Figure 8. Boxplots for unicellular to metazoan and phytoplankton to protozooplankton ratios of each gulf and sampling survey, and heatmaps showing statistical significance of pairwise Wilcoxon test (p -value < 0.05 means samples are significantly different). 1 = autumn; 2 = summer..... 43

Figure 9: Location of the CS considered in this study, as well as main ES providers (that is, ecosystems and species delivering ES) per CS. CS 1: Mesopelagic fishes in the Bay of Biscay; CS 2: Diadromous fishes in the EU Atlantic Area; CS 3: Tunas in the tropical Atlantic Ecoregion; CS 4: Atlantic Bluefin Tuna in Skagerrak; CS 5: System seagrass-lucinids-bacteria along the Slovenian coast; CS 6: Holobionts sponges-microbes in Catalan Sea and CS 7: Plankton in three Gulfs of Italy. 53

Figure 10: Conceptual representation of the intersection between ES identified through topic modelling and those evaluated in literature-based case studies. Red links indicate ES identified via topic modelling that are attributed to one or more groups of organisms in case studies. Blue links represent ES detected through topic modelling that have no corresponding organism groups in case studies. Dashed black links indicate ES evaluated exclusively within the reported selected case studies. **Source:** Russo et al., 2025. 55

Figure 11: Traditional methods to estimate the monetary value (for market goods) or the economic value (for not market goods). **Source:** Müller et al., 2015. 56

Figure 12: Total economic value of ES per square meter for CS 3, 5 and 7. For CS in light red it is not possible to obtain the economic values per square meter. 71

Figure 13. Workshop’s locations 82

Figure 14. Locations of Italian workshops and the corresponding target area. Taken from Jean-Louis et al. 2025. © OpenStreetMap contributors 83

Figure 15. Example Choice Card. Icons sourced from Flaticon and modified in some cases : “Plankton” icons (IDs 3751453, 7588203, 7584197), “Jellyfish” (ID 1167699), “Water Waves” (ID 2352851), “CO₂” (ID 7822231), and “Secure” (ID 95454), used under the license Free. 85

Figure 16. Conditional logit models in WTP space for each region including significance levels for the parameter estimates at $p < 0.1$ (.), $p < 0.05$ *, $p < 0.01$ ** and $p < 0.001$ ***. The displayed data represent the mean estimates and the 95% confidence intervals based on the corresponding means' standard errors 88

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List of Acronyms

AER: Annual Economic Report
APV: Average Present Value
BAU: Business As Usual
CICES: Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services
CS: Case Study
CSP: Carbon Sequestration Potential
DCE: Discrete Choice Experiment
EPE: Environmental Protection Expenditure
ES: Ecosystem Services
EU: European Union
DMV: Deliberative Monetary Value
DOC: Dissolved Organic Carbon
EwE: Ecopath with Ecosim
FG: Functional Group
FM: Fish Meal
FO: Fish Oil
GDP: Gross Domestic Product
GR3D: Global Repositioning Dynamics for Diadromous fish Distribution
HICP: Harmonised Index of Consumer Prices.
IPBES: Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
LDA: latent Dirichlet allocation
MEA: Millenium Ecosystem Assessment
NCA: Natural Capital Accounting
NCP: Nature's Contribution to People
MPA: Marine Protected Area
MSFD: Marine Strategy Framework Directive
OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
RUM: Random Utility Maximisation
SEEA: System of Environmental-Economic Accounting
TCM: Travel Cost Method
TGF: Trip Generation Function
TEEB: The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity
WoS: Web of Science
WTP: Willingness To Pay
ZTCM: Zonal Travel Cost Method

Executive summary

This work grounds the economic assessment and conservation strategy of marine ecosystems in a functional approach to biodiversity. **This supposes, among other things, to estimate the measurement of the economic contribution of ecosystem functions and ecosystem services (ES) through applied natural capital accounting procedures (task 6.2). But also, the investigation of experts' and public's motivations for the valuation and protection of marine biodiversity along the European coastal areas (task 6.3).**

Task 6.2 starts providing (Section 1.1) a set of techniques to develop a general overview of the ES delivered by a high variety of habitats and functional groups. A topic modelling approach combined with systematic review conducted to select a few coastal and marine habitats and key species and go ahead to identify the ES delivered. **The four hot topics delivering ES with increasing trends have been identified, that is, the topics of Marine policy, Climate change impact, blue carbon systems - carbon storage, and Microbial biotic materials and biofuels. Conversely, the three cold topics with decreasing trends were identified, that is, the Coral reefs recreational activities, Coastal tourism and recreational fisheries and the Water purification.** This Deliverable 6.1 establishes the link between these topics and the delivery of ES. The rise in research on the carbon storage of blue-carbon systems is consistent with the growing recognition of their global significance, beginning with the seminal work by Duarte et al. (2005) and the popularization of the term "blue carbon" by Nellemann (2009) and its role in mitigating climate change (Ruiz-Frau et al., 2017). In contrast, topics addressing localized climate change impacts observed a decrease (Water purification) or no changes over time (Coastal protection) despite approximately half of their publications being published in the last five years. This suggests a shift in research priorities from localized issues to broader, globally relevant environmental challenges. The growing emphasis on climate change and associated topics appears to reduce attention on recreation and tourism-related ES. The previous traditional review by Liqueste et al. (2013) identified fisheries, recreation, and tourism among the most-studied marine ES. In the present study, recreational and tourism-related topics were prominent too, accounting for 32.1 % of the dataset. This finding confirms earlier observations (Liqueste et al., 2013; Torres and Hanley, 2017) and suggests that recreation assessment and quantification in monetary terms is more accomplishable than other cultural ES (Hernandez-Morcillo et al., 2013; Martin et al., 2016). However, Coral reefs - linked recreational activities and Coastal tourism and recreational fisheries significantly declined in proportional focus over time; Marine wildlife tourism remained stable. These topics also exhibited three of the lowest percentages of recent publications, further indicating a waning emphasis on tourism and cultural ES in favour of addressing global-scale environmental challenges, despite the numerous benefits recreational activities provide to humans (Tufts et al., 2015; Wood et al., 2013).

This research is being published in the Environmental and Sustainability Indicators, Russo, L., Gomes, H., Murillas, A., and D'Alelio, D., 2025b. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indic.2025.100885>.

This Deliverable offers a very holistic evaluation of the multiple ES provided by Marine ecosystems and their biodiversity, including carbon storage, primary production, the provision of food and materials, and recreational opportunities (D'Alelio et al., 2021; Liqueste et al., 2013). Based on the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services

(CICES), ES fall into three main categories: (i) *regulating and maintenance*, which includes ES that ensure optimal environmental conditions for ecosystems (e.g., water quality and climate regulation); (ii) *provisioning*, which mainly includes ES related to the direct provision of goods such as food and materials; and (iii) *cultural*, which includes non-tangible, immaterial benefits like recreational and educational activities (Haines-Young and Potschin-Young, 2018). ES represents a vital connection between natural ecosystems and their social and economic benefits to humans (Culhane et al., 2018). In this latter respect, coastal marine ecosystems host rich biodiversity and provide ES for human populations, given their proximity to where most people live (Culhane et al., 2018). **And therefore, a key aspect is the analysis of the spatiotemporal variability of the effects of biodiversity on ES, which should be primarily investigated within marine environments** (e.g., Miller et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022).

Plankton are pivotal life forms within marine ecosystems and include highly dynamic and strongly interacting organisms spanning from unicellular to metazoan organisms. Task 6.2 (Section 1.2) analyses how Plankton provides multiple ES, such as nutrient and organic matter storage and cycling (Steinberg and Landry, 2017; Worden et al., 2015). Marine planktonic communities offer multiple ES, including the regulating and maintenance of anthropized ecosystems, food and material provisioning to industrial economic activities, and cultural values that inspire artistic expression and promote tourism. Further research needs to elucidate better the relationship between plankton biodiversity and the overall economic valuation of ES, as reductions in food security, livelihoods, income, or health can negatively impact societal well-being. Adopting a network approach is crucial for identifying trade-offs between ES values, because providing educational ES does not necessarily imply a higher societal value (monetary assessment) compared to other ES. For instance, recreation (cultural ES) and climate regulation from regulating and maintenance ES can exhibit very high monetary valuations. **Moreover, future advancements in policy-relevant information should also include the consideration of ecosystem disservices.** In the context of plankton, such disservices include harmful algal blooms or jellyfish proliferations that can adversely affect tourism and fisheries. However, ecosystem disservices quantification remains a significant challenge due to data limitations and knowledge gaps. **Phytoplankton are responsible for about half of the world's net primary production and offer a range of nutraceutical and biochemical resources** (Falkowski, 2012; Worden et al., 2015). **Zooplankton feed larger animals, from commercially exploitable planktonic crustaceans, mollusks, and fishes to iconic mammals like whales** (Kawamura, 1980; Lomartire et al., 2021). **Despite their importance, the role of plankton in providing ES is still underexplored.** Section 1.2 herein also confirmed the seasonal variability of the planktonic communities highlighting the effect of the different trophic statuses of the water on plankton communities and the ES they provide. Results suggest that the higher concentrations of chlorophyll a (i.e., a proxy for photosynthetic organisms) determines a slightly higher supply of ES provided by organisms standing at higher trophic levels when comparing eutrophic to more oligotrophic water conditions.

These results are being published in Sustainability, Russo et al., 2025a. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17031182>.

This research (Task 6.2, Section 1.3) continues offering a range of ES provided by other marine and coastal ecosystems and functional groups. Kelp forest and seagrass

foundation species yield provision services (food and shelter) and regulation and supporting services (climate change regulation and coastal protection from erosion). Water columns facilitate the role of planktonic microbiomes in regulating services and linking primary productivity to trophic transfer efficiency. Deep sea areas are a source of important ES as those linked to mesopelagic fishes, but also this research covers large-scale oceanic ecosystems including top predatory species (tunas). Megafauna diversity including epipelagic fishes of tunas and emblematic species (sea turtles, marine mammals and seabirds) are providing a vast range of food provision and cultural ES (including recreational fishing but also spiritual around the emblematic species), in addition to other regulating services (climate change regulation).

Section 1.3 expands the previous analysis (Section 1.1 and Section 1.2) though covering seven case studies, which allow to explore a wide diversity of ES contexts. **This diversity is reflected in the variety of ES categories, the heterogeneity of ES providers, the range of habitats where ES are delivered and the breadth of management contexts, encompassing regional and international scales.** This coverage enables a transversal and integrative discussion across all case studies, bridging ecological, functional, and governance dimensions of ES. CS 1 focuses **on mesopelagic fishes**, which are fish species that inhabit the mesopelagic zone of the ocean, typically found at depths between 200 and 1,000 meters below the surface. The importance of this example relies on the economic valuation of ES that are loss/win when deciding to exploit the mesopelagic layer. CS 2 **spotlights on diadromous fishes**, which are species that migrate between freshwater and marine environments during their life cycle, which confers them a valuable example. This migration is typically linked to reproduction, growth, or feeding, and is a key ecological trait that influences their biology and conservation. CS 3 concentrates on **tropical tunas**, mainly including skipjack (*Katsuwonus pelamis*), yellowfin (*Thunnus albacares*), and bigeye tunas (*Thunnus obesus*). This CS 3 is presented as a large example beyond EU waters. CS 4 focuses on another tuna species: the **Atlantic Bluefin Tuna**. CS 5 aims to study system **seagrass-lucinid-bacteria**. In this system seagrass hosts lucinids, which in turn host bacteria, and chemosymbiosis relations occur between them. In particular, the seagrass species considered here is *Cymodocea nodosa*. CS 6 focuses on **holobionts sponges-microbes**. A holobiont refers to a host organism and all of its associated microorganisms, including for example bacteria, archaea, fungi, viruses, and protists, forming a biological unit. This concept emphasizes that the host and its microbiota function together as an ecological and evolutionary entity. Especially, *Agelas oroides* and *Chondrosia reniformis* are studied here. Finally, CS 7 pays attention on **plankton**, which is a diverse group of tiny organisms that drift in aquatic environments, primarily in oceans, seas, and freshwater bodies.

A participatory approach has been followed to identify the ES delivered by those groups of species from which the key ones have been monetary and/or economically assessed using different accounting methods. First, the biophysical characterizations of the ES were done, followed by their conversion into either economic (including the consumer surplus, or the willingness to pay) or monetary values (these last values represent just a market-based valuation). These valuations can be operationalized through the development and application of several methods specifically related to each of the ES such as, direct market valuation approaches, revealed preference approaches and stated preferences approaches. Many uncertainties and barriers were stated when building a first economic approach for those

functional groups which will prevent in the future the adoption of an ES approach in decision making, further from specific case studies' valuations.

Overall, marine ecosystems have been evaluated in terms of their higher or lower yearly-based contribution to the human wellbeing, selected along a 3D gradient from estuaries to deep oceans, together with keystone holobionts, plankton and seagrass. Focusing on absolute values the highest economic estimation of ES is reached for plankton in Gaeta Gulf with 7.10- Food for higher trophic levels while the lowest is for system seagrass-lucinids-bacteria along the Slovenian coast with 5.2- Carbon sequestration. By summing the contribution of all the ES, expressed in absolute terms, plankton in the three gulfs of Italy presents the highest economic estimations, ranging from 23 to 2,153 million €₂₀₂₄, followed by tunas in tropical Atlantic ecoregion (from 448 to 452 million €₂₀₂₄), diadromous fishes in EU Atlantic Area (considering 2.1 and 2.4, from 23 to 43 million €₂₀₂₄) and finally seagrass in Slovenia (from 0.6, considering system seagrass-lucinids-bacteria, to 10 million €₂₀₂₄, considering seagrass alone). When focusing on total economic values per square meter, the highest economic estimation is obtained for seagrass, followed by plankton and finally tropical tunas. However, any position in this ranking all of these groups provide valuable ES. This result seems consistent with literature, since seagrass and plankton are expected to be particularly organisms delivering valuable ES (Costanza et al., 1997 and Grigoratou et al., 2025). The yearly-based contribution to these groups should be taken as an additional criterion for the protection and restauration of marine and freshwater habitats, including benthic and epipelagic habitats. Moreover, the figures also contrast with the substantial uncertainty and variability in the expected outcomes from a new exploitation of the mesopelagic layer. Offering for the mesopelagic fishes (CS1) a wide confidence interval, ranging from a potential gain of 57.59 million €₂₀₂₄ to a loss of 50.68 million €₂₀₂₄, which underscores the substantial uncertainty and variability in the expected outcomes which should crucially be considered in decision making.

Overall, considering just 8 of ES assessed out of the 50 identified, the sum of their economic values represents an underestimated contribution (like an *annually yield*) of the EU natural capital in terms of social benefits, reaching an aggregated value (yearly based), based on evaluated EU ecosystems, which range between €0.4 and €2.2 Billion. Beyond EU waters, the tropical tuna delivers €0.4 Billion at epipelagic ecosystems. Notice the Environmental Protection Expenditure (EPE) in the EU reached in 2023 a 2.1% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The EPE includes the protection of biodiversity, but also the expenditure related to the abatement of air, water, soil and noise pollution, the management of wastewater and waste, and environmental research and development. Being the ES values provided by those EU CS around the 0.01 % of the GDP in 2024. And therefore, the expenditure in protection is relatively poor to cover the huge value provided by those ecosystems. Similarly, and more specifically for marine ecosystems, the Commission adopted in 2025 the first – ever European Ocean Pact with € 1 billion to protect marine life and strengthen blue economy (https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/european-ocean-pact_en). This investment represents a very low value in contrast to the natural and yearly based ecosystems' contribution to the society measured through the ES valuation.

The **Section 2 offers a complementary method to the collection of natural capital accounting methods applied in Section 1.3.** Also offering a good complement of the Section 1.2, coming back to the key example of Plankton, as the base of marine food webs, playing a

critical role in the provision of essential benefits to society such as food, climate regulation, health, and recreation. Valuation of marine biodiversity is particularly challenging due to its complexity, public unfamiliarity, and often strong non-use values (Hanley et al., 2015; Jobstvogt et al., 2014). This deliverable provides **the results obtained after applying deliberative approaches – which combine preference elicitation with improved information provision and group reflections based on discussions – that, may provide more reliable insights, especially with such challenging environmental public goods** (Bartkowski, 2017; Kenter et al., 2016). A central element of the Deliberative Monetary Value design was the **deliberation phase**. In each of the workshops developed, a semi-structured discussion was facilitated around three guiding topics: the perceived complexity of plankton-related ES, participants' own exposure to potential changes, and the role of conservation when scientific outcomes are uncertain. The discussion aimed to encourage preference formation, allow reflection on societal (rather than purely individual) perspectives, and make participants' underlying values more explicit. Moreover, the implemented scenario served as the foundation for the Discrete Choice Experiment, with its attributes reflecting the expected changes associated with the new policies.

In general, respondents were more likely to choose an alternative policy options rather than the business-as-usual scenario. A monetary value is estimated in this Deliverable, and it could be interpreted as the level of compensation respondents would require if the business-as-usual scenario were implemented in the future. The mean responders' willingness to pay for the continued provision of plankton-based ES exceeded their willingness to pay for the control of bloom events, reflecting the limited importance respondents assigned to this attribute. The high WTP for plankton-based ES can be interpreted as an *insurance value* (Bartkowski, 2017; Pascual et al., 2015) - reflecting the importance of safeguarding ecosystem functions and future benefits - rather than as the value of supporting services in the ES classification. This distinction is crucial for ensuring consistency between valuation approaches, as incorporating Deliberative Monetary Value estimates directly into Natural Capital Accounting could lead to double counting. **Instead, the two approaches should be viewed as complementary.**

Key findings summary

1. Functional Approach to Marine Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services

- The research applies a functional approach to biodiversity, using natural capital accounting to measure the economic contribution of marine ecosystem functions and services, and investigates public and expert motivations for valuing and protecting marine biodiversity.

2. Shifting Research Priorities Toward Global Environmental Challenges

- There is a clear shift in research focus from localized issues (like water purification and recreation) to global challenges, especially climate change and blue carbon systems, reflecting the increasing importance of climate regulation and carbon storage in policy.

3. Plankton and Key Marine Ecosystems as Major Providers of Ecosystem Services

- Plankton, seagrass, kelp forests, and megafauna are pivotal in delivering essential ecosystem services such as food provision, climate regulation, and cultural benefits. Plankton plays a critical role in nutrient cycling, primary production, and supporting higher trophic levels.

4. Economic Valuation Reveals Underestimated Social Benefits

- The economic valuation of ecosystem services across diverse marine habitats shows that their annual contribution to human well-being is substantial. Indeed, considering only 8 of 50 ES identified, its economic value range from €0.4 to €2.2 billion.
- By balancing this value with the €1 billion allocated to protect marine life by The European Ocean Pact (2025), it appears that current protection expenditures are relatively low compared to the actual value provided by marine ecosystems.

5. Need for Integrated Valuation Approaches and Consideration of Ecosystem Disservices

- Combining deliberative monetary valuation with natural capital accounting offers a more holistic understanding of marine biodiversity's value. It is crucial to also consider ecosystem disservices (e.g., harmful algal blooms) and uncertainties in economic valuation to inform better decision-making and policy.

6. Current GAP: towards Holistic Ecosystem Services Assessment and Management

- Currently, decision-making in EU is in general not considering ecosystem services, excluding them from advice in decision making, and management decisions.
- To achieve more holistic and/or robust ecosystem services assessments than currently available, significant gaps must be addressed: improved data collection for biophysical and economic characterizations — whether through creation or refinement of already available data — and the development of new methodologies. Addressing these gaps will require additional resources in terms of time, funding, and personnel.

Introduction

The concept of natural capital, appeared in Schumacher (1973), is defined by the Nations United Nations (1997) in their *Glossary of Environmental Statistics* by “natural assets in their role of providing natural resource inputs and environmental services for economic production”. In the framework of the System of Environmental-Economic Accounting (SEEA) the concept is extended “beyond nature as a source of raw materials for production (e.g. timber) to include the role of the environment and ecosystems in supporting human well-being through the supply of such important goods and services as clean water, fertile soils and valuable genetic resources” in which the focus is no longer only on economic production ([SEEA](#)). In that context, [Eurostat](#), one of the Directorates-General of the European Commission, defines ecosystem services (denoted as ES) as “the range of benefits provided to humans by healthy ecosystems”. However, it can be noticed that, over the years, several definitions of ES have been proposed by different authors, highlighting that this concept is still evolving (Häyhä and Franzese, 2014, Müller et al., 2015).

ES can be framed in several classifications including CICES ([Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services](#)) (Haines-Young and Potschin-Young, 2010, Haines-Young and Potschin-Young, 2018), TEEB ([The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity](#)) (TEEB, 2012) and MEA ([Millenium Ecosystem Assessment](#)). Nowadays, the most used classification in Europe is the CICES (Flood et al., 2020). The fundamental characteristic of this classification is its flexibility and hierarchy which allows it to be adapted to different thematic and spatial scales of studies depending on their aim (Czúcz et al., 2018). In this framework the ES are divided into three main categories: provisioning, regulating and maintenance and cultural services. The SEEA defines the first ones as “the material and energy contribution generated by or in an ecosystem, for example, fish or plants with pharmaceutical properties”. For the second ones, it indicates that they “result from the capacity of ecosystems to regulate climate, hydrologic and biochemical cycles, Earth surface processes and a variety of biological processes”. Finally, it signifies cultural services “are generated from the physical settings, locations or situations that give rise to intellectual and symbolic benefits obtained by people from ecosystems through recreation, knowledge development, relaxation and spiritual reflection.” This classification puts emphasis on biogeophysics and economics while social sciences take a back seat (Kadykalo et al., 2019, Norgaard, 2010). To integrate and embrace a broader set of views and stakeholders Nature’s Contribution to People (NCP) can be considered (Díaz et al., 2018, Pascual et al., 2017). This approach, proposed by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services ([IPBES](#)), divided them in 18 categories and defined them as “all the contributions, both positive and negative, of living nature (i.e., diversity of organisms, ecosystems, and their associated ecological and evolutionary processes) to the quality of life for people” (IPBES, 2017). In 2019, IPBES evaluated that 14 of the 18 categories of NCP were declining between 1970 and 2019 (IPBES, 2019).

This research grounds the economic assessment and conservation strategy of marine ecosystems in a functional approach to biodiversity. **This supposes, among other things, to estimate the measurement of the economic contribution of ecosystem functions and ecosystem services (ES) through applied natural capital accounting procedures (task**

6.2). But also, the investigation of experts' and public's motivations for the valuation and protection of marine biodiversity along the European coast (task 6.3).

Task 6.2 provides a set of techniques to develop a general overview of the ES delivered by a high variety of habitats and functional groups. A topic modelling approach combined with systematic review conducted to select a few coastal and marine habitats and key species and go ahead to identify the ES delivered. Kelp forest and seagrass foundation species yield provision services (food and shelter) and regulation and supporting services (climate change regulation and coastal protection from erosion). Water columns facilitate the role of planktonic microbiomes in regulating services and linking primary productivity to trophic transfer efficiency. Deep sea areas are a source of important ES as those linked to mesopelagic fishes, but also this research covers large-scale oceanic ecosystems including top predatory species (tunas), linked to WP5. Megafauna diversity including epipelagic fishes of tunas and emblematic species (sea turtles, marine mammals and seabirds) are providing a vast range of food provision and cultural ES (including recreational fishing but also spiritual around the emblematic species), in addition to other regulating services (climate change regulation).

Once the ES are identified, a physical but also monetary valuation for some of them is provided for the identified marine habitats, functions, species, and ecological networks to apply natural capital accounting methods. The choice of habitats (benthic, water columns, deep seas, coastal areas) involves the assessment of a variety of functions and services both in terms of value provision, function regulation, and human intangible values (cultural and spiritual). Standard economic accounts based on direct market goods and services valued at real markets will be used to provide an assessment of provisioning ecosystem services (ES). For non-market goods and services, shadow prices are assessed by using stated preferences (contingent valuation). Moreover, Deliberative Monetary Valuation (DMV) workshops were run by Task 6.3 at strategic locations during the TREC expedition (WP1). In DMV, small groups of participants explore their values for different policy options through a process of group deliberation, thereby addressing the information gaps and normative complexity involved in the valuation of environmental public goods, such as biodiversity and ecosystem services (Schaafsma et al., 2018). DMV provides an effective tool for democratising valuation and guiding more sustainable and equitable decisions (Vargas et al., 2017). We elicit preferences of individuals to reveal trade-offs between values and interests associated with the protection of marine ecosystems.

Task 6.3 aimed at integrating public attitudes with respect to the valuation of marine ecosystems along the European littoral, building upon existing contributions on social and relational values and the role of deliberation in their uncovering (Bartkowski & Lienhoop, 2018; Chan et al., 2018; Hansjürgens et al., 2017; Kenter et al., 2019; Massenberg, 2019; 2021). A set of 15 DMV workshops along the TREC route (2-3 per selected stop, chosen among longer stops (Kristineberg, Tallin, Bilbao, Porto, Villefranche, Naples, Crete), so as to capture the diversity of values and preferences towards marine ecosystems and the services/benefits they generate. Based on a unified methodology, this research disentangled cultural specificities in this context. In each country, a 'control' workshop was conducted in another location, away from the coast. As a result, it is obtained both quantitative data from a questionnaire (contingent valuation or discrete choice experiment) and qualitative data (audio and/or video) to generate a broad understanding of motivations and underlying fundamental values that drive preferences for marine biodiversity and ecosystem services.

1. Natural capital accounting of selected habitats, functions, and services (Task 6.2)

1.1 General overview: Identification of the ecosystem services derived from coastal and marine communities

1.1.1 Introduction

Water covers 71% of the Earth's surface, with marine ecosystems accounting for about 97% of all aquatic ecosystems (Bigg et al., 2003). Due to their vast extension, marine ecosystems significantly influence global climate and provide economic and social benefits to humanity (Costanza, 1999). In this context, coastal areas host around one-third of the world's population (Finlayson, 2016) and contribute to more than 60% of the planet's total economic value (Costanza et al., 1997). These areas are also among the most prominent providers of ecosystem services (ES) in the natural environment (Mehvar et al., 2018). Numerous studies have delved into the analysis, identification, and revision of marine ES, as well as the intricate relationships between marine biodiversity and these services (e.g., Buonocore et al., 2021; D'Alelio et al., 2021; Liqueste et al., 2013). These reviews have explored ES provided by marine organisms spanning from the smallest ones, such as phytoplankton (e.g., B-Béres et al., 2023; Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023) and zooplankton (e.g., Botterell et al., 2023; Lomartire et al., 2021), to the largest one, such as seagrasses (e.g., do Amaral Camara Lima et al., 2023), fish (e.g., Ashley et al., 2023; Prellezo et al., 2024), and whales (e.g., Cook et al., 2020). However, much of this research has predominantly relied on bibliometric evaluations (e.g., Buonocore et al., 2021; Capasso et al., 2024) or traditional narrative reviews (e.g., B-Béres et al., 2023; Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023). While valuable, these methods often exhibit limitations when addressing broad thematic topics, as they tend to cover only limited time frames or a narrow selection of studies, introducing potential subjectivity and lacking a comprehensive, holistic perspective (Syed et al., 2018). Consequently, to effectively synthesize the growing body of scientific literature (e.g., Marginson, 2022; Miguel et al., 2016), researchers are increasingly turning to advanced methodologies, such as those provided by topic modeling techniques (Boyack and Klavans, 2014; Westgate et al., 2015).

In this context, latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) topic modeling represents a powerful tool for uncovering the underlying thematic structure within a collection of documents and identifying hidden textual patterns (Zuliani et al., 2021). LDA topic modeling enables the conceptual identification of topics in a textual dataset as represented by groups of words that co-occur more frequently than casually (Hu, 2009). This approach provides a practical, fast, and replicable method for analyzing and revising extensive publication datasets (Mohr and Bogdanov, 2013). Due to its utility, LDA topic modeling allowed scientists to revise themes such as fisheries (Syed et al., 2018; Syed and Weber, 2018), trait-based ecology of fishes (Luiz et al., 2019), microplastic (Rezende and Moretti, 2023), ecological and economic aspects in marine science (Hay Mele et al., 2019), marine debris (Tomojiri et al., 2022), maritime industry (Shin et al., 2018) and transport (Bai et al., 2021), hydropower (Jiang et al., 2016), and sustainability in the ocean economy (Kang et al., 2023).

LDA has proven effective in highlighting temporal trends within various research fields. For instance, Luiz et al., (2019) observed a shift in methodologies used to study functional traits in marine and freshwater fishes, specifically, an increasing adoption of

functional diversity metrics alongside a decline in the use of reproductive trait models, which traditionally examined energy allocation strategies in fish reproduction. Similarly, (Bai et al., 2021) demonstrated that maritime transportation research has evolved from a focus on policy and management toward more integrated and sustainable transport solutions. Kang et al., (2023) reported a declining interest in countermeasures for oil spill damage and a growing emphasis on the development of renewable energy sources aimed at reducing carbon emissions.

The present study aims to provide an objective overview of marine ES research based on publication data from the Web of Science (WoS) spanning thirty-four years (January 1990 – December 2024). The approach applied herein employs the LDA topic modelling analysis to examine the main research themes in the marine ES and track topic changes over time.

1.1.2 Material and Methods

1.1.2.1 Bibliographic data acquisition

We performed a bibliometric analysis of scientific literature concerning marine ES. A publications' dataset was compiled from the Web of Science database, covering all years up to December 2024, and retrieved by topic. The search comprised all types of publications (e.g., articles, book chapters, reviews), and employed three specific keyword sets within the titles, abstracts, and keywords of the documents:

i) Keywords describing the whole marine ecosystem: marine OR sea OR ocean OR coastal OR shelf OR estuary OR "deep sea" OR abyssal OR abyssopelagic OR hadopelagic OR bathypelagic OR mesopelagic OR canyon OR pelagic OR demersal OR "abyssal plain"; AND

ii) Keywords representing key organisms characteristics of the marine ecosystems, identified in consultation with experts from the European BIOcean5D project, including "kelp forest" OR seagrass OR *Posidonia* OR *Zostera* OR *Cymodocea* OR diadromous OR anadromous OR catadromous OR "reef*" OR shark* OR megafauna OR tuna* OR seabird* OR "sea turtle*" OR "marine mammal*" OR fish* OR plankton OR bacteria OR archaea OR diatom* OR phytoplankton OR zooplankton OR copepod* OR jellyfish OR bivalv* OR oyster* Or sponge*;
AND

iii) Keywords associated with marine ES, based on the ES classification proposed for marine ecosystems by Liqueete et al., (2013), which integrated and simplified different classifications coming from the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA) (Finlayson, 2016), The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB) (Kumar, 2012), and CICES (Haines-Young and Potschin-Young, 2018): "ecosystem services" OR "food provision" OR "water storage" OR "water provision" OR "biotic material*" OR biofuel OR "water purification" OR "air quality regulation" OR "coastal protection" OR "climate regulation" OR "weather regulation" OR "ocean nourishment" OR "life cycle maintenance" OR "biological regulation" OR "aesthetic value*" OR "symbolic value*" OR recreation OR tourism OR "cognitive effect".

The resulting dataset (**Supplementary Table 1 from Russo et al., 2025b**) was then imported into R version 4.3.2 (R Core Team, 2024), where paper titles and abstracts were combined into a single column, following the methodology outlined in previous studies (D'Alelio et al., 2021; Hay Mele et al., 2019; Russo et al., 2024).

1.1.2.2 Topic modeling

The derived title-abstract dataset was utilized for topic modeling (Zuliani et al., 2021) using the `lda` (Chang, 2024) and `tm` packages (Feinerer et al., 2025) in R and following the R source codes provided by (Droste et al., 2018). Titles and abstracts from the dataset were processed to generate a Document-Term Matrix (DTM). The DTM was stemmed, i.e., a process in computational linguistics that reduces words to their root forms, and then spaces, punctuation, acronyms, numbers, and symbols were removed. Additionally, the terms occurring fewer than five times were filtered out. The refined bag of words was then subjected to topic modeling analysis using the latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) method (Zuliani et al., 2021).

In the LDA method, a topic is represented by a group of words that co-occur together more frequently than expected by chance alone (Hu, 2009). These co-occurring words convey similar meanings and refer to related subjects, thus defining the topics (Llames et al., 2023). Each document is represented as a mixture of latent topics, with each topic defined as a Dirichlet-distributed probability distribution over words. As a result, individual words can appear in multiple topics, reflecting their relevance across different thematic contexts (Droste et al., 2018; Zuliani et al., 2021). The probability that the word w_i is contained in the document d_t is given by:

$$P(w_i|d_t) = \sum_{z=1}^z P(w_i|z) P(z|d_t)$$

Where z is the latent topic, $P(w_i|z)$ is the probability of word given topic z , and $P(z|d_t)$ is the probability of topic z given the document d_t .

The LDA algorithm repeatedly assigns documents to topics and, through a variational Bayes approximation (Droste et al., 2018), produces a posterior distribution that indicates probabilities for each document's topic assignment (Droste et al., 2018; Zuliani et al., 2021). The posterior topic distribution $P(z|d_t)$ provides probabilities for topic assignments of each document, from which it is possible to identify the most probable topic for each document and the most probable documents for each topic.

The number of topics to be identified must be determined a priori, although no definitive rule exists for this choice (Bai et al., 2021). Measures such as Bayesian Markov chain Monte Carlo algorithms and coherence scores can guide topic selection (Droste et al., 2018; Gan and Qi, 2021). However, applying these measures to large datasets, such as the one analyzed in this work, often results in an unmanageable number of topics that exceed what is comprehensible to a human reader (Abson et al., 2014; Droste et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2019). For example, Droste et al., (2018) and Zhang et al., (2019), by analyzing datasets of similar length to the one used here, obtained more than 400 and 100 topics as potential optimal topic numbers, respectively. To address this, we set the topic number as 9, following previous similar ES topic modeling analyses by Droste et al., (2018) and Abson et al., (2014).

1.1.2.3 Labelling topics

The LDA model identifies topics numerically, without descriptive labels (Syed and Weber, 2018). To interpret these results, we assigned descriptive labels by analyzing the 20 most probable words for each topic and examining the titles and abstracts of the 20 most probable

papers within each topic, as done in other studies (Droste et al., 2018; Llamas et al., 2023; Rezende and Moretti, 2023; Syed and Weber, 2018). Manual Inspection was supplemented with the InfraNodus text-mining platform (Paranyushkin, 2019) to analyze the main themes within the titles of the 20 top papers within each topic (**Supplementary Table 2 from Russo et al., 2025b**). This process also facilitated the identification of the main ES associated with each retrieved thematic topic. Interpretation of ES included within each topic followed the ES classification by Liqueste et al., (2013).

1.1.2.4 Analysis of topics

Connections between topics and their ES were visualized using an alluvial diagram created with the `alluvial` function (<https://github.com/mbojan/alluvial>) in R (R Core Team, 2024). Change points within time series data were tested with the non-parametric Pettitt test, implemented using the `pett` function of the `wql` R package (Jassby et al., 2025). Temporal trends (topic popularity sensu (Westgate et al., 2015) in the annual number of papers for each topic (topic frequency) and the yearly proportion of papers in each topic on the total number of papers (topic proportion) (Yang et al., 2023) were analyzed via linear regression in R (R Core Team, 2024), with publication year as the independent variable and topic frequency or proportion as dependent variables (Yang et al., 2023). Positive and negative significant regression coefficients defined, respectively, hot and cold topics (Yang et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2019). Moreover, in line with the classical concept of the Price Index—defined by De Solla Price (1970) as the proportion of references citing literature from the past five years—we examined, for each topic, the percentage of papers published within the last five years (from 2019 to May 2024) relative to the total associated with that topic.

Furthermore, to explore relationships among topics, inter-topic distances (topic similarity according to Westgate et al., 2015) were calculated using the Hellinger metric provided by the `CalcHellingerDist` function from the `textmineR` package (Jones et al., 2021), and the topics were analyzed through hierarchical clustering (Ward's method) using the `hclust` function with `ward.D` option. This comprehensive analysis provided insights into temporal trends and thematic linkages within the dataset under investigation.

1.1.3 Results

1.1.3.1 Topic modelling interpretation

The search performed on scientific literature concerning marine ES yielded 9,048 records (**Supplementary Table 1 from Russo et al., 2025b**). After analyzing the top words associated with each topic, as well as the title and abstract of key documents, the topics were described as follows: 1) Coastal protection; 2) Marine policy; 3) Coral reefs recreational activities; 4) Marine wildlife tourism; 5) Coastal tourism and recreational fisheries; 6) Climate change impact; 7) Blue carbon systems carbon storage; 8) Microbial biotic materials and biofuels; and 9) Water purification. The twenty most probable words for each topic and the assigned label for each retrieved topic are shown in (**Table 1**).

Table 1. Uncovered topics from 9,048 papers about marine ES published between January 1990 and December 2024 with assigned labels, 20 top words (i.e., words with the highest probability), and a short topic description.

Topic	Label	20 top topic terms (stemmed)	Short description
1	Coastal protection	coastal; area; model; sea; beach; wave; data; studi; develop; water; chang; map; protect; energy; eros; coast; result; structur; shorelin	Coastal protection by mangroves, seagrass, coral reefs, and salt marshes
2	Marine policy	ecosystem; manag; servic; marin; ecolog; coastal; conserv; approach; assess; provid; develop; area; fisheri; base; protect; research; human; system; impact; sustain	Marine ecosystem management and policy development
3	Coral reefs recreational activities	reef; coral; fish; speci; area; island; site; dive; marin; protect; communiti; habitat; studi; impact; artifici; diver; differ; tourism; structur; cover	Diving tourism in coral reefs
4	Marine wildlife tourism	fish; speci; shark; popul; tourism; whale; turtl; recreat; activ; area; studi; site; conserv; marin; sea; habitat; effect; data; dolphin; human	Recreational tourism involving observation of large wildlife animals
5	Coastal tourism and recreational fisheries	tourism; fish; marine; development; coastal; economic; community; fisheries; managing; local; resourc; sustain; area; environment; activ; studi; valu; recreat; industri; island	Recreational fisheries and the touristic value of coastal environments
6	Climate change impact	chang; climat; ecosystem; speci; ocean; impact; increas; sea; effect; temperatur; global; marin; model; region; communiti; fish; function; environment; product; servic	Climate regulation
7	Blue carbon systems carbon storage	seagrass; ecosystem; restor; habitat; mangrov; oyster; carbon; servic; coastal; speci; provid; meadow; sediment; communiti; forest; wetland; marsh; import; estuari; studi	Carbon sequestration in blue carbon systems
8	Microbial biotic materials and biofuels	product; marin; microbi; lipid; studi; high; biomass; acid; potenti; growth; diatom; bacteria; biofuel; microalga; cell; carbon; increas; gene; produc; activ	Biotechnological applications of microorganisms
9	Water purification	water; pollut; river; studi; qualiti; coastal; lagoon; concentr; area; sediment; lake; beach; sourc; sampl; activ; nutrient; microplast; tourism; sea; result	Water quality and pollution

The interpretations for each ES (based on (Liquete et al., (2013) classification) included within each topic are as described below (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Alluvial showing main ES (center) characterizing the topics derived (left), with colors following the corresponding ES category (right) of each identified marine ES, based on Liquete et al., (2013) classification.

Topic 1 (Coastal protection) primarily comprised studies examining the protective role of marine ecosystems such as mangroves, seagrass, coral reefs, and salt marshes, in mitigating wave action and erosion (*coastal protection* ES). **Topic 2 (Marine policy)** was the only topic not directly linked to a specific ES. Instead, it encompassed research on marine ecosystem management and policy development. **Topics 3 (Coral reefs recreational activities), 4 (Marine wildlife tourism), and 5 (Coastal tourism and recreational fisheries)** collectively addressed recreational aspects of marine ecosystems. Specifically, Topic 3 focused on diving tourism in coral reef systems (*recreation and tourism* ES), Topic 4 centered on recreational tourism involving observation of large wildlife animals such as whales, turtles, and sharks (*cognitive effect, recreation and tourism, and life cycle maintenance* ES); Topic 5 emphasized recreational fisheries and the touristic value of coastal environments (*symbolic and aesthetic values, recreation and tourism, and food provision* ES). **Topic 6 (Climate change impact)**

addressed the global issue of *climate regulation* ES. **Topic 7 (Blue carbon systems carbon storage)** focused on carbon sequestration in blue carbon systems (*climate regulation* ES), while **Topic 8 (Microbial biotic materials and biofuels)** was the topic linked to biotechnological applications of microorganisms implemented in the production of biofuel and other biochemical substances (*biotic materials and biofuels* ES). Lastly, **Topic 9 (Water purification)** dealt with the issue of water quality and pollution (*water purification* ES).

1.1.3.2 Topics' proportion, aggregation, and temporal

Topics 2 (Marine policy) and 5 (Coastal tourism and recreational fisheries), with 20.6% and 18.7% of papers, respectively, accounted for the broadest proportion within the dataset. Topics 2 and 5 shared the highest similarity, resulting in the widest paper group within the dataset (39.3%) (**Figure 2A and B**). The second largest group (20.8%) was the one including Topics 6 (Climate change impact, 10.3%) plus Topic 7 (Blue carbon systems carbon storage, 10.5%), while the third group included Topics 1 (Coastal protection, 8.4%) plus 9 (Water purification, 9.9%), accounting for 18.3% of the dataset. Lastly, Topics 3 (Coral reefs recreational activities), 4 (Marine wildlife tourism) and 8 (Microbial biotic materials and biofuels) showed the lowest similarity with other topics and represented 4.8% 8.6% and 8.0% of the dataset, respectively (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Topic modeling results from semantic analyses of the dataset. A: Proportion of papers associated with topics. B: Cluster analysis (hierarchical clustering, Ward's method) of topics based on the document-term matrix.

The overall scientific output on marine ES has shown a strong upward trend over time, marked by two distinct phases separated by a statistically significant change point between 2006 and 2007 (Pettitt.K = 324, p-value < 0.001). Regarding topic frequency, all topics were classified as “hot topics”, showing statistically significant increases in the annual number of papers over time (p-values < 0.05, **Supplementary Table 3 from Russo et al., 2025b** and

Figure 3). However, trends in topic proportion revealed more nuanced dynamics, with four “hot topics”, three “cold topics”, and two topics that were neither hot nor cold (**Supplementary Table 3 from Russo et al., 2025b** and **Figure 3**). **The four hot topics with increasing trends were: topic 2 (Marine policy), 6 (Climate change impact), 7 (Blue carbon systems carbon storage), and 8 (Microbial biotic materials and biofuels) (Figure 3).** Conversely, the three cold topics with decreasing trends were **Topics 3 (Coral reefs recreational activities), 5 (Coastal tourism and recreational fisheries) and 9 (Water purification) (Figure 3).** Analyzing the percentage of papers published within the last five years relative to the total in each topic, we observed that about half of the dataset (52.4%) was released during this period. The lowest percentage was found in Topic 5 (43.5%), while the highest was in Topic 7 (61.9%) (**Supplementary Table 3 from Russo et al., 2025b**). The percentages for the other topics were as follows: Topic 1, 54.5%; Topic 2, 55.6%; Topic 3, 48.1%; Topic 4, 48.0%; Topic 6, 58.0%; Topic 8, 49.0%; and Topic 9, 54.1% (**Supplementary Table 3 from Russo et al., 2025b**).

Figure 3. Temporal dynamics of the yearly paper publication associated with each topic. A: Annual number of papers for each topic (topic frequency). B: Annual proportion of papers in each topic on the total number of papers (topic proportion). Straight lines represent “hot

topics”, dashed lines are “cold topics”, dotted lines represent topics with no significant changes. Color coding in A and B indicates the topic as illustrated in the legend.

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1.2 Applied Natural Accounting: the role of marine plankton in providing ecosystem services based on its special role in marine ecosystems

1.2.1 Introduction

Marine ecosystems and their biodiversity provide multiple ES, including carbon storage, primary production, the provision of food and materials, and recreational opportunities (D'Alelio et al., 2021; Liqueste et al., 2013). ES represents a vital connection between natural ecosystems and their social and economic benefits to humans (Culhane et al., 2018). In this latter respect, coastal marine ecosystems host rich biodiversity and provide ES for human populations, given their proximity to where most people live (Culhane et al., 2018). As a result, coastal waters play a pivotal role in supporting key economic activities, including fisheries, aquaculture, and tourism (Costello, 2024; Hay Mele et al., 2019). Even though identifying the ES provided by all components of a marine community is essential for offering decision-makers and stakeholders the necessary information for accurate marine ecosystem management (Buonocore et al., 2021; Culhane et al., 2018), the ES assessment

of coastal waters must be improved (Buonocore et al., 2021). As the services of a specific ecosystem or region are generally linked to local biodiversity (Harrison et al., 2014; Miller et al., 2017; Sukhdev et al., 2014), the spatiotemporal variability of the effects of biodiversity on ES should be primarily investigated within marine environments (e.g., Miller et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2022).

Plankton are pivotal life forms within marine ecosystems and include highly dynamic and strongly interacting organisms spanning from unicellular to metazoan organisms (Sunagawa et al., 2020). The former includes groups like heterotrophic bacteria (prokaryotes), phytoplankton (cyanobacteria plus strictly autotrophic protists), and protozooplankton (mainly heterotrophic protists, also including 'mixotrophic' organisms capable of performing both predation and photosynthesis) (Flynn et al., 2019). Moreover, planktonic metazoans (zooplankton) include all invertebrate phyla, which are numerically dominated by the crustacean copepods, together with gelatinous organisms like jellyfish (i.e., Cnidaria, including colonial forms such as siphonophores and Ctenophora) as well as the very diverse larvae of benthic and nektonic species (Ivory et al., 2019; Sunagawa et al., 2020). Plankton communities show high spatiotemporal variability (Bellardini et al., 2024a; Bialonski et al., 2016; Jagadeesan et al., 2013), which is particularly pronounced in coastal marine ecosystems (Bellardini et al., 2024a; Hernández-Carrasco et al., 2018) characterized by steep bathymetric gradients, freshwater inputs, and human activities (Bellardini et al., 2024a; DiBattista et al., 2020; Hernández-Carrasco et al., 2018).

Plankton provides multiple ES, such as nutrient and organic matter storage and cycling (Steinberg and Landry, 2017; Worden et al., 2015). **Phytoplankton are responsible for about half of the world's net primary production and offer a range of nutraceutical and biochemical resources** (Falkowski, 2012; Worden et al., 2015). **Zooplankton feed larger animals, from commercially exploitable planktonic crustaceans, mollusks, and fishes to iconic mammals like whales** (Kawamura, 1980; Lomartire et al., 2021). **Despite their importance, the role of plankton in providing ES is underexplored, with assessments focusing only on broad groups such as phytoplankton or zooplankton rather than on the entire planktonic diversity** (e.g., B-Béres et al., 2023; Botterell et al., 2023; Lomartire et al., 2021; Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023). In this context, Naselli-Flores and Padisák, (2023) compiled an exhaustive review about the ES provided by marine and freshwater phytoplankton, while B-Béres et al., (2023) reviewed all the ES associated with freshwater and marine diatoms. Botterell et al., (2023) analyzed all the ES provided by zooplanktonic organisms such as copepods, krill, and jellyfish, while Lomartire et al., (2021) focused on the analysis of the role of zooplankton in providing food for higher trophic levels such as fish.

This study aims to explore the literature on marine plankton-related ES, identifying those provided by different plankton groups - i.e., consortia of species behaving similarly from the ecological point of view - at the global scale. Additionally, this study maps the ES identified by a literature search against 49 plankton trophic networks that include taxa belonging to the above-mentioned groups and stemming from data collected during 2 biodiversity surveys along the coastal waters of the Campania region (Gulfs of Gaeta, Naples, and Salerno) in the Tyrrhenian Sea (Mediterranean Sea). This exercise allows us to explore the relationship between the spatiotemporal variability of plankton biodiversity and the ES they provide.

1.2.2 Material and Methods

1.2.2.1 Literature Search of Global Plankton Ecosystem Services

This systematic review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) checklist (Page et al., 2021) (**Supplementary Materials S1 and S2 from Russo et al., 2025a**). The search (Web of Science database) utilized a specific set of keywords within the titles, abstracts, and keywords of papers, listed in the following text:

(i) plankton OR megaplankton OR macroplankton OR mesoplankton OR microplankton OR nanoplankton OR picoplankton OR microbial OR microbiome OR microbe* OR bacteria OR archaea OR holobiont OR prokaryote* OR cyanobacteria OR nanoflagellate* OR protist* OR protozoa* OR chlorophyt* OR diatom* OR bacillariophy* OR coccolithophor* OR prasinophyt* OR cryptophyt* OR haptophyt* OR phytoplankton OR microalgae OR euglenozoa OR alveolat* OR dinoflagellat* OR ciliat* OR ciliophora OR radiolaria OR rhizaria OR cercozoa OR mixoplankton OR mixotroph* OR protozooplankton OR zooplankton OR ichthyoplankton OR meroplankton OR “planktonic metazoa*” OR copepod* OR “planktonic crustacean*” OR calanoid* OR cyclopoid* OR jellyfish OR gelatinous OR medusae OR cnidaria* OR “planktonic tunicate*” OR salp* OR amphipod* OR chaetognath* OR cladocer* OR decapod* OR euphasiid* OR appendicularia* OR heteropod* OR ostracod* OR pteropod* OR rotifer* OR foraminifer* OR ctenophor* OR fungi OR basidiomycota OR ascomycota OR virus* OR viral (Topic)

(ii) AND marine OR sea OR ocean OR coastal OR shelf OR estuary (Topic)

(iii) AND “ecosystem services” (Topic).

The first group of keywords permitted the retrieval of the whole biodiversity within plankton, including taxa associated with prokaryotes, phytoplankton, protozooplankton, and zooplankton. The second group made it possible to associate the planktonic taxa within the context of marine ecosystems. For the latter, we used only the keyword “ecosystem services” to include only papers that strictly express the connection between plankton and the ES they provide, following Lique et al. (2013).

A PRISMA flow diagram outlining the literature-filtering process appears in **Figure 4**. The initial search yielded 728 papers (**Supplementary Table S1 from Russo et al., 2025a**). Subsequently, this work screened the titles and abstracts of all the retrieved documents for their relevance to the research theme. Only those papers that evidenced the relationship between plankton and the provision of ES participated in the subsequent analyses. This selection resulted in 27 papers analyzed to obtain a detailed description of the main ES provided by plankton. As detailed information about ES of specific plankton taxa was mainly unavailable in the literature, this work assigned ES to major plankton groups (**Supplementary Tables S2 and S3 from Russo et al., 2025a**). The ES provided by each plankton group identified from the literature review, based on the CICES classification (Haines-Young and Potschin-Young, 2018), were visualized through an alluvial diagram using the [alluvial package](#) in R version 4.3.2 (R Core Team, 2024).

Figure 4. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram showing the screening of identified records for systematic review.

1.2.2.2 Spatiotemporal Network Analysis of Plankton Ecosystem Services at a Regional Scale

This work mapped the ES identified from the literature onto 49 conceptual and unweighted plankton trophic networks (see the following paragraphs for further details) derived from taxa presence–absence data collected at 49 sampling stations during two seasonal research surveys in the frame of the FEAMP-ISSPA project (<https://feamp-isspa.it/>) (**Supplementary Table S4 from Russo et al., 2025a**). These surveys took place in autumn 2020 (September–October) and summer 2021 (June–July) along the coastal waters of the Campania region (Tyrrhenian Sea, NW Mediterranean), namely, from north to south: the Gulf of Gaeta, the Gulf of Naples, and the Gulf of Salerno. The Campania region is highly affected by human pressures from the Naples metropolitan area (ca. 4 million inhabitants) and by two of the largest ports on the Mediterranean Sea, those of Naples and Salerno (Appolloni et al., 2018; Tornero and Ribera d’Alcalà, 2014). Campania is a relevant socio-ecological area, with numerous fishery consortia, aquaculture, and maritime activities (Appolloni et al., 2018) and a rich cultural heritage attracting millions of tourists yearly (Mattei et al., 2019). During the first survey, samplings occurred at 22 stations (9, 7, and 7, in the Gaeta, Naples, and Salerno Gulfs, respectively), and during the second survey, at 27 stations (9, 12, and 6, in the Gaeta, Naples, and Salerno Gulfs, respectively). The sampling strategy and taxonomic identification

followed standardized protocols (Campese et al., 2024), which are available in Bellardini et al., (2024b). The workflow of plankton trophic network construction included the following steps: (i) taxa identification on all 49 sampling stations at the finest possible taxonomic resolution; (ii) the building of a presence–absence matrix (**Supplementary Table S4 from Russo et al., 2025a**); (iii) the definition of network nodes based on the trophic habits of retrieved taxa according to information from the literature and specific online databases like Globi (Poelen et al., 2014) (see **Supplementary Table S5 from Russo et al., 2025a**); (iv) the definition of network links (from prey to predators) based on trophic compatibility among co-occurring taxa.

Following the methodology of Keyes et al., (2021), all the ES identified by the literature search (see previous section) and associated with plankton groups took part in the planktonic trophic networks; this operation resulted in 49 meta-networks containing both planktonic and ecosystem service nodes (**Supplementary Tables S6 and S7 from Russo et al., 2025a**). These networks included two types of links: trophic interactions among network nodes and linkages between nodes and the ES they provide (from plankton to ES) (see **Supplementary Tables S6 and S7 from Russo et al., 2025a**). The linkages between the ES and protozooplankton were analogous to those among ES and phytoplankton due to the similarity of these categories in terms of phylogeny and dimensions (Mitra et al., 2023; Sunagawa et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022), and since no specific literature information was available.

This work applied network analysis to the 49 plankton trophic networks mentioned above by calculating the redundancy and the trophic level (sensu Keyes et al., 2021) for each ES (**Supplementary Table S8 from Russo et al., 2025a**), following Keyes et al., (2021), to explore the relationships between plankton biodiversity and ES. Redundancy for the ES nodes stemmed from the inDegree centrality (Keyes et al., 2021), i.e., the total incoming links associated with the planktonic taxa providing a specific ES, calculated using the `iGraph` R package version 2.1.4 (Csárdi and Nepusz, 2006). In this way, the InDegree of a node informed us about the number of planktonic taxa providing specific ES. The trophic level of the ES stemmed from the mean trophic level of ES providers (i.e., the nodes directly linked to ES nodes) (Keyes et al., 2021), calculated using the `NetIndicies` R package version 1.4.4.1 (Kones et al., 2009). The following step was to analyze, using the non-parametric pairwise Wilcoxon test in R (R Core Team, 2024), possible differences between the three gulfs and the sampling sites based on trophic level and the InDegree of the ES categories. Furthermore, the calculation of the sampling site-specific ratios (non-parametric pairwise Wilcoxon test in R) for ‘unicellular vs. metazoan’ and ‘phytoplankton vs. protozooplankton’ nodes (**Supplementary Table S9 from Russo et al., 2025a**) made it possible to characterize the relationships between plankton biodiversity, the trophic levels they occupy, and the ES they provide.

1.2.3 Results

1.2.3.1 Plankton Ecosystem Services

From the twenty-seven selected papers (**Supplementary Table S2 from Russo et al., 2025a**), several ES emerged belonging to all the three main ES categories (*regulating and maintenance, provisioning, and cultural services*, based on the CICES classification) and coming from five main plankton groups (planktonic bacteria, phytoplankton, planktonic crustaceans, jellyfish, and other zooplankton, the latter including other metazoans such as

salps, chaetognaths, and appendicularians) (**Figure 2**). Overall, the review evidenced that provisioning and regulating and maintenance were the ecosystem services categories mainly associated with different plankton groups; the cultural category was weakly associated with plankton, with planktonic bacteria absent from it.

Figure 5. An alluvial diagram showing ES (**center**, based on the CICES classification (Haines-Young and Potschin-Young, 2018)) identified from the systematic review of the literature for plankton groups (**left**), with colors following the corresponding ES category (**right**) of each identified planktonic ES.

1.2.3.2 Regulating and Maintenance Ecosystem Services

Marine plankton provides numerous *regulating and maintenance* ES, which play crucial roles in ocean *biogeochemical cycles* (**Figure 5**). Planktonic bacteria, i.e., the major consumers of dissolved organic carbon (Baird et al., 2019), are fundamental for carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur remineralization through decomposition processes (Falkowski, 2012). Planktonic bacteria reintroduce organic matter into marine communities being preyed on by protozooplankton (i.e., the so-called microbial loop; Azam et al., 1983), which in turn feed

planktonic metazoans (Baird et al., 2019). Phytoplankton performs a similar function, reintroducing organic matter and nutrients within marine communities and serving as prey for zooplankton (Duan et al., 2020; Roman et al., 2014). Moreover, diazotrophic cyanobacteria can fix atmospheric nitrogen, making it available to other phytoplankton groups and secondary consumers as organic matter (Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023). Among planktonic metazoans, copepods contribute to *biogeochemical cycles* within marine ecosystems (**Figure 5**) by transporting carbonic matter from the surface towards water column layers at higher depths as they produce fecal pellets and undertake diel vertical migration (Steinberg and Landry, 2017). Planktonic crustaceans and other zooplanktonic taxa can also remineralize carbon by eating fecal pellets produced by metazoans (Steinberg and Landry, 2017). Salps (herein within the other zooplankton group) feed on a wide range of prey, spanning from picoplankton (<2 µm) to macroplankton (up to 1 mm) (Sutherland et al., 2010), and produce fast-sinking fecal pellets (Phillips et al., 2009). The slow sinking of small-sized phytoplankton (e.g., cyanobacteria) facilitates their vertical transportation of carbon to the ocean interior (Henschke et al., 2013; Lebrato and Jones, 2011).

Carbon cycling also occurs during the sinking of the dead bodies of planktonic crustaceans and other zooplanktonic taxa like salps, which are estimated to export high amounts of carbon to the ocean bottom (Alcaraz et al., 2014; Henschke et al., 2013). Jellyfish, often seen as pests (Graham et al., 2014; Richardson et al., 2009) and a cause of damage for marine ecosystems and economies (e.g., fisheries and aquaculture) (Purcell et al., 2007), also contribute to biogeochemical cycles through feeding processes (excretion of fecal pellets) and the sinking of their carcasses (Chelsky et al., 2015; Lebrato and Jones, 2011). Altogether, through the sinking of dead bodies and the production of fecal pellets, planktonic metazoans play a crucial role in sequestering carbon from the surface to the ocean depths (*climate control*, see **Figure 5**) (Botterell et al., 2023).

Regulating and maintenance ES exploit biotic interactions occurring in plankton communities. For instance, jellyfish help control invasive species populations through predation (*biological control*, **Figure 5**). In the North Sea, jellyfish helped reduce the population of the invasive ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi* (Hosia and Titelman, 2011). Solitary and colonial jellyfish provide protection and food to copepods and small fish, harboring them under their bells or between their tentacles (Gasca et al., 2015; Graham et al., 2014). On the other hand, diatoms (phytoplankton) provide surfaces for other unicellular organisms (e.g., planktonic bacteria and cyanobacteria) to grow, facilitating ecological processes (B-Béres et al., 2023). Moreover, non-toxic phytoplankton can reduce the spread of toxic species through competition for resources (Naselli-Flores and Barone, 2011; Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023).

Moreover, plankton plays a role in indicating and regulating water conditions. Planktonic metazoans, such as copepods, respond rapidly to environmental changes (D'Alelio et al., 2016) and are used as indicators of water quality (**Figure 5**) and to assess the effects of pollutants such as heavy metals, chemicals, and microplastics on marine ecosystems (Botterell et al., 2019; Serranito et al., 2016). Some species of copepods are involved in the bioremediation of eutrophic waters by removing nitrogen and phosphorus in excess in coastal environments (Dinesh Kumar et al., 2016; Li et al., 2014). Planktonic bacteria and phytoplankton taxa, such as diatoms, are also known to degrade anthropogenic pollutants, heavy metals, and toxins, thus exerting water-quality control on marine ecosystems (Marella et al., 2020; Rodrigues-Filho et al., 2023).

Primary production is a pivotal and well-recognized ecological process associated with plankton (**Figure 5**) (Field et al., 1998). Nearly half of the global net primary production comes from phytoplankton, despite these latter organisms accounting for only about 1% of global photosynthetic biomass (Field et al., 1998; Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023). Diatoms contribute the most to this production (20–40%) (Malviya et al., 2016; Uitz et al., 2010) and are responsible for about 40% of total oceanic carbon uptake (Benoiston et al., 2017). The so-called carbon sequestration (falling into the *climate control* category, see **Figure 2**) performed by phytoplankton occurs as the oxygen produced during photosynthesis uses CO₂ as a carbon source (Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023; Rodrigues-Filho et al., 2023). Coccolithophores (phytoplankton) use this carbon to calcify their external structure, i.e., coccoliths made of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃). These structures can sink to the ocean interior and remove copious carbon from the atmosphere (Haunost et al., 2021; Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023). Collectively, the phytoplankton sequester about 20–35% of global annual CO₂ (Khatiwala et al., 2009; Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023).

1.2.3.3 Provisioning Ecosystem Services

Food

Among the ES categories, provisioning links directly with economic activities, including natural food and material supply (Haines-Young and Potschin-Young, 2018). As a foundational component of the marine food web, plankton sustains entire marine communities by serving as a primary *food for higher trophic levels* (**Figure 5**). Zooplankton play a crucial role by connecting their prey, i.e., planktonic bacteria, phytoplankton, protozooplankton, and zooplankton (Armengol et al., 2020), or larger marine metazoans such as fish, sharks, and other top predators (Lomartire et al., 2021) (*food for higher trophic levels*). This ecological process translates into economic activities such as fisheries and aquaculture, where plankton feed the animals (Lomartire et al., 2021).

In aquaculture, phytoplankton are food for zooplankton, which become nutrition for fish (Lomartire et al., 2021) (*food for higher trophic levels*). The most used food sources for cultured zooplankton, the microalgal genera *Nannochloropsis*, *Tetraselmis*, *Pavlova*, and *Isochrysis* (Lomartire et al., 2021; Nichols et al., 1989), are rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids and docosahexaenoic acid, which are necessary for growth, tissue development, and immunity function in the juvenile stages of fish, mammals, and birds (Lomartire et al., 2021; Nichols et al., 1989; Tocher, 2010). Diatoms (phytoplankton) also contain high concentrations of essential nutrients, and they are used as food sources within aquaculture for vertebrates and invertebrates (B-Béres et al., 2023; Peltomaa et al., 2019), as well as the larval stages of marine finfish species (B-Béres et al., 2023; Kumaran et al., 2017) (*food for higher trophic levels*).

Jellyfish are generally considered a low-quality food source due to their low specific calorific values compared to other marine species (Hays et al., 2018; Khong et al., 2016). However, they contain high-quality proteins (Khong et al., 2016) and represent a food source for many organisms, such as leatherback turtles (Hays et al., 2018; Heaslip et al., 2012), several fish species (e.g., bluefin tuna and swordfish), sea birds, and penguins (Cardona et al., 2012; Hays et al., 2018). For these reasons, jellyfish are a common food source in aquaculture, where they are eaten by planktonic crustaceans and fish (Duarte et al., 2021; Miyajima et al., 2011) (*food for higher trophic levels*). Jellyfish are also a direct source of *food for humans* (**Figure 2**), with dedicated fisheries distributed worldwide (Brotz and Pauly, 2017). They are a popular

food in Asia but not in Western countries, where policymakers still do not consider them a proper *food for humans* (Botterell et al., 2023; Graham et al., 2014). Indeed, China is the world's major consumer of jellyfish (Pauly et al., 2009), with these animals being part of the traditional diet for over 1700 years (Omori and Nakano, 2001). Their consumption in other Asian countries like Japan, Malaysia, and Singapore has significantly increased in the last century (Pauly et al., 2009).

Plankters smaller than jellyfish are seldom directly consumed by humans. Asian regions base their cuisine on planktonic crustaceans as ingredients of many traditional umami dishes (Hajeb, 2013). Planktonic crustaceans such as krill and some species of the genus *Calanus* provide oil supplements (Botterell et al., 2023; Nicol and Foster, 2016). Concerning phytoplankton, the most eaten organism by humans belongs to the freshwater genus *Arthrospira* (also known as *Spirulina*) (Araújo et al., 2021; Vonshak and Tomaselli, 2002), which is a cyanobacterium that has been harvested to provide food for thousands of years (Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023) and has been traditionally used in western countries for nutritional purposes since the 1970s (Araújo et al., 2021; Jung et al., 2019) (*food for humans*).

Health

Phytoplankton are also widely used as food and nutritional supplements (*biochemical products*), with several microalgae being important sources of antioxidants, pigments, oils, and vitamins (Araújo et al., 2021). *Spirulina*, Chlorophyta *Haematococcus* spp., and *Dunaliella* spp. can accumulate high quantities of antioxidants like astaxanthin and β -carotene (Araújo et al., 2021; Mobin and Alam, 2017). The genus *Chlorella* (Chlorophyta) has a high protein and carbohydrate content, and it is also rich in B vitamins (Araújo et al., 2021); the genus *Nannochloropsis* (Chlorophyta) is a source of eicosapentaenoic acid (Araújo et al., 2021; Mobin and Alam, 2017) (*biochemical products*). The chrysophytes *Mallomonas* and *Paraphysomonas* can produce bioactive compounds such as polyunsaturated fatty acids (Cranwell et al., 1988; Lengyel et al., 2023). The chrysophyte *Synura* produces sterols like β -sitosterol and cholesterol, which are precursors for vitamin D (Lengyel et al., 2023) (*biochemical products*). Planktonic bacteria produce compounds such as exopolysaccharides and methanol (Fenibo et al., 2023). Moreover, jellyfish are used in soil fertilizers (biochemical products) as they increase the nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium contents of the soil (Botterell et al., 2023; Emadodin et al., 2020).

Some phytoplankton genera (e.g., *Arthrospira*, *Chlorella*, *Dunaliella*, *Haematococcus*) and planktonic bacteria produce compounds beneficial to human health like antifungal, anti-viral, anti-inflammatory, and immune system stimulants (Araújo et al., 2021; Erwin et al., 2010) (*human medicine*). Several diatoms can produce high amounts of bioactive compounds such as polyphenols, carotenoids, and sulfated polysaccharides identified as immunostimulants (*human medicine*) (B-Béres et al., 2023; Sharma et al., 2021). Compounds extracted from diatoms are also reported to be effective against HIV and cancers (B-Béres et al., 2023; Mishra et al., 2017). Among the 30,000 microalgal species known, only a few are the objects of chemical composition studies, and even fewer participate in commercial cultivations (Guieysse and Plouviez, 2024; Mobin and Alam, 2017). This significant imbalance between the vast phytoplankton biodiversity in marine ecosystems and the limited number of microalgae used in biotechnology is due to the challenges associated with cultivation in artificial settings (Guieysse and Plouviez, 2024; Mobin and Alam, 2017). Moreover, as any novel species must follow the Novel Food regulations, the commercialization of new

microalgae or their products is further impeded by administrative hurdles, which promote food safety but are perceived by stakeholders as costly and time-consuming processes (Araújo et al., 2021).

Concerning metazoans, some jellyfish contain high levels of collagen, a compound used in the biomedical industry for tissue engineering and regenerative medicine, for instance, to cure osteoarthritis (Botterell et al., 2023; Hoyer et al., 2014). Jellyfish toxins are used as anticancer compounds (Graham et al., 2014; Leone et al., 2013) and antioxidant nutritional supplements (Graham et al., 2014) (*human medicine*).

Others

Several phytoplankton genera (e.g., *Botryococcus*, *Chlamydomonas*, *Chlorella*, *Dunaliella*, *Skeletonema*) can also produce large amounts of hydrocarbons, which are used for biofuel production (**Figure 2**) (Mucko et al., 2020; Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023). Lastly, planktonic bacteria, phytoplankton, and planktonic metazoans are also fundamental genetic resources (**Figure 2**) (Botterell et al., 2023; Llamas et al., 2023; Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023). For example, the Green Fluorescent Pigment, a luminescent marker extensively used in molecular experiments as a biological gene-expression marker, is isolated from jellyfish (Botterell et al., 2023; Graham et al., 2014). Diatoms are also used as genetic resources in genetic engineering studies (Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023).

1.2.3.4 Cultural Ecosystem Services

Cultural ES encompass intangible benefits related to religious, artistic, educational, and recreational values (Cabana et al., 2024). Plankton has historically inspired myths, legends, and artistic expression, contributing to *cultural heritage*, *educational values* and *recreation* (**Figure 2**). Several planktonic microalgae color surface waters during blooms, giving rise to various myths and legends (Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023). The first plague in Egypt, where fish died and people could not drink the water from the River Nile, was likely due to a harmful algal bloom (Fogg, 2002; Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023). The myth of the phoenix may have stemmed from blooms of bioluminescent dinoflagellates (e.g., belonging to the genera *Alexandrium*, *Protoceratium*, *Noctiluca*). When a bird takes off from coastal areas where these blooms occur, it appears to shine as its feathers are drenched with these bioluminescent dinoflagellates: the mechanics of flight trigger the luciferase–luciferin reaction, creating the impression of a glowing bird (Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023).

Plankton have also inspired science and art. Various species of planktonic microalgae have inspired bracelets, pendants, and earrings (Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023). The German biologist Ernst Haeckel's multivolume series *Kunstformen der Natur* (Haeckel, 1899) features intricate drawings of plankton, including unicellular organisms like diatoms and radiolaria, as well as metazoans like jellyfish, later inspiring mosaics, chandeliers, and windows in the Oceanographic Museum of Monaco, Montecarlo, and influencing Art Nouveau design and architecture (Jungck et al., 2019; Naselli-Flores and Padisák, 2023). Dinoflagellates were also represented in pioneering artworks (Schütt and Schütt, 1892) by scientist and artist Franz Schütt, who was one of the scientists who worked on the “Plankton expedition” of 1889 with Victor Hensen, i.e., the scientist that coined the term “plankton” (Dolan, 2024). Planktonic crustaceans like copepods are popular in many movies, TV shows, and cartoons (Botterell et al., 2023).

Planktonic organisms are also attractions for tourists. Jellyfish, an iconic group with several species exhibited worldwide (Graham et al., 2014), generate economic income through *recreation* and *educational values* for the public (Botterell et al., 2023; Graham et al., 2014) and provide recreational activities like scuba diving with the jellyfish *Nemopilema nomurai* in the Sea of Japan and with the jellyfish *Mastigias* in the Pacific Island nation of Palau, where over 30,000 visitors annually swim with them (Botterell et al., 2023; Graham et al., 2014). Blooms of bioluminescent species like the heterotrophic dinoflagellates *Noctiluca scintillans* and the ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi* generate tourism and a sense of inspiration, education, and recreation in those observing these natural events (Botterell et al., 2023).

1.2.3.5 Spatiotemporal Variability of Plankton Ecosystem Services

This study mapped the ES provided by plankton, resulting from a systematic literature review, on 49 planktonic trophic networks referring to plankton samples collected across two seasons and within the three gulfs of Gaeta, Naples, and Salerno along the Campania coast. The applied meta-analysis revealed the spatiotemporal variability of the relationship between plankton biodiversity and the related ES. Regulating and maintenance services were the ES potentially provided by the largest number of planktonic taxa, showing the highest redundancy (highest values of InDegree) within all the gulfs and in both the seasonal sampling surveys; cultural and provisioning ES showed similar InDegree values (**Figure 6**). This finding is further supported by the non-parametric pairwise Wilcoxon test, evidencing a general statistically significant (p -value < 0.05) difference between regulating and maintenance ES and the cultural and provisioning ES (**Supplementary Figure S1 from Russo et al., 2025a**).

Figure 6. Median inDegree values of each ES category within each gulf and sampling survey (indicated with numbers next to the colored circles, see Supplementary Tables S4, S6 and S7 from Russo et al., 2025a). 1 = autumn; 2 = summer.

Provisioning ES showed the highest variability among sampling stations, suggesting a higher influence of plankton biodiversity on this ES category (Figure 6 and Supplementary Figure S1 from Russo et al., 2025a). This observation is explained by considering the specificity of the ES included in the provisioning category (Supplementary Figure S2 from Russo et al., 2025a), like the biofuel and primary production ES (Supplementary Figure S2 from Russo et al., 2025a), which are associated with organisms able to photosynthesize (i.e., phytoplankton and mixotrophic protists). Consequently, biodiversity is more likely to impact these ES than more redundant ES (i.e., those showing a higher InDegree). Among the latter ES, food for higher trophic levels had one of the highest InDegree values, highlighting the

crucial role of plankton in sustaining marine biodiversity and economic activities such as fisheries and aquacultures.

The ES InDegree analysis across the two seasonal sampling surveys revealed a general increase in potential plankton-associated ES from autumn to summer (**Figure 6** and **Supplementary Figure S1 from Russo et al., 2025a**). The planktonic ES in the Gulf of Naples showed the highest InDegree in both seasons, followed by the Gulfs of Gaeta and Salerno (**Figure 6**).

The different environmental conditions and plankton biodiversity characteristics of each gulf and season led to notable variations in the trophic levels of the ES. Compared to the InDegree values, the analysis of ES trophic level revealed an even greater spatiotemporal variability, with a general statistically significant difference observed among the trophic levels of all the ES categories at each gulf and season (**Supplementary Figure S1 from Russo et al., 2025a**). Notably, ES from all categories exhibited higher trophic levels during summer than autumn, indicating that these ES depend on organisms with higher trophic levels during summer (**Figure 4**). Among the gulfs, the planktonic community in the Gulf of Salerno displayed the highest ES trophic levels in both seasonal surveys (**Figure 4** and **Supplementary Figure S1 from Russo et al., 2025a**). The Gulf of Naples was, in both seasons, second in rank when looking at the ES trophic levels, with the Gulf of Gaeta showing the lowest values among the gulfs in each survey (**Figure 7**) and **Supplementary Figure S1 from Russo et al., 2025a**).

Figure 7. Median trophic level values of each ES category within each gulf and sampling survey (indicated with numbers next to the colored circles, see Supplementary Tables S4, S6 and S7 from Russo et al., 2025a). 1 = autumn; 2 = summer.

The analysis of the unicellular to metazoan and phytoplankton to protozooplankton diversity ratio explains the above-mentioned results (**Figure 8**). The unicellular vs. metazoan plankton ratio was consistently higher during summer (second survey), with a slight increase in the Gulf of Naples, a large but not significant increase in the Gulf of Gaeta, and a statistically significant increase in the Gulf of Salerno (**Figure 8**). This result agrees with chlorophyll concentration, which was higher in the summer than in autumn within each of the three gulfs (Bellardini et al., 2024b). The overall increase in unicellular organisms within each gulf stemmed from a significant rise in the number of species of protozooplankton over those belonging to phytoplankton in all the gulfs from autumn to summer (**Figure 8**).

Figure 8. Boxplots for unicellular to metazoan and phytoplankton to protozooplankton ratios of each gulf and sampling survey, and heatmaps showing statistical significance of pairwise Wilcoxon test (p -value < 0.05 means samples are significantly different). 1 = autumn; 2 = summer.

1.2.4 References

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1.3 Applied Natural Accounting to ecosystem services in the water column. From coastal to deep sea ecosystems, from microbes to tuna fishes

1.3.1 Introduction

Evaluation of Nature Contribution to People (NCP) made by Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services ([IPBES](#)) in 2019, shows that 14 of the 18 categories of NCP were declining between 1970 and 2019 (IPBES, 2019). In that context it is becoming increasingly urgent to put in place effective solutions for managing natural capital. To achieve that, more and more scientists advocate the integration of economic assessments of natural capital in management processes (Costanza et al., 1997, Su and Peng, 2021). Indeed, some studies emphasise on the capacity of economics to quantify and balance trade-offs (White et al., 2012, Cowling et al., 2008), while others highlight economic values can be persuasive and/or helpful tools in management context (O'Higgins et al., 2020, Guerry et al., 2015). In particular, Spash (2013) advocates that economic assessments of ES present the most pragmatic way to communicate with political and business institutions. The implementation of this type of approach is also supported by institutional frameworks. In fact, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive ([directive 2008/56/EC of the European parliament and of the council of 17 June 2008](#)) requires Member States to assess their marine waters not only in terms of their biological and ecological characteristics (Article 8(a)), but also from a socio-economic perspective (Article 8(c)). Another example is in a report prepared by the

United Nations Secretariat and the Global Ocean Accounts Partnership in which the importance of developing tools to make “environmental values and economic benefits for policy visible given the important role of the ocean economy to livelihoods of societies and economies” is stated (Secretariat and Partnership, 2021).

However, although there is widespread consensus on the importance of integrating economic valuations into environmental and marine managements, in practice, their implementations remain complex and contested (Cowling et al., 2008, Laurans et al., 2013). Firstly, literature points out that there is not a strict consensus about the most suitable methodology for each ES (Kornatowska and Sienkiewicz, 2018, Krusberg et al., 2024, Torres and Hanley, 2016). Furthermore, Whitham et al. (2015) demonstrate that economic values obtained can diverge significantly depending on the methodologies used. At the same time, Mengist and Soromessa (2019) underline that certain ES are not, or only minimally, evaluated economically in the literature, leading in the most of cases to underestimations of total economic values of ecosystems or species. Beyond the problems arising from the assessments themselves, studies point out issues in how to integrate them in management processes (Laurans et al., 2013, Walther et al., 2025).

In that context, the main objectives of this research are to continue emphasizing the importance of monetary assessments of natural capital and initiate discussions about their utilizations in management contexts. To achieve that, various pilot case studies (CS) are considered. For each of them, ES delivered are first identified, and afterwards, several of them are estimated in terms of economic assessments. Thus, a range of monetary assessments of natural capital is provided. This approach permits us to break out of the theoretical framework in various contexts. Here, the focus is on biotic components of ecosystems, which is the mainstream in Europe.

1.3.2 Material and Methods

1.3.2.1. Case Studies overview

Seven CS are considered in this section 1.3. Detailed descriptions of each CS are available in **Appendix A.1.1. Figure 9** shows that they are distributed between EU waters and international waters. At EU level marine waters, the Mediterranean Sea (CS 5, 6 and 7), the North Sea (CS 4) and the Bay of Biscay (CS 1) are covered at different scales (for example regional scale in CS 6 and international in CS 1). CS 2 also focuses on EU waters, including part of the North Sea, the Bay of Biscay and the Portuguese Coast. Regarding international waters, CS 3 is being developed for the Tropical Atlantic Ocean. Taking all these CS into account in this study enables us to consider organisms from microorganisms (CS 7) to mega-organisms (CS 3 or 5 for example).

CS 1 focuses on mesopelagic fishes, typically inhabiting the mesopelagic zone of the ocean, typically found at depths between 200 and 1,000 meters below the surface. CS 2 spotlights on diadromous fishes, which are species that migrate between freshwater and marine environments during their life cycle. This migration is typically linked to reproduction, growth, or feeding, and is a key ecological trait that influences their biology and conservation. CS 3 concentrates on tropical tunas, mainly including skipjack (*Katsuwonus pelamis*), yellowfin (*Thunnus albacares*), and bigeye tuna (*Thunnus obesus*). Focusing on a different geographical area, CS 4 centres on another tuna species - the Atlantic Bluefin Tuna (*Thunnus thynnus*) - which provides different ES compared to CS 3 tuna species. CS 5 aims to study

the system seagrass-lucinid-bacteria. In this system, the seagrass hosts lucinids (bivalve molluscs), which in turn host bacteria, and chemosymbiosis relations occur between them. In particular, the seagrass species considered here is *Cymodocea nodosa*. CS 6 focuses on holobionts sponges-microbes. A holobiont refers to a host organism and all its associated microorganisms, including for example bacteria, archaea, fungi, viruses, and protists, forming a biological unit. This concept emphasizes that the host and its microbiota function together and form an ecological and evolutionary entity. Specifically, the sponges *Agelas oroides* and *Chondrosia reniformis* are studied here. Finally, CS 7 focuses on plankton, a diverse group of tiny organisms that drift in aquatic environments, primarily in oceans, seas, and freshwater bodies.

Figure 9: Location of the CS considered in this study, as well as main ES providers (that is, ecosystems and species delivering ES) per CS. CS 1: Mesopelagic fishes in the Bay of Biscay; CS 2: Diadromous fishes in the EU Atlantic Area; CS 3: Tunas in the tropical Atlantic Ecoregion; CS 4: Atlantic Bluefin Tuna in Skagerrak; CS 5: System seagrass-lucinids-bacteria along the Slovenian coast; CS 6: Holobionts sponges-microbes in Catalan Sea and CS 7: Plankton in three Gulfs of Italy.

1.3.2.2. Identification of ecosystem services following a participatory approach

A participatory approach is used based on specialists' expertise as well as scientific literature reviews with the aim of providing a list of ES delivered by the different ecosystems and species studied across the CS. In Section 1.1. a general overview of the most common ES provided

by marine and coastal ecosystems was developed, now complemented each other with the empirical knowledge and additional literature review. Online structured interviews with experts were organised from January 2024 to September 2025, as well as a hybrid workshop during the annual meeting of the project [BIOcean5D](#) (February 2025, Barcelona, Spain). During this workshop a dynamic exercise was set up in the visual collaboration platform [Mural](#) with the collaboration of at least one expert per CS. As highlighted in **Table 2**, the number of experts ranges from 1 (CS 4) to 4 (CS 2 and 3) and, the number of meetings, including conducted interviews and the workshop, from 2 (CS 2) to 10 (CS 7). Overall, a minimum of 36 meetings with 18 scientists were organized. However, some previous EU projects outputs have been also here capitalized, getting information from many other experts beyond BIOcean5D across a higher number of meetings. This is happening with the mesopelagic CS (EU Horizon SUMMER project) and the diadromous fishes CS (EU Atlantic Interreg DIADES project) Therefore, the number of meetings reported in **Table 2** should be considered a minimum, as additional insights have emerged informally.

An iterative Step-by-Step participatory process was followed with the help of the interviews and the workshops. Initially, a general meeting was held to explain the ES-approach concept with all CS and other stakeholders. Afterwards, this conceptual context was repeated individually at the CS level. Therefore, a template to be completed by CS leaders was shared. Its aim was to gather both empirical and scientific knowledge to identify the ES delivered by the species/habitats covered at each CS, following the CICES classification. In particular, CS leaders suggested relevant publications to be reviewed. Thus, they co-developed a preliminary list of ES, that was later validated or modified during the organization of a workshop in person, during one of the annual meetings of the BIOcean5D project. During this workshop an interactive platform was used (Mural) to validate the list, and experts were asked to classify the identified ES according to whether they are key ES or not. Key ES are defined as ES having high importance in biological, ecological, economic and/or social terms. In addition, habitats where ES are delivered were also informed by the experts.

This exercise was crosscheck with the output from the Topic Modelling approach developed as part of the Section 1.1. The intersection between ES identified through topic modelling and those getting from the empirical knowledge at the CS is showed at **Figure 10**. It should be noted that some CS shown in this figure are not included in the following sections (for example coral reefs), and conversely, some CS considered in the following sections are not shown in the figure (for example: tunas in Tropical Atlantic Ecoregion).

Figure 10: Conceptual representation of the intersection between ES identified through topic modelling and those evaluated in literature-based case studies. Red links indicate ES identified via topic modelling that are attributed to one or more groups of organisms in case studies. Blue links represent ES detected through topic modelling that have no corresponding organism groups in case studies. Dashed black links indicate ES evaluated exclusively within the reported selected case studies. **Source:** Russo et al., 2025.

Table 2: Numbers of experts consulted and meetings (including interviews conducted and workshops) for each CS

Case Studies Name	Number of experts	Number of meetings
1. Mesopelagic fishes in Bay of Biscay	2	4
2. Diadromous fishes in the EU Atlantic area	4	2
3. Tunas in Tropical Atlantic Ecoregion	4	7
4. Atlantic Bluefin Tuna in Skagerrak	1	3
5. System <i>Cymodocea nodosa</i> -lucinids-bacteria along the Slovenian coast	2	5
6. Holobionts Sponges- microbes in Catalan Sea	2	5
7. Plankton in three Gulfs in Italy	3	10

1.3.2.3. Methods to assess economically ecosystem services: an overview

Economic valuations of ES typically involve a two-step process: first, the biophysical characterizations of the ES, followed by their conversion into either economic or monetary values (these last values represent just a market-based valuation). These valuations can be operationalized through the development and application of several methods specifically related to each of the ES. Each of them includes strengths and weaknesses, influencing the valuations obtained. In this context, it is essential to understand the

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methodologies employed in conducting economic assessments to ensure their appropriate and effective application. ES economic valuation methods can be classified in four main categories: direct market valuation approaches, revealed preference approaches, stated preferences approaches and environmental benefit transfers (Legesse et al., 2022, Pascual et al., 2012, Johnston et al., 2021). The first ones are useful for assess, in monetary values, ES which are directly linked to market transactions while others are mostly used to evaluate economic values of ES with gaps in prices and/or direct markets information (Legesse et al., 2022). It is also key to consider certain uncertainties surrounding the ES valuation, reason why option value techniques are useful to introduce uncertainty in the ES monetary valuation. The option value represents a type of expected net present value of future benefits. A detailed classification of methods is shown at **Figure 11**.

Figure 11: Traditional methods to estimate the monetary value (for market goods) or the economic value (for not market goods). **Source:** Müller et al., 2015.

Direct market valuation approaches

These approaches rely on data from existing markets. They can be separated in three main categories: market price-based methods, cost-based methods and production function methods (Koetse et al., 2015, Pascual et al., 2012). The first ones, market price-based methods, are most of the time used to assess the economic value of provisioning services, and rely on the market prices of the products provided by the ecosystem (i.e. fishes, energy, plants, etc) (Pascual et al., 2012, Ecoacsa Reserva de Biodiversidad et al., 2021). The second ones, cost-based methods, economically evaluate ES by estimating the non-spent money due to their delivery. These methods are most frequently used to estimate regulating

and maintenance services. They can be divided into three approaches: replacement cost, mitigative expenditures and damage cost avoided. The first estimates the value of the ES based on the costs that would be incurred if artificial technologies had to perform their function (Notaro and Paletto, 2012). The second one refers to the expenses incurred to counteract the impacts resulting from the degradation or loss of ES (Legesse et al., 2022). The third approach assesses the value of ES by estimating the costs that would arise if their loss led to damage to property, infrastructure, or production systems (Wiehl and Manns, 2014b). Lastly, the production function methods assess the impacts of a qualitative or quantitative change in an ES delivery (mostly regulating and maintenance service) that is reflected in the production of a measurable marketed good or service (Wiehl and Manns, 2014c).

The main advantages of these approaches is the relatively easy way to obtain the data required and the capacity to reflect actual preferences of ES' users (Pascual et al., 2012). However, experts point out that these approaches are unable to capture the non-use values of the ES, leading to underestimations of their economic values (Legesse et al., 2022). These methods can be completed by an evaluation of the consumer surplus to assess the ES in economic values.

In this study, these approaches are used in CS 1, 2, 3, 5, 6 and 7.

Revealed preference approaches

These approaches estimate the value of ES based on observations of choices and behaviour of consumers in related markets. Two main approaches for this category can be stated: the travel cost method (denoted as TCM) and the hedonic pricing method. The first one is mainly used to estimate cultural ES (i.e. recreational activity and/or site) (Koetse et al., 2015, Shrestha et al., 2002). Three main forms of TCM exists: individual TCM, zonal TCM (denoted as ZTCM) and random utility TCM (Tourkolia et al., 2015). Based on surveys, demand curve for the evaluated ES is created based of the expenses induced to enjoy this ES, as well as socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents (Koetse et al., 2015). Value of the ES is considered to be equal to the consumer surplus obtained though the demand curve. For the application of ZTCM it is necessary to firstly construct the Trip Generation Function (denoted as TGF), which estimates the estimated visitation rates for each zone as a function of collected data (i.e. costs and socio-demographic variables of respondents) (Prayaga et al., 2006). The hedonic pricing approach evaluates economic value of ES by examining how they influence the market value of goods or properties (Legesse et al., 2022). The ES assessed with this approach are used to be regulating and maintenance services and cultural services. Existing literature emphasizes that housing prices constitute the most commonly used metric within this methodology (Koetse et al., 2015).

The most underlined strength of these approaches is that estimated values are based on actual choices and behaviours of people rather than stated choices, which lead to more reliable estimations. Focusing on the limitations of these methodologies, Boyle (2003) underlines that they only capture use values. Moreover, reviews of methodologies also point that one main disadvantage is that large data sets are needed to apply the complex statistical underlying analysis and models required (Legesse et al., 2022, Koetse et al., 2015, OECD, 2018), thus inducing high costs in time and money (Pascual et al., 2012).

In particular in this study, these approaches are used in CS 4.

Stated preferences approaches

Stated preferences approaches include mainly contingent valuation and choice experiment methods (Mahieu et al., 2014). Both methods rely on surveys conducted among individuals to assess their willingness to pay (denoted as WTP) or willingness to accept (denoted as WTA), depending on whether the ES are expected to improve or be maintained, or conversely, to degrade. While contingent valuation focuses on one option regarding state of ES for respondents, choice experiments methods permit to integrate several levels of attributes (i.e. levels of money and of quality of ES delivered) (Pascual et al., 2012).

On the one hand, the main advantage of these approaches is the possibility to evaluate all ES (Koetse et al., 2015). Especially, they can be used to assess non-related markets ES and represent often the only possibility to assess non-use values (Pascual et al., 2012). On the other hand, literature questions the reliability of these methodologies. Main criticisms concern the divergence between values obtained from WTP and WTA approaches (Pascual et al., 2012), cognitive limitations in valuing unfamiliar public goods and services (Svedsäter, 2003), and scope-related biases (such as embedding, part-whole bias, or insensitivity to scope problem) (Veisten, 2007, Veisten and Navrud, 2006). However, Arrow et al. (1993) advocate that reliable evaluations can be provided by contingent valuations relying on stringent guidelines.

In this study, these approaches are used in CS 2 and 3.

Environmental benefit transfers

Environmental benefit transfers offer simplified techniques for estimating the economic values of ES by adapting and transferring valuation data from existing studies, with appropriate contextual adjustments (Wiehl and Manns, 2014a). They can be decomposed into four main forms: value transfer, single site or single study function transfer, structural preference-function transfer and meta-analysis function transfer (Johnston et al., 2021). Value transfer techniques estimate the economic significance of ES at a given site by adapting valuation data from previous studies—either as individual figures or ranges—tailored to the specific context. In contrast, function transfer approaches rely on statistical models developed from one or more existing studies, incorporating relevant variables to produce refined and site-specific value estimates for policy applications (Loomis, 1992).

The main advantage of these methodologies is to provide practical alternatives for estimating economic values of ES when constraints such as limited time, budget, or data availability prevent the implementation of original valuation studies. However, the robustness of the estimates obtained is often called into question. Moreover, each of these methodologies present strengths and weaknesses, and the selection of one of them can be a complex process as highlighted in Johnston et al. (2021).

In this study, these approaches are used in CS 1.

1.3.3 Results: a holistic ES economic/monetary valuation

1.3.3.1. Identified ecosystem services following a participatory approach

Table 3 presents the ES identified through both the participatory approach and the literature reviews. More detailed descriptions of the ES identified for each CS are available in the **Appendix A.1.1**. As shown in **Table 3**, the total number of ES and key ES identified are 50

and 28, and varies across CS, ranging from 3 (CS 4) to 15 (CS 7) and 2 (CS 1, 4) to 7 (CS 7), respectively. The most represented CICES category is Regulation and Maintenance (47%), followed by Cultural (28%) and finally Provisioning (26%). Regarding the CICES codes (version 5.1), the seven CS collectively cover 19 subcategories. In terms of Nature's Contributions to People (NCP), 12 categories are represented. Focusing on ES providers, and as indicated in Section 1.3.2.1, the inclusion of the seven CS allows us to consider a wide spectrum of providers, from microfauna (CS 7) to macroflora (CS 5) and macrofauna (CS 1 to 4). Notably, in CS 5 and 6, the ES providers are not always a single organism, but rather systems encompassing several species. Regarding the habitats where ES are delivered, this study spans a vertical dimension with coverage of zones such as the benthic, epipelagic, and mesopelagic, among others. Thus, the consideration of these seven CS allows for the exploration of a wide diversity of ES contexts. This diversity is reflected in the variety of ES categories, the heterogeneity of ES providers, the range of habitats where ES are delivered and the breadth of management contexts, encompassing regional and international scales (See Section 1.3.2.1). This coverage enables a transversal and integrative discussion across all CS, bridging ecological, functional, and governance dimensions of ES.

Table 3: ES identified for each CS. “Regulating and Maintenance” CICES category is denoted by “Regulating” with key ES blue-coloured

#CS	ES delivered	ES Name	Habitat(s)	ES Code	CICES Category & code	Relative NCP
1	Mesopelagic fishes	Fish oil and fish meal for aquaculture (Potential future fishery)	Mesopelagic	1.1	Provisioning (1.1.6.1)	12
	Mega fauna species	Food provisioning (current fishery)	Epipelagic	1.2	Provisioning (1.1.6.1)	12
	Mesopelagic fishes	Carbon sequestration due to diet vertical migration	Epipelagic, mesopelagic	1.3	Regulating (2.2.6.1)	4
	Endangered/ threatened species	Cultural value: preservation for future generations	Epipelagic, mesopelagic	1.4	Cultural (3.2.2.2)	18
2	Diadromous fishes	Food provisioning	Marine-freshwaters	2.1	Provisioning (1.1.6.1)	12
	Diadromous fishes	Nutrient transportation rivers - marine systems		2.2	Regulating (2.2.5)	7
	Diadromous fishes	Recreational fisheries		2.3	Cultural (3.1.1.1)	16
	Diadromous fishes	Cultural value (cultural local identity, brotherhood)		2.4	Cultural (3.2.1.3)	17
3	Tunas and other species	Food provisioning	Epipelagic	3.1	Provisioning (1.1.6.1)	12
	Tunas and other species	Carbon sequestration		3.2	Regulating (2.2.6.1)	4
	Large predatory species	Maintaining balance in oceanic ecosystems		3.3	Regulating (2.2.2.3)	1
	Endangered/threatened species	Cultural value: preservation for future generations		3.4	Cultural (3.2.2.2)	18
	Tuna species	Cultural value associate to the local identity of the tuna industry		3.5	Cultural (3.2.1.3)	18
	Tuna species	Recreational fisheries		3.6	Cultural (3.1.1.1)	16
4	Atlantic Bluefin Tuna	Potential future commercial fishery	Epipelagic	4.1	Provisioning (1.1.6.1)	12
	Atlantic Bluefin Tuna	Recreational fishery		4.2	Cultural (3.1.1.1)	16
	Atlantic Bluefin Tuna	Eco-tourism		4.3	Cultural (3.1.1.2)	16
5	Global system	Oxygen production	Benthic	5.1	Regulating (2.2.6.1)	4
	Global system	Carbon sequestration		5.2	Regulating (2.2.6.1)	4
	Global system	Carbon storage		5.3	Regulating (2.2.6.1)	4
	Global system	Nutrient cycling		5.4	Regulating (2.2.5.2)	7
	Seagrass	Nursery function		5.5	Regulating (2.2.2.3)	1
	Bacteria	Oxidation of sulfide		5.6	Regulating (2.2.1.3)	7
	Seagrass	Coastal protection		5.7	Regulating (2.2.1.3)	9

Deliverable 6.1. NCA and DMV of marine ecosystem services

	Seagrass	Recreation		5.8	Cultural (3.1.1)	16
	Holobionts	Genetic material		6.1	Provisioning (1.2.2.3)	14
	Holobionts	Cosmetics		6.2	Provisioning (1.1.6.2)	13
	Holobionts	Aquaculture		6.3	Provisioning (1.2.2.2)	12
	Holobionts	Carbon sequestration		6.4	Regulating (2.2.6.1)	4
6	Holobionts	Carbon cycling (DOC uptake and conversion)	Benthic	6.5	Regulating (2.2.6.1)	4
	Holobionts	Nitrification		6.6	Regulating (2.2.5.2)	7
	Holobionts	Water filtration		6.7	Regulating (2.2.5.2)	7
	Sponges	Provision of microhabitat		6.8	Regulating (2.2.2.3)	1
	Holobionts	Sulfur cycling		6.9	Regulating (2.2.5.2)	7
	Holobionts	Potential future material		6.10	Cultural (3.2.2.2)	18
	Plankton	Antioxidants		7.1	Provisioning (1.1.6)	14
	Plankton	Biofuel		7.2	Provisioning (1.1.6.3)	14
	Plankton	Food for human		7.3	Provisioning (1.1.6.1)	12
	Plankton	Genetic resources		7.4	Provisioning (1.2.2.3)	14
	Plankton	Human medicine		7.5	Provisioning (1.2.2.3)	14
	Plankton	Primary production		7.6	Regulating (2.2.6.1)	4
	Plankton	Climate regulation		7.7	Regulating (2.2.6.1)	4
7	Plankton	Biogeochemical cycles	Epipelagic	7.8	Regulating (2.2.6.1)	7
	Plankton	Water quality		7.9	Regulating (2.1.1 & 2.2.5.2)	7
	Plankton	Food for higher trophic levels		7.10	Regulating (2.2.2.3)	1
	Plankton	Biological control		7.11	Regulating (2.2.3)	10
	Plankton	Cultural heritage		7.12	Cultural (3.1.2.3)	17
	Plankton	Recreation		7.13	Cultural (3.1.1.1)	16
	Plankton	Educational values		7.14	Cultural (3.1.2.1 & 3.1.2.2)	15
	Plankton	Aesthetic value (artistic inspiration/entertainment)		7.15	Cultural (3.1.2.4 & 3.2.1.3)	15

1.3.3.2. Material and methods for biophysical characterization and economic assessment

Table 4 provides a summary of the ES economically assessed in this study, the methodologies applied, the data required for biophysical characterizations, and their respective sources of data. Across all CS, the number of assessed ES is 18. The selection of these ES is based on the relevance of the ES for the CS considered and the availability of data and methodologies to assess it. In particular, it was decided to work only with existing datasets. **Table 5** focuses on the economic data used to estimate the economic value of the ES. Since the identification (and development) of methodologies and data for each ES require extensive literature review and multiple consultations with case study providers, these steps are considered part of the study's results. Therefore, they are not included in Section 1.3.2 – Materials and Methods.

Table 4: ES economically assessed with valuation methods, data needed for biophysical characterizations and their origin

Ecosystem service	Valuation method	Method reference	Data needed	Source of the data
1.1	Market price	(Prellezo et al., 2024a)	Quantities of FO and FM obtained from mesopelagic fishery under MSY scenario	(Prellezo et al., 2024a)
1.2	Market price	(Prellezo et al., 2024a)	Landings from current fishery under BAU and MSY scenarios	(Prellezo et al., 2024a)
1.3	Market price	(Prellezo et al., 2024a)	Carbon transport due to DVM under BAU and MSY scenarios	(Prellezo et al., 2024a)
1.4	WTP from Benefit transfer function	(Amuakwa-Mensah et al., 2018, Prellezo et al., 2024a, Dowd et al., 2022)	Biomass of species under BAU and MSY scenarios Level of vulnerability of species Charisma of species	(Prellezo et al., 2024a) (Ospar, 2022) (Prellezo et al., 2024a)
2.1	Market price	(Ashley, M., et al., 2023)	Annual tons landings	Specific surveys
2.2	Replacement cost	(Morton et. al. 2017, Ashley, M., et al., 2023)	Annual nutrient load based on the number of living and dead individuals	(Poulet et. al., 2021)
2.4	Contingent valuation	(Alberini and Kahn, 2006; Cameron and Huppert 1989)	No biophysical data and/or characterization needed	Specific surveys
3.1	Market price		Landings from tuna fishery	BIOcean5D
3.2	Market price		Biomass of individuals died naturally and bycatches	BIOcean5D
3.5	Contingency valuation and econometric models	(Castilla et al., 2025 (In Press) Castilla et al., 2023)	No biophysical data and/or characterization needed	CABFishMAN EU project
4.2	ZTCM	(Tourkolias et al., 2015)	No physical characterization/data needed.	
5.1	Market price	(Zheng et al., 2009)	Net Community Production (O ₂ flow considering net primary production and respiration)	Italian PRIN2022 project ENGAGE
5.2	Market price		Quantity of CO ₂ sequestered	Obtained though photosynthesis equation

Ecosystem service	Valuation method	Method reference	Data needed	Source of the data
5.3	Market price		Quantity of CO ₂ stored	Obtained by a proportionality factor based on sequestered CO ₂ (proportionality factor based on ACCION data https://pti-oceans.csic.es/)
6.7	Replacement cost	(Ottaviani, 2020)	Rate of water filtration	(Aguilo-Arce et al., 2023)
7.7	Market price		Quantity of CO ₂ sequestered	project ISSPA—PO FEAMP Campania 2014–2020, BIOcean5D
7.9	Replacement cost	(Zheng et al., 2009)	Quantity of O ₂ produced Quantity of N uptaken Quantity of P uptaken	Obtained though photosynthesis equation Obtained though Redfield ratio Obtained though Redfield ratio
7.10	Production function		Potential planktivorous fish biomass	Project ISSPA—PO FEAMP Campania 2014–2020, BIOcean5D

Table 5: Economic data needed and references

Ecosystem service	Economic data needed	Reference
1.1	Fish Oil and Fish Meal prices	Kok et al. (2020) and IndexMundi (2021)
1.2, 3.1, 7.10	Market price of species	Annual Economic Report (AER): Prelezo et al. (2024b) and Prelezo et al. (2020)
1.3; 3.2 5.2; 5.3; 7.7 3.5	EU carbon permits Demographic, geographic indicators, fleet sizes, inventories of the cultural heritage elements, the number of fishing companies together with their sale volume and number of workers	Trading economics website Surveys and official data from national statistics. Castilla et al., 2025 (In Press) Castilla et al., 2023
4.2	Expenses induced by fishermen for recreational fishery Socio-economic characteristics of fishermen	Maar et al. (2022)
5.1; 7.7 6.7	O ₂ market price Capital and operating costs of a wastewater treatment plant of primary and secondary waste-water treatments	Business analytiq website Pham et al. (2019)
7.9	Shadow prices for N and P	Hernández-Sancho et al. (2010)
3.1; 7.10 2.1	Harmonised index of consumer prices (HICP) Diadromous fish first-sale prices	Eurostat website Surveys to the fish associations, stakeholders
2.2	Quantification of land-sea nutrient fluxes supplied by allis shad across the species' range	Poulet, C., et al., 2021
2.4	A contingent-based survey tool is used including a set of questions about awareness and affinity on diadromous fisheries, knowledge, WTP, and sociodemographic aspects.	A consumer panel. Interviews were conducted in random locations getting survey error for each location +/- 5.7%

1.3.3.2.1. CS 1: Mesopelagic fisheries in Bay of Biscay

To capture the system's dynamics (including populations and fisheries dynamics), an Ecopath and Ecosim (EwE) model (Christensen and Walters, 2004) is built for the Bay of Biscay. It includes 52 functional groups, denoted as FG, and 13 fishing fleets (Appendix A.1.2). As explained in the Appendix A.1.1.1, this CS relies on a fishery that does not currently exist, thus it is not possible to present a 'snapshot' of the current values of the ES associated with this fishery. In this context, the economic assessment for each ES for this CS is presented in terms of Average Present Value, APV, calculated for the period 2020-2050, expressed as:

$$APV_{ES} = \sum_{t=2020}^{T=2050} \left[\frac{FV_{ES,t}}{(1+r)^t} \right] * \frac{1}{(2050 - 2020)}$$

In which FV is the difference of the future value of the ES considered under Maximum Sustainable Yield (denoted as MSY) and Business As Usual (denoted as BAU) scenarios (See Section A.1.1.1). The discount rate, r , is fixed at 4.25% (Boyce, 2018).

Two provisioning services are considered: 1.1 - fish oil (denoted as FO) and fish meal (denoted as FM) for aquaculture provided by the potential mesopelagic fishery, as well as 1.2 - food provisioning from current fisheries. For both, FV is obtained by multiplying the difference of landings of fished species between both scenarios by the market prices. Regarding the regulating and maintenance services, 1.3 - carbon sequestration realized by mesopelagic fishes is assessed based on diet vertical migration (denoted as DVM). DVM refers to their daily movement toward surface waters at night to feed on zooplankton and other prey, and back to deeper, darker waters during the day to avoid visual predators—linking deep-sea and surface ecosystems through their feeding behaviour. Three processes of the DVM are considered: respiration flux, egestion and excretion (Davison et al., 2013). For this ES, FV is obtained by multiplying the difference of biomass of mesopelagic fishes between both scenarios by quantity of CO₂ sequestered per unit of biomass and EU carbon permits values. Finally, 1.4 - cultural value of charismatic species with special focus on endangered and threatened species 'values are estimated based on WTP, obtained through a benefit transfer function (Amuakwa-Mensah et al., 2018). Specially, the value of the WTP depends on the levels of vulnerability and charisma of the species. The FV of this ES is obtained by multiplying the difference of biomass of these species by the WTP per unit of biomass obtained.

To account for uncertainties in model parameters and ecosystem responses, 95% confidence intervals for all APV estimates are provided. This allows the presentation of minimum, maximum, and mean values for each ES, offering a more robust basis for interpreting trade-offs.

More information about the model and the methodologies to assess the APV of each ES are available in Prellezo et al. (2024a).

1.3.3.2.2. CS 2: Diadromous fishes in EU Atlantic Area

The most relevant biophysical data is needed to estimate the value of the 2.2 - nutrient transportation (regulating ES). The total nutrient load, i.e., the amount of Nitrogen (N), and Phosphorus (P) imported into an estuary by fishes is calculated by summing the carcass decomposition from in-migrating spawners, their gamete emission, and their excretion. The total nutrient load exported from an estuary is calculated from the out-migrating juveniles.

Subtracting exported load from the imported load provides the total nutrient load. A nutrient calculator implemented in a mechanistic species distribution model called GR3D (Global Repositioning Dynamics for Diadromous fish Distribution) was developed by Poulet et. al., 2021 to help understand the nutrient load associated with shad species. The routine automatically computes the nutrient load over time based on the number of living and dead individuals which is provided by GR3D. Results were averaged over the 1900-1930 period, under no anthropogenic influences. Also, for the commercial fisheries, the annual tons landings are used to estimate the 2.1- food provisioning ES. Finally, statement-based methods for the cultural ecosystem services were used. A set of surveys or questionnaires to elicit market values were developed involving individual respondents (Fischhoff, 1991 and Satterfield, 2001). The questionnaires built to cover on the one hand, a set of informative questions (narratives on the different cultural ecosystem services – non-market based) and on the other, a set of questions to get knowledge on the intrinsic value of certain cultural ES. To catch the cultural value of the diadromous fish commercial fisheries (2.4) a contingent valuation exercise was implemented (Alberini and Kahn, 2006) where respondents were asked about their WTP for preserving the existence of certain commercial fisheries or recreational fisheries. The payment proposed was a 'once in a lifetime donation' and the money raised would be exclusively used for that program.

1.3.3.2.3. CS 3: Tunas in Tropical Atlantic Ecoregion

An EwE model, including 36 FG as well as 15 fleets (Appendix A.1.3), is developed to evaluate ecosystem dynamics in the Tropical Atlantic Ecoregion. Based on the outputs of this model two ES are assessed: 3.1- food provisioning and 3.2- carbon sequestration. The first one focuses on European fisheries (French and Spanish Purse Seiners, fleets 1 to 4 in Appendix A.1.3). The economic value for this ES is obtained by multiplying the landings by the market prices of the commercial species, which were extracted from the Annual Economic Report (AER). The carbon sequestration is assumed to be realized by some species¹ when they die in open ocean. Thus, the biomass of individuals who died naturally (i.e. from senescence, disease and starvation) (Mouillot et al., 2023) is considered, as well as bycatches, as they are assumed to be discarded at sea. As in Mariani et al. (2020), low and high estimations are considered based on percentages of carbon in individuals of, respectively, 10% and 15% (Bar-On et al., 2018), leading at low and high economic assessments for this ES. Assessments are based on outputs' model for 2022; market prices of 2022, actualized through Harmonised Index of Consumer Prices (HICP) data in 2024, and value of EU carbon permits for 2024. 3.5- cultural value of the tuna requires of a complex combination of methods. For the cultural heritage elements, ports and landscape, the social practices, the food and gastronomy and the tangible fixed assets were considered (identified thanks to a previous project ([CABFishMAN](#) INTERREG Atlantic). A stratified random sampling of 1524 online surveys administered to residents in households in Spain, aged 18 years old or older were used to derive the WTP. However, in addition to this previous information on cultural elements, this research has completed the data with a collection of additional variables that have allowed us to distinguish between the WTP to protect the cultural heritage of industrial fleets and fisheries in relation to the value attached to smaller fleets. The method consisted of estimating an econometric model in which the dependent variable uses as the average WTP and the independent variables were the origin or the visitors and the cultural elements, the proportion

¹ FG considered for this ES are indicated in **Table 13** (Appendix A.1.3).

of semi-industrial and industrial ports with respect to the total number of ports, and, the proportion of spending on tourism activities with respect to the average total per capita spending. The model includes a total of 49 variables to act as predictors of the WTP both themselves and indicators based on them, or cross products, either with numerical variables or with the artificial variables considered.

1.3.3.2.4. CS 4: Atlantic Bluefin Tuna in Skagerrak

To understand the biological and ecological dynamics underlying the recovery of Atlantic Blue Fin Tuna in Skagerrak, Maar et al. (2022) implemented, between 2017 and 2021, a targeting program based on catch and release fishery realized by recreative fishermen. Only fishermen taking part on this program were allowed to realize this fishery. In order to evaluate the economic impacts of reopening this recreative fishery, scientists also implemented an economic survey among these fishermen from 2018 to 2020. This survey permits to obtain information about the expenses induced by fishermen to realize the recreational fishery as well as some socio-demographics characteristics. Based on the data collected in this survey a TCM is applied to evaluate the value of 4.2- Danish recreational fishery. As regulations set a short fishing season (August-September) majority of anglers are expected to realize no more than one trip per year and thus a ZTCM is used here (Tourkolias et al., 2015). Respondents were grouped into five zones based on the initial digit of their zip code: zone 1 includes zip codes starting with 1 or 2, zone 2 with 3 or 4, zone 3 with 5 or 6, zone 4 with 7 or 8, and zone 5 with 9. The total cost declared by the respondents is increased by considering opportunity cost (Mayer and Woltering, 2018). This opportunity cost is based on the time spent on preparation and transport related to bluefin tuna recreational fishery, as well as the income (before taxes) of the respondents, considering a leisure time valuation coefficient set at one-third of the hourly wage, as commonly applied in TCM studies (Parsons, 2017). Hourly wages are derived from self-reported income data or, when unavailable, from data provided by [Statistics Denmark website](#). Estimates of hours worked are based on figures from the [Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development](#) (OECD) for Denmark. After testing several functional forms, namely linear, semi-log and double log, for the TGF, as well as the consideration of several different explicative variables, the following linear model is selected:

$$VR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TC + \beta_2 Year_{2019} + \beta_3 Year_{2020} + \beta_4 (TC \cdot Year_{2019}) + \beta_5 (TC \cdot Year_{2020}) \\ + \beta_6 Days_targeting_tunas + \beta_7 Days_prevented_from_fishing \\ + \beta_8 Nautical_miles_sailed + \beta_9 km_driven$$

In which VR is the Visitation Rate and TC is the total cost, including the opportunity cost. $Year_{2019}$ and $Year_{2020}$ are dummy variables permitting the consideration of data for the three years of the survey in the same model. The total number of kilometres driven by the respondents due to participation in tuna fishing is denoted as km_driven .

Estimated coefficients β as well as model diagnostics—including goodness-of-fit measures, residual autocorrelation tests, and multicollinearity indicators—are available in Appendix A.1.5. The high values of R^2 (0.9342) and adjusted R^2 (0.8157), combined with a significant F-statistic (7.886, $p = 0.0175$), indicate that the model fits the data well. The low magnitude of residuals (ranging from -3.89×10^{-5} to 9.02×10^{-5}) further supports the model's accuracy. Additionally, the Durbin-Watson statistic (1.9867, $p = 0.7762$) suggests no autocorrelation in the residuals. Finally, all Generalized Variance Inflation Factor scaled by degrees of freedom,

denoted by $G\text{VIF}^{1/(2 \times Df)}$, values are below 3, confirming that multicollinearity among explanatory variables is not a concern.

1.3.3.2.5. CS 5: System seagrass-lucinids-bacteria along the Slovenian coast

Assessments of ES provided by system seagrass *Cymodocea nodosa*- lucinids and bacteria are based on lab data. Material (e.g seagrass and lucinids, bacteria) comes from Piran in Slovenia. Experts measure daily O₂ fluxes in incubation chambers containing seagrass alone; lucinids-bacteria alone; seagrass and lucinids-bacteria combined and nothing (as a control). In order to increase the statistical robustness, several replicates of the same experiments are made. This allows for the presentation of minimum and maximum estimations. Two series of experiments are carried out: one representative of the environmental conditions for March 2024 and one for July 2024. It can be noticed that the density of the lucinids in the chambers are not equal to the density in the field. Assuming that each daily O₂ flow measurement is representative of mid-year conditions, the annual O₂ flow is derived. By multiplying this value by the market price of O₂, an estimation of the economic value of 5.1 - oxygen production is obtained. Using the photosynthesis equation, the annual quantity of CO₂ sequestered is then calculated. This last metric is then transformed into carbon storage in biomass and soil through proportionality coefficients based on as-yet-unpublished data from an AZTI project (ACCION project). The evolution of stocks, and hence their annualization, is measured using an exponential decay formula (Murray et al., 2011). Values of these two ES rely on carbon market price, based on EU carbon permits. As daily O₂ fluxes obtained by lab data are given per unit of surface of seagrass, values obtained are multiplied by the surface of *Cymodocea nodosa* along the Slovenian coast. This data is extracted from Ivajnšič et al. (2022) assuming that the species composition observed in the mapped area is representative of the broader seagrass distribution along the Slovenian coast.

1.3.3.2.6. CS 6: Holobionts Sponges-microbes in Catalan Sea

The assessment of 6.7- water filtration provided by sponge-microbe holobionts in the Catalan Sea draws conceptual inspiration from Ottaviani (2020). In that publication, the authors propose that the sponge's highly efficient bacterial removal capacity—reaching up to 99%—can be assimilable to the functioning of a wastewater treatment facility. Specifically, they associate it to the early stages of treatment, where coarse filtration and biological processing of organic matter occur, followed by the elimination of bacteria through methods such as chlorination, ultraviolet irradiation, or ozonation. In this context, a replacement cost methodology is applied, based on data from a wastewater treatment plant in Toronto (Canada), available in Pham et al. (2019). Costs data are divided into two parts: capital and operating costs. Capital costs are linked with the installation of a new ultraviolet disinfection facility. Without estimations of lifetime of this type of system, two values for the ES are provided: one considering just the operating costs and one considering the operating cost and capital costs annualized based on a lifetime of 3 years for the new ultraviolet disinfection facility. Based on bacterial removal efficiency data, two species are selected: *Agelas oroides* (Gili et al., 1984) and *Chondrosia reniformis* (Tassara et al., 2023). Using filtration rates reported by Aguilo-Arce et al. (2023), along with the nominal treatment capacity and cost data from the wastewater treatment plant, the economic value of the ecosystem service of water filtration provided by these two species is estimated per unit of biomass. As Aguilo-Arce et al. (2023) provide range for filtration rates, depending on the microorganisms

species symbionts, minimum and maximum estimations are provided for both methodologies (i.e. considering operating cost only or capital and operating costs).

1.3.3.2.7. CS 7: Plankton in three Gulfs in Italy

Input data for assessing ES provided by plankton in the Gulfs of Gaeta, Naples and Salerno are sourced from plankton food web model outputs presented in Bellardini et al. (2025). In this publication, authors applied a numerical modelling approach based on the [Ecopath algorithm](#), integrating environmental and biological data from the study area to develop seasonal time-snapshot (autumn 2020 and summer 2021) of planktonic food webs. 35 FG considered in the model are available in Appendix A.1.4. As for CS 5 (Section 1.3.3.2.5), each set of data is considered as representative of conditions for the mid of the year to obtain annual estimations.

Input data needed for the model were collected, for each Gulf, at several stations, thus permitting us to present assessments in terms of ranges. Specifically, 7.7- climate regulation and 7.9- water quality services are quantified using the respiration rates of planktonic communities and the primary production of photosynthetic organisms, as estimated by these models (Bellardini et al., 2025). These values are used to calculate gross primary production of the planktonic communities, which in turn informed estimates of total carbon sequestration potential (CSP), based on the methodologies and equations outlined in Gao et al. (2021) and Jia et al. (2022). The CSP for each planktonic community is subsequently converted into oxygen production through the equation of photosynthesis (Zheng et al., 2009). In our study these two latest ES are considered within 7.7- climate regulation, although they also contribute to others such as 7.6- primary production, 7.9- water quality and 7.8- biogeochemical cycles. Using the Redfield ratio (Redfield, 1958), the CSP for each planktonic community is also converted into Nitrogen (denoted by N) and Phosphorous (denoted by P) uptakes (Zheng et al., 2009). In our study these two ES are considered within 7.9- water quality, although they also contribute to others such as 7.8- biogeochemical cycles. For these 4 assessments, physical characterizations are multiplied by related prices (which are carbon price based on EU carbon permits, O₂ market price and shadows prices for removing N and P).

In addition, input data for evaluating the food for higher trophic levels are also derived from the plankton food web models in Bellardini et al. (2025) following the framework proposed by D'Alelio et al. (2016). Specifically, the secondary production of the planktonic metazoans — key food sources for planktivorous fish (e.g., (Taieb et al., 2013, Morote et al., 2010) — is extracted for the same Gulf regions (Bellardini et al., 2025). Assuming negligible natural mortality and applying a trophic transfer efficiency of 10%, along with a carbon-to-dry-weight conversion ratio of 1:9, as per D'Alelio et al. (2016), these secondary production values are converted into estimates of potential planktivorous fish biomass. Following Leonart and Maynou (2003), D'Anza et al. (2024) and Storelli et al. (2011) anchovies and sardines, i.e., the most abundant planktivorous fish in the Mediterranean Sea, are considered to constitute the planktivorous fish biomass estimated in this study. Consequently, the market prices of these species are used. Price data for the year 2022 are extracted from the AER and adjusted to 2024 values using the HICP.

1.3.3.3. Economic and monetary estimations of identified ecosystem services

This section presents a summary of the economic/monetary values estimated once Section 1.3.3.2 are applied. Due to methodological differences between CS 1 and the others, leading to distinct types of outputs, results are presented separately: **Table 6** for CS 1 and **Table 7** for

the remaining CS. In addition, **Figure 12** presents the annual total economic value per square meter for some CS. The total economic value is defined as the sum of the mean values of each ES per CS. It should be noted that, for certain case studies - highlighted in light red in **Figure 12** - the economic value of ES could not be estimated in terms of annual value per square meter. This is especially difficult when estimating fish functional groups delivering services in large ecosystems. In the following subsections a brief additional explanation is provided per CS.

Table 6: Average present value of ecosystem services once the mesopelagic fishery starts exploiting (CS1)

Main species of the CS	Ecosystem Service	Average Present Value (mean)	Average Present Value (95% confident interval of the mean: min-max)	Unit
Mesopelagic fishes	1.1	$15.55 \cdot 10^6$	$4.98 \cdot 10^6 - 40.24 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	1.2	$-2.85 \cdot 10^6$	$-21.84 \cdot 10^6 - 25.52 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	1.3	$-9.02 \cdot 10^6$	$-26.11 \cdot 10^6 - (-4.75 \cdot 10^6)$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	1.4	$-4.98 \cdot 10^6$	$-7.71 \cdot 10^6 - (-3.41 \cdot 10^6)$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹

Table 7: Economic and monetary values of ecosystem services delivered by diadromous fishes, tuna, seagrass, sponges and plankton in epipelagic, benthic and freshwaters ecosystems (CS 2 - CS 7). Lines in blue are used to obtain an overall value.

Main species of the CS	Ecosystem Service	Value (min-max)	Unit
Diadromous fishes	2.1_Food provisioning	$9 \cdot 10^6 -$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	2.2_Nutrients transportation	$0.2 \cdot 10^6 -$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹ specie ⁻¹
	2.4_Cultural value	$13.796 \cdot 10^6 - 34.13 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	2.4_Cultural value	18-45	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹ kg (landings) ₁
Tropical tunas (beyond EU)	3.1_Food provisioning	$369.98 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	3.2_Carbon sequestration	$8.70 \cdot 10^6 - 13.05 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	3.5_Cultural value	$69.46 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
Atlantic Bluefin Tuna	4.2_Recreational fishery	/	
Seagrass	5.1_Oxygen production		
	Seagrass alone	$119.11 \cdot 10^3 - 389.69 \cdot 10^3$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	Seagrass, lucinids and bacteria	$22.33 \cdot 10^3 - 198.04 \cdot 10^3$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	5.2_Carbon sequestration		
	Seagrass alone	$72.56 \cdot 10^3 - 237.39 \cdot 10^3$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	Seagrass, lucinids and bacteria	$13.61 \cdot 10^3 - 120.64 \cdot 10^3$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
Sponges	5.3_Carbon storage		
	Seagrass alone	$3.02 \cdot 10^6 - 9.87 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	Seagrass, lucinids and bacteria	$565.43 \cdot 10^3 - 5.01 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	6.7_Water filtration (considering operating costs, gDW stands for grams of Dry Weight)		
Sponges	<i>Agelas oroides</i>	$7.48 \cdot 10^{-4} - 3.42 \cdot 10^{-2}$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .gDW ⁻¹ .year ⁻¹
	<i>Chondrosia reniformis</i>	$2.38 \cdot 10^{-4} - 1.09 \cdot 10^{-1}$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .gDW ⁻¹ .year ⁻¹
	6.7_Water filtration (considering operating and capital costs)		
Plankton	<i>Agelas oroides</i>	$2.49 \cdot 10^{-2} - 1.14$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .gDW ⁻¹ .year ⁻¹
	<i>Chondrosia reniformis</i>	$7.91 \cdot 10^{-3} - 3.63$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .gDW ⁻¹ .year ⁻¹
	7.7_Climate regulation (CO ₂ sequestration)		
Plankton	Gaeta	$3.33 \cdot 10^6 - 11.67 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹

Main species of the CS	Ecosystem Service	Value (min-max)	Unit
	Naples	$2.02 \cdot 10^6 - 5.02 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	Salerno	$5.73 \cdot 10^6 - 11.89 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	7.7_ Climate regulation (O ₂ production)		
	Gaeta	$5.46 \cdot 10^6 - 19.15 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	Naples	$3.32 \cdot 10^6 - 8.24 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	Salerno	$9.41 \cdot 10^6 - 19.51 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	7.9_ Water quality (N uptake)		
	Gaeta	$26.63 \cdot 10^6 - 93.34 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	Naples	$16.20 \cdot 10^6 - 40.15 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	Salerno	$45.84 \cdot 10^6 - 95.09 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	7.9_ Water quality (P uptake)		
	Gaeta	$2.26 \cdot 10^6 - 7.91 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	Naples	$1.37 \cdot 10^6 - 3.40 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	Salerno	$3.88 \cdot 10^6 - 8.06 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	7.10_ Food for higher trophic level		
	Gaeta	$152.48 \cdot 10^6 - 1,403.22 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	Naples	$19.92 \cdot 10^6 - 177.61 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹
	Salerno	$82.23 \cdot 10^6 - 248.32 \cdot 10^6$	€ ₂₀₂₄ .year ⁻¹

Figure 12: Total economic value of ES per square meter for CS 3, 5 and 7. For CS in light red it is not possible to obtain the economic values per square meter.

Focusing on absolute values (Table 7), the highest economic estimation of ES is reached for plankton in Gaeta Gulf with 7.10- Food for higher trophic levels while the lowest is for system seagrass-lucinids-bacteria along the Slovenian coast with 5.2- Carbon sequestration. By summing the contribution of all the ES, expressed in absolute terms, plankton in the three gulfs of Italy presents the highest economic estimations, ranging from 23 to 2,153 million €₂₀₂₄, followed by tunas in tropical Atlantic ecoregion (from 448 to 452 million €₂₀₂₄), diadromous fishes in EU Atlantic Area (considering 2.1 and 2.4, from 23 to 43 million €₂₀₂₄) and finally seagrass in Slovenia (from 0.6, considering system seagrass-lucinids-bacteria, to 10 million €₂₀₂₄, considering seagrass alone).

On the contrary, **focusing on total economic values per square meter (Figure 12)**, the highest economic estimation is obtained for seagrass, followed by plankton and finally tropical tunas. This result seems consistent with literature, since seagrass and plankton are expected to be particularly organisms delivering valuable ES (Costanza et al., 1997. and Grigoratou et al., 2025)

Overall, considering just 8 of ES assessed out of the 50 identified, represented in blue in (Table 7), the sum of their economic values represents an underestimated contribution (like an *annually yield*) of the EU natural capital in terms of social benefits, reaching an aggregated value (yearly based), based on evaluated EU ecosystems, which range between 0.4 and 2.2 Billion€₂₀₂₄. Beyond EU waters, the tropical tuna delivers 0.4 Billion€₂₀₂₄ at epipelagic ecosystems. Notice the Environmental Protection Expenditure (EPE) in the EU reached in 2023 a 2.1% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The EPE includes the protection of biodiversity, but also the expenditure related to the abatement of air, water, soil and noise pollution, the management of wastewater and waste, and environmental research and development. Being the ES values provided by those EU CS around the 0.01 % of the GDP in 2024. And therefore, the expenditure in protection is relatively poor to cover the huge value provided by those ecosystems. Similarly, and more specifically for marine ecosystems, the European Commission adopted in 2025 the first – ever European Ocean Pact with 1 billion €₂₀₂₅ to protect marine life and strengthen blue economy (https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/european-ocean-pact_en). This investment represents a very low value in contrast to the natural and yearly based ecosystems' contribution to the society measured through the ES valuation.

1.3.3.3.1. CS 1: Mesopelagic fisheries in Bay of Biscay

This CS is considerably different to the others because it is a good example to assess the loss and win ES if a mesopelagic commercial fishery is launched. Currently, a commercial mesopelagic fishery does not exist in the Bay of Biscay, although scientific knowledge is opening the possibility of planning a potential exploitation of the mesopelagic layer. The decision about its future exploitation will be based, among others, on the new knowledge from the expected ES delivered and their economic assessment. Regarding mean values, the Average Present Value (APV) for ES 1.1 – FO and FM for aquaculture – is positive, and its value considering 95% confidence interval remains entirely above zero. This confirms that ES 1.1 would consistently benefit from the opening of a mesopelagic fishery. In contrast, mean APV for all other ES are negative, although the confidence interval for ES 1.2 – food provisioning from the current fishery – suggests a potential for positive outcomes in some scenarios. Overall, the newly exploitation of a mesopelagic fishery is associated with a negative trade-off estimated at approximately 1.3 million €₂₀₂₄ (mean value). However, the wide confidence interval, ranging from a potential gain of 57.59 million €₂₀₂₄ to a loss of 50.68 million €₂₀₂₄, underscores the substantial uncertainty and variability in the expected outcomes.

1.3.3.3.2. CS 2: Diadromous fishes in the EU Atlantic area

In this CS a replacement cost about 0.01 €.Kg⁻¹ of net balance biomass (imports less exports of biomass of fish) is obtained. With the caveat that the net migration balance should be obtained showing low values per kg of net balance of biomass flow, however the annual amount only for one species, *Allis shad*, reaches 193 k€. Following the output of DiadES project, there are eleven key diadromous species in the EU Atlantic habitats. Although, there is a scientific gap concerning the different contribution of each species this value for *Allis shad* species can be understood as a reference one.

In relation to the cultural values, respondents who were not willing to pay were allocated an amount of WTP equal to 0 € similarly to those answers able to pay 0 €. Considering these responses in the estimates, the weighted average WTP amounts an average of 6.13 € (non-

weighted average of 12 €). Notice, the cultural value ES estimates is very high because general population figure is used to upscale the overall value.

1.3.3.3.3. CS 3: Tunas in Tropical Atlantic Ecoregion

In this CS, although few fisheries are considered and the cultural value focuses just on the Spanish fishery, the highest economic value is for the provisioning services, followed by the cultural services and finally the regulating and maintenance service of the carbon sequestration. Tropical tunas play crucial roles in those oceanic pelagic marine ecosystems provisioning fish food ES being among the most commercially valuable fish species in the global seafood market. These species are fished for canning and for the high-end markets such as sashimi, being their fishing, processing and trade a significantly source for the economies of both Atlantic coastal nations and the distant-water fishing nations. A high challenge is therefore, estimating the cultural ES for such distant-water fleet, given that Spanish people is also distant- surveyed through a contingent analysis. Local population in Spain have valued those ES in a lesser extent they do with respect to coastal fleets. Thus, for example, for the Basque Country Region in the North of Spain, the WTP relating to the “Combination of natural landscape and port fishing” is estimated at range [19.00 , 21.00] € of which 19.5% is attributable to the industrial fleet; in the case of the “Performing arts” the WTP is estimated [17.00, 24.00] € of which 20.4% would correspond to the industrial fleet; for “Social, ritual and festive events” the estimated WTP is [17.00, 21.00] € of which 20.1% would correspond to the industrial fleet and, finally, for “Tangible cultural heritage immovable”, the estimated WTP is [12.00, 14.00] € of which 25.2% corresponds to the industrial fleet. All of them per visit of each visitor or resident in the North of Spain. The Basque Region contribution is the most relevant to evaluate the Spain’s PS contribution to CES, because it represents the majority fleet operating in the Tropical Atlantic Area.

1.3.3.3.4. CS 4: Atlantic bluefin tuna in Skagerrak

Estimated coefficient for total cost, β_1 , is positive (See Appendix A.1.5) indicating a positive relationship between the visitation rate and the total cost. In that context, it is not possible to compute the consumer surplus and thus to obtain an economic value of the ES – 4.2 - Danish recreational fishery using the methodology of the ZTCM. Although it is not possible to obtain a precise estimate of the economic value of this ES, it can nonetheless be asserted that its value exceeds the market value. In this case, the market value is represented by the total expenditures incurred by recreational fishers to engage in the activity, which are estimated at 1.67 million €₂₀₂₄ annually (Maar et al., 2022).

Although most of the time demand curves present negative relationships between quantity and price, sometimes the opposite phenomenon can be observed, as in the model obtained in this study. This is, for example, the case for Veblen goods, Giffen goods or for lemons markets. First ones include mainly luxury goods (Veblen, 1899) while seconds ones refer to essential goods (Marshall, 1890). Lemons markets refer to markets in which information asymmetry between buyers and sellers occurs (Akerlof, 1978). Here, considering the nature of the activity as well as the good modelling highlighted by regression model diagnostics, it seems consistent to consider the recreational fishery of Atlantic Bluefin Tuna as a Veblen good.

1.3.3.3.5. CS 5: System seagrass-lucinids-bacteria along the Slovenian coast

Regarding CS 5, the highest economic value is obtained for 5.3- carbon storage, followed by 5.1- oxygen production and finally 5.2- carbon sequestration, for both experimental conditions (seagrass alone and seagrass and lucinids combined). Comparing the two experimental conditions, results highlight that seagrass alone exhibits higher estimations than seagrass combined with lucinids.

1.3.3.3.6. CS 6: Holobionts Sponges-microbes in Catalan Sea

Regarding CS 6, economic values range from $7.48 \cdot 10^{-4}$ to $1.14 \text{ €}_{2024} \cdot \text{year}^{-1} \cdot \text{gDW}^{-1}$ and $2.38 \cdot 10^{-4}$ to $3.63 \text{ €}_{2024} \cdot \text{year}^{-1} \cdot \text{gDW}^{-1}$ for *Agelas oroides* and *Chondrosia reniformis* respectively. Consistently with the methodologies applied, the highest economic values are obtained when operating and capital costs are considered for both species. *Chondrosia reniformis* exhibits both the lowest and highest values across both methodologies, while *Agelas oroides* shows a lower variability in the estimations.

1.3.3.3.7. CS 7: Plankton in three Gulfs in Italy

Focusing on CS 7, it appears that, across all Gulfs, the ES 7.10 – food provision for higher trophic levels consistently exhibits the highest economic value. This is followed by ES 7.9 – Nitrogen uptake, ES 7.7 – Oxygen production, ES 7.7 – Carbon sequestration, and finally ES 7.9 – Phosphorus uptake. Comparing the three areas, the Gulf of Salerno presents the highest economic values for 7.7 and 7.9, followed by Gaeta and finally Naples while, Gulf of Gaeta exhibits the highest economic value for 7.10, followed by Salerno and Naples.

1.3.4. References

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2. Deliberative Monetary Valuation of marine biodiversity [Task 6.3]

2.1 Introduction

Plankton, as the base of marine food webs, play a critical role in the provision of essential benefits to society such as food, climate regulation, health, and recreation. Yet, it is affected by the pressures faced by marine ecosystems, e.g. pollution, overuse, and climate change. At the same time, plankton's contribution is rarely captured in economic terms. Without recognising their value, policies risk underestimating the true costs of biodiversity loss (Beaumont et al., 2008; Cavanagh et al., 2016).

Valuation of marine biodiversity is particularly challenging due to its complexity, public unfamiliarity, and often strong non-use values (Hanley et al., 2015; Jobstvogt et al., 2014). Stated preference methods are widely applied to assess biodiversity and associated ES, but deliberative approaches – which combine preference elicitation with improved information provision and group reflections based on discussions – may provide more reliable insights, especially with such challenging environmental public goods (Bartkowski, 2017; Kenter et al., 2016).

This study applies deliberative monetary valuation (DMV) to explore how the public values marine biodiversity in general and plankton-related ES in particular across different European contexts. We conducted workshops in five countries, at both coastal and inland sites, to examine preferences and WTP.

2.2 Material and Methods

2.2.1 Workshop design and implementation

A total of 15 DMV workshops were organised between October 2023 and February 2024 across five European countries. In each country, two coastal and one inland location were selected to capture spatial variation. The workshops took place in the following locations (Figure 13).

- ✓ **Poland** : Sopot (coastal), **Poznań** (inland)
- ✓ **Italy**: Chioggia (coastal), **Padova** (inland)
- ✓ **Spain (Basque Country)** : Bilbao (coastal), **Vitoria-Gasteiz** (inland)
- ✓ **Germany**: Bremerhaven (coastal), **Hannover** (inland)
- ✓ **France** : Brest (coastal), **Rennes** (inland)

Workshop Locations

Poland, Italy, Spain (Basque Country), Germany, France

Figure 13. Workshop's locations

Each workshop included 10–13 lay participants, recruited by a professional market research company through online panels. Screening questions ensured broad representativeness in terms of age, gender, and education. Coastal participants were required to live within 10 km of the shoreline, while inland participants had to reside at least 50 km away. Individuals working in market research were excluded.

Workshops were held in the respective local language and followed a standardised procedure. A professional facilitator guided participants through all steps using presentation slides, while one or two domain experts in marine environmental issues were present to answer questions. At the beginning, participants confirmed data privacy consent and were informed about the project background and objectives. They then completed a pre-questionnaire capturing socio-demographic characteristics, prior knowledge of plankton, attitudes, and personal values.

Following this, participants were presented with an implementation scenario describing how new policies – such as nutrient reduction in agriculture and expansion of marine protected areas (MPAs) to 30% (associated with the CDB targets) – could affect a given target area. This target area was defined as follows: “Starting from the nearest point within territorial waters (the reference was the place of residency) this would affect an ocean segment of 25 km in both directions within territorial waters (ca. 22 km from the coastline). In all cases, the total area affected by the measures would thus cover approximately 50 km x 22 km (≈1000 km²).” (Jean-Louis et al., 2025, p. 6). **Figure 14** shows an illustrative representation of the locations and target area for the Italian workshops.

Figure 14. Locations of Italian workshops and the corresponding target area. Taken from Jean-Louis et al. 2025. © OpenStreetMap contributors

The implementation scenario served as the foundation for the Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE, see section 2.2.2), with its attributes reflecting the expected changes associated with the new policies. Participants could ask clarifying questions to experts and the facilitator to ensure adequate understanding.

A central element of the DMV design was the deliberation phase. In each workshop, a semi-structured discussion was facilitated around three guiding topics : the perceived complexity of plankton-related ecosystem services, participants' own exposure to potential changes, and the role of conservation when scientific outcomes are uncertain. The discussion aimed to encourage preference formation, allow reflection on societal (rather than purely individual) perspectives, and make participants' underlying values more explicit. The discussion was followed by the completion of the DCE, after which participants filled out a post-questionnaire covering motivations, perceived importance of attributes, certainty of choices, and perceived influence of other participants during the discussion. All workshops were audio- and video-recorded, with prior consent obtained during recruitment.

2.2.2 Discrete Choice Experiment

After the deliberation, participants completed a DCE with 16 choice tasks. Each task presented three alternatives: two policy scenarios and one business-as-usual (BAU) option. The latter was characterised by the attribute levels indicated accordingly below and no costs. To reduce

hypothetical bias, participants were explicitly reminded to only select scenarios they would actually be willing to pay for. The attributes and levels included in the DCE scenarios were:

1. **Plankton composition:** less stable (BAU level) vs. more stable, reflecting the reliability of plankton-based ES provision such as food supply, oxygen production and air quality maintenance, climate regulation, sediment formation, tourism, science and education services, genetic resources and green chemistry, and biological control. A more stable composition was introduced as a proxy for the continued provision of all these services, whereas a less stable one indicated an unstable or reduced provision.
2. **Algal and jellyfish blooms:** Higher probability of such events occurring in the target area (Yes = BAU level; No = improved condition).
3. **Climate regulation:** the potential amount of CO₂ fixed by phytoplankton and permanently sequestered in the target area (+0% [BAU level], +50%, +100%, +150% relative to current levels).
4. **Marine Protected Area protection status:** minimally protected (BAU level), highly protected, or fully protected. Protection levels reflect the trade-off between increased marine biodiversity protection measures and decreased human use potential.
5. **Cost:** an annual tax over ten years to finance the measures (€0 in the BAU only; €10, €20, €40, €80, €120, €180 in policy scenarios; Poland: equivalent values in Polish zloty adjusted by purchasing power parity).

Figure 15 presents an example choice card from which respondents were required to select their prioritised scenario. Attributes and levels were based on a literature review, expert consultation, a focus group and a pre-test conducted in July 2023. Please refer to Jean-Louis et al. (2025) for further details on the study design.

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Business as usual scenario
Plankton composition	Less stable 		
Higher probability of algal blooms and jellyfish blooms	No 		
Climate regulation	 + 0%		
Protection status of Marine Protected Area	Fully protected 		
Costs	80 €	20 €	0 €

Figure 15. Example Choice Card. Icons sourced from [Flaticon](https://flaticon.com/) and modified in some cases : “Plankton” icons (IDs 3751453, 7588203, 7584197), “Jellyfish” (ID 1167699), “Water Waves” (ID 2352851), “CO₂” (ID 7822231), and “Secure” (ID 95454), used under the license Free

2.2.3 Econometric model

To estimate WTP for the non-price attributes, we applied discrete choice econometric models grounded in the Random Utility Maximisation (RUM) framework (McFadden, 1974). In this framework, individuals are assumed to select the alternative that provides them with the greatest utility. Utility is modelled as a function of the attributes of each alternative, plus an unobserved error term. In the conditional logit specification, the probability that individual n chooses option i depends on the relative utility of all available alternatives:

$$P_{ni} = \frac{\exp(\beta X_{ni})}{\sum_{j=1}^J \exp(\beta X_{nj})}$$

where X_{ni} are the attribute levels of option i and β are the corresponding preference weights. To capture preference heterogeneity, we additionally estimated mixed logit models, in which the coefficients vary randomly across individuals².

² In mixed logit models, preference parameters are treated as random variables. However, the assumed randomness reflects unobserved heterogeneity revealed through respondents' actual choices, rather than variation occurring independently of the data.

To derive marginal WTP directly, we estimated conditional logit and mixed logit models in WTP space (Train & Weeks, 2005). In this specification, utility is written as:

$$U_{njt}^* = \alpha_n^*(\omega_{nk} \cdot X_{njt} - p_{njt}) + \varepsilon_{njt}$$

Here, α_n^* combines the scale and price parameters, ω_{nk} is the vector of the marginal WTP for each non-monetary attribute X_{njt} , and p_{njt} is the cost attribute. Log-likelihood estimation was used to estimate marginal WTP for each attribute (ω_{nk}).

2.3 Results from Deliberative Monetary Valuation

Data obtained from the questionnaires can be accessed online (Jean-Louis, 2024)³. The following **Table 8** presents summary statistics for selected socio-demographic variables of our sample, alongside EU averages.

Table 8. Selected socio-demographic variables of workshops participants and comparison with the corresponding actual EU data.

Socio demographic	Sample	EU 27
% Female	51.7	51.1 ⁴
Age (median)	44	44.5 ⁵
% Educational level (ISCED 0-2)	14.5	26.7 ⁶
% Educational level (ISCED 3-4)	46.5	44.9 ³
% Educational level (ISCED 5-8)	37.8	29.5 ³
Monthly net income		
0 - 500 €; 0 - 2,225 PLN	10.5 %	
501 - 750 €; 2,226 - 3,338 PLN	2.3 %	
751 - 1000 €; 3,339 - 4,450 PLN	16.9 %	
1,001 - 1,250 €; 4,451 - 5,563 PLN	9.9 %	
1,251 - 1,500 €; 5,564 - 6,675 PLN	16.3 %	
1,501 - 1,750 €; 6,676 - 7,788 PLN	9.3 %	
1,751 - 2,000 €; 7,789 - 8,900 PLN	8.7 %	
2,001 - 2,250 €; 8,901 - 10,013 PLN	4.1 %	
2,251 - 2,500 €; 10,014 - 11,125 PLN	6.4 %	
2,501 - 2,750 €; 11,126 - 12,238 PLN	2.9 %	
2,751 - 3,000 €; 12,239 - 13,350 PLN	4.7 %	
> 3,001 €; > 13,351 PLN	7.6 %	
NA	0.6 %	

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/12638010>

⁴ Eurostat, Population on 1 January by age and sex (2024a). https://doi.org/10.2908/DEMO_PJAN

⁵ Eurostat, EU median age increased by 2.3 years since 2013 (2024b). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/de/web/products-eurostat-news/w/ddn-20240215-1>

⁶ Eurostat, Population by educational attainment level, sex and age (%) (2023). https://doi.org/10.2908/EDAT_LFS_9903

The results from the conditional and mixed logit models are displayed in the subsequent **Table 9**. Altogether, the responses of 168 respondents were considered for these model estimations.

Table 9. Conditional and mixed logit models result

	Conditional logit model	Mixed logit model	
	Mean	Mean	SD
ASC_bau	-77.39***	-89.89***	62.01***
Stable plankton composition	56.31***	50.68***	47.89***
Control of bloom events	12.42**	16.71***	47.21***
+1% Carbon sequestration	0.29***	0.30***	0.63***
Fully protected MPA	32.96***	34.38***	27.21***
Highly protected MPA	38.03***	30.66***	12.01
Cost	-0.015***	-3.60***	-0.41***
Log-likelihood (final)	-2229.24	-1883.48	
Adj. Rho-squared vs equal shares	0.2393	0.3546	
Bayes information criterion	4513.72	3877.44	
Akaike information criterion	4472.47	3794.95	
Number of individuals	168	168	
Number of rows in database	2676	2676	

The results of both logit models indicate significant WTP estimates for all attributes. The negative WTP for the alternative-specific constant (ASC_bau) suggests that respondents were more likely to choose one of the policy options rather than the business-as-usual scenario. This negative value can be interpreted as the level of compensation respondents would require if the business-as-usual scenario were implemented in the future.

The mean WTP for the continued provision of plankton-based ES exceeded €50 in both models. In contrast, WTP for the control of bloom events was lower, reflecting the limited importance respondents assigned to this attribute, as further confirmed by an additional analysis of their stated motivations. With respect to WTP for MPA protection levels, the results suggest that respondents preferred stricter measures over the minimum level of protection. However, the models provide no clear evidence on whether the strictest level (fully protected) was preferred to medium protection measures (highly protected), indicating preference heterogeneity.

Conditional logit models in WTP-space were also estimated separately for the five study regions (Poland, Italy, Basque Country, Germany, France), with results summarised in **Figure 16**. No significant regional differences emerged for the business-as-usual ASC, stable plankton composition, bloom control, or the cost attribute. However, German participants expressed a significantly higher WTP for carbon sequestration than Italian participants. For

fully protected MPAs, WTP in Germany was significantly higher than in Poland and Italy, while Polish respondents showed a lower WTP for highly protected MPAs compared to Germans. Separate model estimations for coastal and inland respondents did not reveal significant differences for any of the DCE attributes

Figure 16. Conditional logit models in WTP space for each region including significance levels for the parameter estimates at $p < 0.1$ (.), $p < 0.05$ *, $p < 0.01$ ** and $p < 0.001$ ***. The displayed data represent the mean estimates and the 95% confidence intervals based on the corresponding means' standard errors

2.4. References

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3. Discussion

3.1 Natural Capital Accounting [Task 6.2]

3.1.1. General overview: Identification of the ecosystem services derived from coastal and marine communities

The present study analyzed scientific literature from the Web of Science on marine ES, compiling a dataset of 9,048 articles. Using LDA topic modelling, we identified key topics from article titles and abstracts. This approach provided a broad and reproducible exploration of the main themes in marine ES research and their evolution over time. Most articles retrieved herein focused on policy-oriented topics or those related to recreation and tourism. However, a long-term analysis highlighted a significant rise in research on environmental issues, particularly climate change impacts, blue carbon systems, and carbon storage. This trend suggests a growing concern about global warming's effects on natural ecosystems in the coming years.

To analyze global trends in marine ES research, this study applied LDA topic modelling to text data extracted from titles and abstracts of papers retrieved using the keyword 'ecosystem services' in the context of marine ecosystems. The topic modelling identified key research themes characterizing marine ES scientific output (**Figures 1 and 2**). The findings align with and expand those of Liqueete et al., (2013), who conducted a systematic review of marine ES-related papers from 1823 to April 2012 and identified fishery, water purification focusing on nutrients and suspended matter, coastal protection, recreation and tourism, life cycle maintenance, and climate regulation as the most studied marine ES (Liqueete et al., 2013). The review by Liqueete et al., (2013) also highlighted that the coastal zone was the most frequently studied area. Similarly, our study found that the marine coasts dominate marine ES research, reflecting their significance in economic activities (i.e., Topics 3, 4, and 5) and environmental management (i.e., Topics 1, 7, and 9).

3.1.1.1 Temporal trends of marine ecosystem services

From the analysis of marine ES publications in the present study, a statistically significant change point emerged between 2006 and 2007, which aligns with findings from the traditional review by Liqueete et al., (2013), and it stems from the introduction of the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (Finlayson, 2016). The significant increase in the yearly publication rate across all topics over time, retrieved herein, confirms and extends Liqueete et al., (2013) and highlights how marine ES research has mirrored the broader growth trends in the scientific literature (e.g., Marginson, 2022; Miguel et al., 2016). In addition, the annual proportions of topics reveal notable patterns, with increasing trends in Topics 2 (Marine policy), 6 (Climate change impact), 7 (Blue carbon systems carbon storage), and 8 (Microbial biotic materials and biofuels), and decreasing trends in Topics 3 (Coral reefs recreational activities), 5 (Coastal tourism and recreational fisheries) and 9 (Water purification).

Climate change (Topic 6) not only underwent a significant increase, but influenced interconnected themes, with increases in topics related to the global management of marine ecosystems and the formulation of marine policies (Topic 2), the reduction of the amount of atmospheric carbon (Topic 7), and the production of alternative and more sustainable energy sources (Topic 8). The rise in research on the carbon storage of blue-carbon systems (Topic 7) is consistent with the growing recognition of their global significance,

beginning with the seminal work by Duarte et al., (2005) and the popularization of the term "blue carbon" by Nellemann, (2009) and its role in mitigating climate change (Ruiz-Frau et al., 2017). Blue carbon systems play a pivotal role in global carbon sequestration and burial (Duarte et al., 2013; Mcleod et al., 2011) (*climate regulation* ES), a service valued at about USD 190.7 bn annually (Bertram et al., 2021).

In contrast, topics addressing localized climate change impacts observed a decrease (Water purification, Topic 9) or no changes over time (Coastal protection, Topic 1), despite approximately half of their publications being published in the last five years. This suggests a shift in research priorities from localized issues to broader, globally relevant environmental challenges, as also reported in previous studies (e.g., D'Alelio et al., 2021). In the coming decades, climate change is expected to exacerbate extreme weather events and sea-level rise (Vitousek et al., 2017; Vousdoukas et al., 2018), thus potentially increasing local impacts. However, blue carbon systems also offer coastal protection (Topic 1) by attenuating wave heights and reducing flood risks (Carlot et al., 2023; Duarte et al., 2013), safeguarding human populations and economic activities (Arkema et al., 2013; Barbier et al., 2011; Trégarot et al., 2021) (Topic 1 - *coastal protection* ES). By exacerbating extreme weather events, climate change is also expected to increase flow discharge from rivers to the sea (D'Alelio et al., 2022; Jakimavičius et al., 2018). Blue carbon systems help mitigate these effects by absorbing significant land-based nutrient loads, improving water quality (Soumya et al., 2015; Sousa et al., 2010) (Topic 9 - *water purification* ES).

The growing emphasis on climate change and associated topics appears to reduce the attention on recreation and tourism-related ES. The previous traditional review by Liqueste et al., (2013) identified fisheries, recreation, and tourism among the most-studied marine ES. In the present study, recreational and tourism-related topics (Topics 3, 4, and 5) were prominent too, accounting for 32.1% of the dataset. This finding confirms earlier observations (Liqueste et al., 2013; Torres and Hanley, 2017) and suggests that recreation assessment and quantification in monetary terms is more accomplishable than other cultural ES (Hernández-Morcillo et al., 2013; Martin et al., 2016). However, Coral reefs recreational activities (Topic 3) and Coastal tourism and recreational fisheries (Topic 5) significantly declined in proportional focus over time; Marine wildlife tourism (Topic 4) remained stable. These topics also exhibited three of the lowest percentages of recent publications, further indicating a waning emphasis on tourism and cultural ES in favour of addressing global-scale environmental challenges, despite the numerous benefits recreational activities provide to humans (Tufts et al., 2015; Wood et al., 2013).

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3.1.2. Applied Natural Accounting: the role of marine plankton in providing ecosystem services based on its special role in marine ecosystems

The ES InDegree analysis from the two seasonal surveys indicated an overall rise in potential plankton-associated ES from autumn to summer (**Figure 6**). Among the studied areas, planktonic ES in the Gulf of Naples exhibited the highest InDegree in both seasons, followed by those in the Gulfs of Gaeta and Salerno (**Figure 6**). These results agree with the study by Bellardini et al., (2024b), reporting seasonal differences in environmental conditions across the gulfs and suggesting a significant influence by riverine inputs.

Moreover, the observed increase in the ES trophic levels during summer was not due to a higher presence of planktonic metazoans but rather to the increased contribution of protozooplankton. This finding is consistent with the high trophic redundancy among planktonic metazoans and protozooplankton, which can establish similar trophic interactions and exhibit closely related trophic levels (e.g., Russo et al., 2023, 2022). This result confirms the crucial ecological role exerted by protozooplankton within the planktonic

communities (Anschütz et al., 2024; Russo et al., 2022) by improving the stoichiometry of food quality and increasing the efficiency of transfer of organic matter towards the higher trophic levels (Anschütz et al., 2024). However, despite the growing literature on these organisms (Anschütz et al., 2024) and the production of exhaustive databases reporting the trophic habits and ecological behaviors of protozooplankton and mixotrophic protists (Mitra et al., 2023; Schneider et al., 2020), a significant knowledge gap remains concerning this group of organisms (Anschütz et al., 2024). This gap could depend on the phytoplankton–zooplankton dichotomy, where the marine food webs are represented by just two main groups of organisms: the primary producers and their metazoan grazers (Anschütz et al., 2024).

The phytoplankton–zooplankton dichotomy has likely influenced even the systematic review conducted in this study, which revealed a lack of information on the ES directly provided by protozooplankton (**Figure 2**). In this context, the European Union Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), i.e., the primary EU directive for managing marine ecosystems, uses 11 descriptors to assess environmental status, where ‘phytoplankton’ and ‘zooplankton’ are referenced in two descriptors (Biological Diversity and Food Webs) and protozooplankton are, remarkably, absent (Anschütz et al., 2024). Since functional diversity is a critical aspect of biodiversity when evaluating ecological functions within natural communities, it is essential to analyze the entire spectrum of biodiversity in the ecosystem services assessment (Culhane et al., 2018).

Natural communities often exhibit significant variations across spatiotemporal scales, thus influencing the delivery of ecosystem services (Wang et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022). This aspect is particularly relevant for plankton, whose composition depends on environmental factors (e.g., Bellardini et al., 2024a; Russo et al., 2022). Along the Campania coast, plankton undergo seasonal (Bellardini et al., 2024b, 2024a) and trophic changes (D’Alelio et al., 2016). The analysis applied herein also confirmed the seasonal variability of the planktonic communities of the Campania region (**Figure 5**), highlighting the effect of the different trophic statuses of the water on plankton communities and the ES they provide within each gulf and season. Bellardini et al., (2024b) reported higher chlorophyll *a* concentration during the summer in each gulf compared to autumn, with the Gulf of Naples consistently showing the highest values, indicating a more eutrophic status. In line with this, our findings revealed a general increase in the potential ES provided by plankton biodiversity from autumn to summer, along with their trophic level during the summer within each gulf (**Figure 3 and Figure 4**). These results suggest that the higher concentrations of chlorophyll *a* (i.e., a proxy for photosynthetic organisms, Vidussi et al., 2001) observed during summer determined a slightly higher supply of ES provided by organisms standing at higher trophic levels when comparing eutrophic to more oligotrophic water conditions. Despite these differences, all the gulfs analyzed herein can sustain fisheries and aquaculture, offering substantial support for local economic activities and confirming the strong connection between coastal habitats and human social and economic benefits (Culhane et al., 2018).

Further research needs to elucidate better the relationship between plankton biodiversity and the overall economic valuation of ES, as reductions in food security, livelihoods, income, or health can negatively impact societal well-being. Adopting a network approach is crucial for identifying trade-offs between ES values, because providing a higher inDegree, such as that attributed to educational ES in this study, does not necessarily imply a higher societal value (monetary assessment) compared to other ES with a lower inDegree (e.g., the intangible

benefits society receives from cultural heritage ES). Conversely, recreation from cultural ESs and climate regulation from regulating and maintenance ES can exhibit high monetary valuations (e.g., Borja et al., 2015; Costanza et al., 2014; de Groot et al., 2012) in line with the high inDegree values found in this study.

3.1.2.1 References

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3.1.3. Applied Natural Accounting: a collection of case studies

3.1.3.1. Economic estimation as an indicator of biological/ecological conditions?

CS 6 (holobionts sponges-microbes) and CS 7 (plankton) enable comparisons between organisms and locations, respectively. This approach provides a basis for discussing the extent to which economic assessments of ES can reflect underlying ecological and biological functions/conditions of ecosystems/organisms. Focusing on CS 7, values obtained in Section 1.3.3.3 can be converted to a per-square-meter basis to be comparable with ecological indicators presented in Bellardini et al. (2025) and Bellardini et al. (2024b). There is a particular match between the highest values of ecological indicators and the highest economic assessments of ES. Indeed, Naples, which presents highest economic values for 7.7- climate regulation and 7.9- water quality, which are ES linked with photosynthetic organisms, also exhibits highest biomass of phytoplankton (Bellardini et al., 2025) and highest value of chlorophyll *a* (Bellardini et al., 2024b). Focusing on 7.10- food for higher trophic level, which is linked with planktonic metazoans, the highest value is obtained for Gaeta, which also presents highest zooplankton abundance (Bellardini et al., 2024b) and biomass (Bellardini et al., 2025). The match between ecological indicators and economic values is less obvious for second and third places. For 7.7 and 7.9, the second highest economic value is obtained for Salerno, followed by Gaeta, this result generally matches with chlorophyll *a* for autumn but not for summer (Bellardini et al., 2024b). Regarding 7.10, the second highest economic value is obtained for Salerno, followed by Naples, this assessments match with the abundance of Cyclopoida, but not for the total zooplankton abundance and that of the other groups of zooplankton studied in Bellardini et al. (2024b). Focusing on CS 6, as detailed in Section 1.3.3.2.6, the highest and lowest economic values—across both applied methodologies—were observed for *Chondrosia reniformis*. This outcome aligns with filtration rate data reported by Aguilo-Arce et al. (2023), where *Chondrosia reniformis* exhibited values ranging from 3 to

1363 mL·h⁻¹·gDW⁻¹, compared to 9 to 427 mL·h⁻¹·gDW⁻¹ for *Agelas oroides*. Although this result was anticipated based on the methodologies used, it clearly demonstrates that economic assessments of ES not only provide economic indicators but can also effectively capture biological characteristics of the species. Consequently, incorporating economic assessments of ES may help reduce the number of indicators required to characterize an ecosystem and/or a species by encapsulating biological and ecological conditions.

3.1.3.2. Critical uncertainties and gaps in the estimation of the ecosystem services economic assessment

Across all the studied CS, economic assessments of ES present either large ranges or the impossibility of producing values, highlighting high uncertainties attached to both the biophysical data and processes and, the economic data and models. This uncertainty issue is a consistent result with previous literature (Ecoacsa Reserva de Biodiversidad et al., 2021). These high uncertainties are due to uncertainties in biophysical characterizations of the ES and/or in economic data.

The first ones can arise from two main reasons: a high level of uncertainty surrounding in the scientific data collection but also, due to the important missing knowledge about the ecosystem's functions and processes when delivering ES. The next two paragraphs focus on these last two points, and the third on economic data.

Biophysical characterization's related uncertainties due to the lack of knowledge (data, models)

Regarding uncertainties in data collection, focusing on CS 5 (Seagrass) and CS 7 (Plankton), with the aim of increasing the robustness of the data, they are obtained from different incubations chambers and stations respectively, leading to ranges in values. Moreover, even if plankton exhibits strong seasonality in planktonic communities' composition and biomass (Winder and Cloern, 2010, Zingone et al., 2019), especially in the studied area (Bellardini et al., 2025, Bellardini et al., 2024a), and carbon sequestration realized by seagrass meadows is impacted by light levels exposure (Dahl et al., 2016), annualizations are realized considering that few months of data are representative for all the year. In addition, for CS 5, conditions in incubations chambers differ from those in the field (for example, lucinids density) which can lead to bias in estimations. At the same time, due to cost of time, personal and material it is impossible to cover all the year in real conditions with experiments or field data.

The scientific knowledge gap is highlighted in several CS. For example, in CS 1 (mesopelagic fishes), since the biomass of mesopelagic fishes in the Bay of Biscay remains scientifically unknown, a high variability is equally transferred to the estimated economic valuations. As noticed in Prellezo et al. (2024), uncertainties also emerged from imprecisions regarding biomass of the other functional groups considered given the complexity of the ecosystem model used in the study. The gap in scientific knowledge can be also related to the difficulty in quantifying underlying mechanisms. Indeed, in CS 1 the relative error in the quantification of respiration process is around 75% which later generate additional errors when estimating economic values. In CS 2 (diadromous fishes) the nutrient transportation service could only be estimated thanks to the development of a specific biophysical model currently available for only one specific diadromous fish species (Allis shad). It is costly in terms of human capacities and financial resources to develop this model for many other species. The transference of results from Allis shad to other species is a key source of uncertainty. In CS 6 (holobionts

sponges-microbes), the scientific knowledge gap is due to the non-identification of the symbiont species, requiring the consideration of water filtration rates relative to several microorganisms. Regarding CS 3 (tropical tunas), as percentages of carbon individuals are only available for some species (i.e., *Scomber scombrus*, *S. japonicus* (Czamanski et al., 2011) and mesopelagic fishes (Bar-On et al., 2018), ranges were considered which implies assuming uncertainties.

Economic characterization related uncertainties due to the lack of knowledge (data, models)

Lastly, some uncertainties may arise from the economic values used in this study. For instance, for CS 7 (plankton) various estimates of prices for removing phosphorus and nitrogen can be found in the literature (HELCOM, 2023; Hautakangas et al., 2014; Bogaart et al., 2023). In this study, it is chosen to use the values provided by Hernández-Sancho et al. (2010) for Spain, as the economic context of their analysis—particularly regarding labour and energy costs—appears more comparable to the Spanish context than other sources, making their estimates more suitable for our case. Nevertheless, the absence of a universally accepted value introduces a degree of uncertainty into the results. Uncertainties due to lack of economic information are also indirectly illustrated in CS 6, in which the lack of knowledge of the lifetime of ultraviolet disinfection facility induces ranged economic assessments with a minimal estimation, without consideration of capital costs, and maximal estimations with consideration of a short lifetime of ultraviolet disinfection facility. Although uncertainties may arise from various sources, the aim of this study is to explore approaches for integrating economic assessments of ES into management strategies, rather than to implement specific measures based on the estimated economic values. In this context, the methodologies developed are considered adequate to fulfil the study's objectives.

3.1.3.3. Barriers preventing the economic valuation of ecosystem services

Based on the current knowledge available, some of ES identified in **Table 3** cannot be assessed. This is due to gaps in knowledge, which can be broken down into three gaps categories: gaps in biophysical characterisations, gaps in economic data and gaps regarding methodologies. However, as stated in section 0, all the ES could be evaluated by stated preferences approaches. This would require specific surveys to be carried out for each CS, which was not the desired approach here. Indeed, as indicated in Section 1.3.3.2, to assess ES here the focus is on already available datasets.

Gaps in biophysical characterization can be illustrated in CS 6. First, the literature review doesn't permit quantifying the bacterial removal efficiency for *Crambe crambe*. Thus, it is not possible to know if the methodology used in this study for 6.7- water filtration can be applied to this species. Secondly, at the moment, there is no data about the biomass of sponges in the Catalan Sea, thus the assessments can only be provided per unit of biomass, and it is not possible to reach an economic value for the Catalan Sea itself.

In addition, gaps in economic data have been found. For example, in CS 3 selling prices of fished species by non-European fleets were not available and, as such, the valuation of the food provisioning for these fleets was not estimated. Other examples of gaps in economic data were found in CS 6 and CS 7. Indeed, examples of assessments of ES such as Genetic material (6.1; 7.4) or Medicinal resources (7.5) found in the literature, excluding stated preferences approaches and values transfer, are, as usually for provisioning services, based

on direct market valuation approaches (See for example Brander et al. (2024)⁷). Specifically focusing on marine genetic resources, Krusberg et al. (2024) underline that their economic assessments rely mostly on monetary valuations of marine-derived pharmaceuticals. Thus, assessments of these ES are only possible when products derived of such organisms are already identified and market information are available, which are, in general, not accessible data.

Lastly, gaps in methodologies can be illustrated with ES 6.6- Nitrification (i.e. oxidation of ammonium to oxidized inorganic nitrogen, denoted as NO_x (Alexander, 1965)). Despite being considered an important ES provided by sponges, no economic valuation of this service was identified in the existing literature. Considering that in some wastewater treatment plants, nitrogen removal from marine ecosystems involves several processes—including the oxidation of ammonium to NO_x (U.S. EPA, 2007)—one possible valuation approach could be the replacement cost method. This could follow the example of Hernández-Sancho et al. (2010), focusing only on the costs related to this specific step, as was done for 6.7 – water filtration. However, to validate this methodology, it would be necessary to ensure that the costs of this step can be separated from the other costs of the wastewater treatment plants. In addition, once the methodology would be validated it would be necessary to collect the related economic data. Another methodology could be a production function approach. Indeed, Diaz and Ward (1997) highlight that nitrate production by some sponges could account for 50 to 120% of the nutrients needed for the gross productivity of a Caribbean reef. However, the development of this methodology would require a good knowledge of the relation between NO_x production and productivity of the Catalan Sea, which is, to our knowledge, not yet known. CS 4 exhibits another example of gap in methodology. Indeed, as indicated in Section 1.3.3.2.4, estimated TGF appears to be well parameterised, and representative of the data collected. However, the model obtained does not permit to evaluate the ES 4.2- Danish recreational fishery using a ZTCM (See section 1.3.3.3.4), which is nevertheless the recommended methodology for this type of ES.

3.1.3.4. The benefits of a multidisciplinary/interdisciplinary team

Across all the CS, the benefits of forming a multidisciplinary team to realize reliable and useful economic assessments of ES emerged. Indeed, as ES assessments is an interdisciplinary research field (Häyhä and Franzese, 2014), forming teams with experts in each relevant field helps to avoid misunderstandings about the processes involved. This is illustrated in CS 6, with 6.6- Nitrification for example. Shadow prices of removing nitrogen, considering the net flow of nitrogen, can be estimated. However, as highlighted in Jiménez and Ribes (2007) some sponges produce more NO_x than they consume ammonium, leading to an increase of nitrogen in the ecosystem, which in reality should lead to assess this ES including negative economic values, while the nitrification made by sponges has positive impact in ecosystem, as demonstrated by Diaz and Ward (1997) (See section 3.1.3.3). That reflexion highlights that, without a good understanding of ES, permitted by ecological experts, economists could apply an unsuitable methodology by confusing the nitrification and nitrogen uptake services, leading to biased economic assessments. Beyond forming a multidisciplinary team of academic experts, this study also highlights the benefits of include industrial partners. Indeed, they could reduce the uncertainties and gaps about economic data, such as industrial costs of nitrification

⁷ [Ecosystem Service Valuation Database](#) consulted on 08/08/2025

or incomes generated from genetic materials, or industrial processes, such as lifetime of ultraviolet disinfection facility (see sections 1.3.3.2.6, 3.1.3.2 and 3.1.3.3).

The benefits of forming a multidisciplinary team also emerges in CS 5 (seagrass). Indeed, based on the assessments produced in section 1.3.3.3, seagrass alone presents higher economic values than system seagrass-lucinids-bacteria. However, experts' insights reveal that the presence of hosted organisms—specifically lucinid bivalves and their associated bacteria—play a crucial ecological role by removing toxic sulfide and fixing nitrogen. These processes enhance seagrass growth (Van Der Heide et al., 2012), thereby supporting the provision of numerous valuable ES (Campagne et al., 2015), thus can permit, in reality, to reach a better situation. In that context, this CS 5 illustrates that the selection of ES assessed, due to different gaps (See Section 3.1.3.3), can lead to biased conclusions if results are not discussed with experts.

3.1.3.5. A step forward: the adoption of an ecosystem services approach in decision making

The EU is continuously experimenting new pressures on the natural environment. However, the same environment is delivering ES to satisfy the rising expectations of human welfare. Human lifestyles are closely linked to the state of the natural environment. However, these linkages are still poorly understood, and when new knowledge does emerge, it is often difficult to integrate into decision-making processes. This research contributes to exploring the non-systematic evaluation of the potential nature's contribution to people. An evaluation of the changing relationship between the natural resources and the delivery of their ES. The valuation of ES should help to develop measures, policies or at least, start helping decision-making to ensure the natural resources' protection and conservation. The EC is promoting the valuation of the ES, but the adoption of this ES-approach in decision-making is less visible, and decisions usually disregard the total value of large marine and coastal ecosystems. This situation is not an exception when working across the adopted CS. The next **Table 10** indicates the status baseline (i.e. the current situation) of the management of the different species and how decisions are adopted.

Table 10: Status baseline of management processes for each case study, as well as propositions to introduce ecosystem services concept into them.

Case Study	Is the ecosystem services approach currently undertaken in decision making across CS?	
	Status baseline	Step forward: propositions
1- Mesopelagic fishes	This CS considers a potential commercial mesopelagic fishery currently non-existing. Thus, there are not specific management measures, although new knowledge is being collected to support the decisions about a potential exploitation.	The decision about its potential exploitation should be based on the whole array of ES values , including provisioning but also regulating and cultural ES.
2- Diadromous fishes	Management actions have been species-specific, carried out at the local scale, during a short period of time, with limited knowledge on the biology of many of the target species and without consideration of their full economic value . Positive outcomes to date have not been sufficient to ensure the viability of diadromous species in the long term. Climate change is compounding the main threats, acting as a driver of changes in species distributions that could	A necessary co-production of knowledge to support long-term and large-scale management of diadromous species with the enhancement of related ES is needed . Priority should be given to ES quantification in a climate-change scenario as a tool to support

Case Study	Is the ecosystem services approach currently undertaken in decision making across CS?	
	Status baseline	Step forward: propositions
	lead to new territorial interconnections and opportunities. (Policy brief).	management actions and enhance restoration (Policy brief).
3- Tropical tunas (beyond EU) & 4- Atlantic Bluefin Tuna	Stocks of tunas are managed by the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas (ICCAT). Based on stocks assessments, ICCAT estimates Total Allowable Catches (TACs) for each species, which are after validated by a committee. Once TACs are validated, there is an annual commission to share the TACs between different geopolitical entities. In this context, a part of the TACs is delivered for the European Union, which shares them between the Member States. At present, ES, except for food provisioning, are not considered as part of the management processes. Nevertheless, in the context of establishing the new strategic plan, which should be validated at the end of the year, discussions about the integration of ES, at least in a conceptual way, have begun. Currently, Denmark has not quota for Atlantic Bluefin Tuna and therefore arrangements with the EU are needed. A capture-tag-release program (See Appendix A.1.1.4) and a bilateral agreement between Denmark and Spain exists, in which Spain transfers 5 tons of its quota to Denmark in exchange of small amounts of Danish quotas of other fish species. The two exceptions are permitted for the purpose of scientific research and do not allow the sale of the tuna caught. Thus, any ES value is being used as part of those exceptions.	The introduction of ES, either conceptually or by considering their economic and/or monetary values, should therefore be initiated at least at the European level, or even at ICCAT, as is currently being discussed. This could be more complicated than trying to initiate the discussion at the national level. One option could be, for example, to consider organising a session with ES-experts at the next ICCAT annual meeting to start sharing the ES-approach concept.
4- Atlantic Bluefin Tuna		
5- Seagrass	No management measures currently exist for <i>Cymodocea nodosa</i> in Slovenia. Researchers working on this topic propose the use of the MediSkew index (Orlando-Bonaca et al., 2015). The index combines two metrics derived from leaf length data: the deviation from a reference median and the skewness of the distribution of ln-transformed leaf lengths, with greater weight given to the median deviation. Within long-term monitoring programs, the use of MediSkew is recommended to be complemented with data on meadow coverage and visual assessments of potential disease symptoms on seagrass leaves (Orlando-Bonaca et al., 2024).	The first step could be to initiate discussions with scientists to assess the possibility of forming a new index based on MediSkew and incorporating an economic dimension. This would enable biologists and economists to pool their efforts when dealing with public decision-makers and would certainly lead to greater acceptance by the latter.
6- Sponges	Not available	Not available
7- Plankton	There are no specific management measures for the conservation of plankton. Instead, management actions concerning planktonic organisms focus on their potential impact on coastal systems, such as in the form of eutrophication and harmful algal blooms, without considering the full economic value of the ES that plankton provide.	Necessity to broaden the knowledge about plankton ecology, with an increased consideration of the ES provided by planktonic biodiversity, such as biogeochemical cycling, climate regulation, and support to marine fisheries. Priority should be given to the identification and evaluation of these ES to support management actions on climate change and the welfare of fish stocks.

Previous sections of the discussion (Sections 3.1.3.2 about uncertainties and 3.1.3.3 about barriers) point, based on the current knowledge, the difficulty to obtain robust estimations of economic and/or monetary values of ES. Thus, highlighting the need to invest more resources in data collection, in well understanding and quantifying biophysical and industrial processes at play, and in the development of methodologies for ES assessments, to support decision-making on reliable and robust economic values. For instance, a situation like CS5 should be avoided, where, based on the ES that can currently be evaluated, the seagrass, which receives much more attention in previous literature, seems to deliver more valuable ES than the whole system (which integrates seagrass-lucinids and bacteria). Identifying and estimating values, as much as possible, is a challenging task. However, the lack of value does not mean a lack of relevance but maybe a data gap, which should carefully be translated into decision-making. In this example, experts are aware of the higher relevance and the role the system plays in marine ecosystems in contrast to only considering the seagrass which can be misunderstood according to their combined ES values.

As highlighted in CS 1- mesopelagic fishes, it is crucial to underlay the trade-offs supported by ES valuations at least in a conceptual way (Prellezo et al., 2024). When estimations of economic values of ES cannot be reached, consideration of trade-offs between gains and losses in ES can be considered using to coviability approaches. Indeed, coviability approaches aim to ensure reconciliation between different constraints (Doyen, 2018). For example, in a fisheries context, Doyen et al. (2017) develop a fishing management strategy based on coviability, in which three constraints tried to be fulfilled during all the study period:

- Ecological requirement: the biomasses of species must not fall below critical threshold levels.
- Social requirement: the catches must meet the food demand.
- Economic requirement: the profits of the fisheries must remain positive.

In the case of CS studied here, this type of approach could be applied, for example, in CS 5- seagrass, to consider the MediSkew and economic values of ES at the same time. Try to develop an index based on MediSkew and economic values of ES could be another approach to consider several dimensions at the same time, emphasizing the benefits of forming a multidisciplinary team, as already highlighted in Section 3.1.3.4. Lastly, if economic assessments of ES cannot be considered as input during establishment of management measures, they can be, at least, used as an indicator to validate or not their establishment. Indeed, economic estimates of ES can be compared to costs induced by management measures proposed, and if these latter are lower, there would be no reason to not implement them. For example, for seagrass, if a monitoring of it, based on MediSkew and/or spatio-temporal maps of seagrass meadows (Ivajnsič et al., 2022), indicates a bad state and management measures are proposed for its recovery, costs can be considered as acceptable until 0.6 million €₂₀₂₄, the minimal estimates of its economic values.

3.1.3.6. References

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3.2 Deliberative monetary valuation [Task 6.3]

A central finding of the DMV study is the consistently high WTP for the continued provision of plankton-based ES. An additional analysis of respondents' motivations revealed that the corresponding WTP is related to the perceived importance of plankton as a foundation of marine ecosystem functioning, with respondents placing greater value on their ecological role and contribution for future generations than on immediate or direct-use benefits. In contrast, the relatively low WTP for algal and jellyfish bloom control suggests that respondents considered this service less essential, which is consistent with the view that functional and long-term values outweigh short-term, use-oriented benefits in this context.

Differences between study regions were identified for carbon sequestration and MPA protection levels. The differences regarding carbon sequestration may reflect the level of concern of a population towards climate change, which is more pronounced in Germany compared to Italy (European Commission DG CLIMA, 2023). In terms of MPA protection levels, the discrepancy most likely reflects income differences between the German and Polish as well as between the German and Italian respondents, which was supported by an additional model, testing the effect of increased income. Among the non-price attributes, this interaction effect was only evident for both MPA levels, suggesting increasing WTP for both protection levels among individuals with higher income.

Interestingly, no significant differences were found between coastal and inland participants regarding WTP for plankton-related attributes. This implies that the value of plankton ES is not confined to those living near the sea but is broadly shared, likely reflecting the recognition of indirect use and bequest values.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. The study's small sample size limits the generalisability of the results in terms of statistical representativeness. The workshop setting, while strengthening preference formation through deliberation, may have introduced biases due to variations in facilitation, expert input, and group dynamics across countries. Furthermore, differences in regional marine ecosystems may have influenced preferences in ways not captured by the study design. Moreover, comparing WTP estimates across separate models does not account for scale heterogeneity, meaning that some of the observed differences could stem from variations in scale rather than preferences alone.

Despite these limitations, the findings provide valuable initial evidence on WTP estimates for plankton ES and their associated heterogeneity. Future research should seek to assess the robustness of our findings in larger-scale samples.

Conclusion

✓ Megafauna and Microfauna communities have been included in this research across multiple habitats. That is, holobionts communities, seagrass and plankton physically associated with benthic fauna, fishes from deep-seas (mesopelagic) to coastal and freshwater ecosystems (diadromous) and tuna fishes in epipelagic habitats. All of them have been assessed following a holistic view to work towards developing a new framework which coupled physical characteristics of delivered ES by those groups with their economic assessment.

✓ For all these habitats and functional groups, this research has used Standard Economic Accounts, National Accounting, based on direct market goods and services valued at real markets to provide assessment of fish provisioning ES, or carbon sequestration ES. For non-market goods and services, such as the cultural value associated with recreational fishing, shadow prices are assessed using revealed preferences (travel cost) or stated preferences (contingent valuation) are applied to value the tropical tuna cultural value linked to local identity, among other services. As a step forward from the assessment of biodiversity value of marine ecosystems towards the elaboration of biodiversity-driven protective policies, this research also integrates public attitudes with respect to the valuation of marine ecosystems along the European littoral. A set of Deliberative Monetary Value workshops along the TREC route have been developed.

✓ A total of 50 ES has been identified being the most represented CICES category the Regulation and Maintenance (47%), followed by the Cultural (28%) and finally, the Provisioning category (26%). From which economic accounting is provided for 18 ES types, with a higher number of evaluations covering different local, regional, and global ecosystems. Overall, in absolute values the highest economic estimation of ES is reached for plankton in Gaeta Gulf based on the delivery of food for higher trophic levels while the lowest is for system seagrass-lucinids-bacteria along the Slovenian coast based on its role with carbon sequestration ES. By summing the contribution of all the ES, expressed in absolute terms, plankton in the three gulfs of Italy presents the highest economic estimations, ranging from 23 to 2,153 million €₂₀₂₄, followed by tunas in tropical Atlantic ecoregion (from 448 to 452 million €₂₀₂₄), diadromous fishes in EU Atlantic Area (considering 2.1 and 2.4, from 23 to 43 million €₂₀₂₄) and finally seagrass in Slovenia (from 0.6, considering system seagrass-lucinids-bacteria, to 10 million €₂₀₂₄, considering seagrass alone). Focusing on total economic values per square meter the highest economic estimation is obtained for seagrass, followed by plankton and finally tropical tunas.

✓ A long-term monetary and economic measure of marine biodiversity still faces multiple limiting factors which prevent understanding the biodiversity contribution to the citizens' wellbeing (social benefits). Among these, it is the scientific capacity to sample marine ecosystems over the long run, across spatial and temporal scales. An urgent requirement is for environmental researchers, who should also adopt an ES-approach from the fieldwork onwards. The major gap stated by this research is the lack of consistent measure of the aquatic functional groups in its physic-chemical context, to produce the needed data for applying economic models and therefore, for reaching an ocean accounting, that includes ES assessment. It prevented the estimation of a higher number of identified ES.

✓ Moreover, this research also faces the challenge of scaling-up the effects of marine biodiversity in space (local to regional, or even to global), across communities, and, to cover the huge number of functions and services simultaneously. As this research demonstrates,

the assessment of only one specific service, for one specific functional group (for instance, the evaluation of the carbon sequestration ES delivered by seagrass) demands a high number of human resources and capacities (interdisciplinary background) and economic resources.

✓ This research offers a relevant tool to overcome some of these limitations, that is, a topic modelling approach is provided to facilitate an initial holistic identification of ES provided by marine ecosystems. Its potential to identify ES is higher in relation to a more traditional literature review combined with empirical knowledge.

✓ ES literacy is compulsory to educate citizens but also managers, and policymakers about the monetary yield these ecosystems are providing, which should be understood as a powerful tool to drive marine conservation. Understanding the diverse but consistent monetary values for those habitats (from benthic to epipelagic, mesopelagic habitats, also including freshwater aquatic systems) and their potential uses in decision making is essential for shaping effective protection of the marine and freshwater ecosystems. According to the empirical knowledge collected by this research thanks to the participatory process adopted, currently, management of the studies functional groups rarely consider their delivery value of ES as part of their own management. However, these ES values could play a crucial role for instance, to avoid the excessive compartmentalization when managing transboundary fisheries (such as, diadromous fishes). Following with this example, the ES-approach contribute to land-sea continuum research moving across the species life cycle providing a commonly adopted standard criteria. Also, public values and the public's awareness of the economic contribution of marine biodiversity to ES, should drive marine conservation policies.

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Annexes

A. Natural Capital Accounting [Task 6.2]

A.1. Applied Natural Accounting: a collection of case studies

A.1.1. CS descriptions

A.1.1.1. CS 1: Mesopelagic fishes in Bay of Biscay

This CS comes from the project SUMMER, funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement n°817806. The experts consulted are Raúl Prellezo and Xavier Corrales (AZTI, Spain).

In this project the researchers aimed to evaluate the economic impacts of opening a mesopelagic fishery in Bay of Biscay. The catches made by this fishery would be used as raw materials for production of FO and FM for aquaculture, creating a new valuable ES (1.1). Nevertheless, non-caught mesopelagic fishes already provide other ES. They include climate regulation due to DVM of mesopelagic fishes (1.3), and cultural value associated with their mere existence (1.4). At the same time, beyond the direct effects of fishing on target species, fishing has the potential to disrupt food webs, thus, impacting stocks and so compromising their ability to provide ES supporting human well-being. In this CS these ES include the current commercial fisheries in Bay of Biscay exploiting other species than mesopelagic (1.2), and cultural value associated to commercial and non-commercial species (1.4). Authors study the impacts of opening a mesopelagic fishery by evaluating the economic trade-offs in terms of ES between a situation in which the mesopelagic fishes are exploited at the MSY level and the current situation, BAU scenario, with no exploitation of mesopelagic fishes. By adopting this methodology, the food provisioning provided by this new potential fishery is considered as a provisioning service.

More information about this CS are available in Prellezo et al. (2024a) and in [SUMMER website](#).

A.1.1.2. CS 2: Diadromous fishes in EU Atlantic Area

This CS comes from [DiadES project](#). In general, numbers of diadromous fish species are declining across their Atlantic distribution, despite current management efforts, causing ecological and socioeconomic impacts on local communities. However, it is for mention evidence on contribution to ES supported by European and global conservation policies for individual species such as salmon or the European eel. Diadromous species transition between marine and freshwater environments, and provide a unique set of benefits for local communities and people visiting the water bodies within their range. Drouineau et al. (2018) identify a decline in abundance since the late 20th Century, when diadromous fish accounted for 75% of commercial landings from inland fisheries in case study locations in France. This decrease was also accompanied by a decrease of the economic value associated to the ES. Although certain aspects of diadromous fish species biology and ecological roles have been well studied, evidence of the wide-ranging social and economic benefits, provided by all diadromous species in the northeast Atlantic has not longer studied. Likewise, these services have neither been monetary assessed being very few the research efforts to identify the benefits they provide. Those fishers offer an example of transnational approach, needed to enable a common management for the conservation and enhancement of the ES associated

to these species, that includes the explicit long-term and large-scale issues related to climate change.

A.1.1.3. CS 3: Tunas in Tropical Atlantic Ecoregion

This CS comes from the BIOcean5D project, funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement n°101059915. The experts consulted are Eider Andonegi (AZTI, Spain), Xavier Corrales (AZTI, Spain), Maria José Juan Jordá Maria José (IEO, Spain) and Josu Meléndez (AZTI, Spain).

This CS focuses on the Tropical Atlantic Ecoregion, where tropical tunas—such as skipjack (*Katsuwonus pelamis*), yellowfin (*Thunnus albacares*), and bigeye tuna (*Thunnus obesus*)—along with other billfishes and sharks, represent some of the largest predatory species in pelagic ecosystems, feeding primarily on smaller prey. Based on a literature review six ES are identified for this CS: one provisioning service, two regulating and maintenance services and three cultural services. The first one relies on fisheries exploiting as targeted species tuna's species (3.1). Based on the [International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas \(ICCAT\) statistical database](#), for this area in 2022, these 3 species represented around 98% of the total landing (*Katsuwonus pelamis* – 59%, *Thunnus albacares* - 29% and *Thunnus obesus* – 10%). ICCAT data also indicates that, in 2022, 32 countries were fishing in this area, and the 4 main fleets were Ghanaian Purse Seiners (23% of the total landing), Spanish Purse Seiners (11% of the total landing), Senegalese Purse Seiners (11% of the total landing) and French Purse Seiners (10% of the total landing). Regarding the regulating and maintenance services identified, the first one is the carbon sequestration (3.2). Indeed, Mariani et al. (2020) indicate that dense and large-bodied fusiform fish species realize carbon sequestration through the sinking of their carcasses when they died in open ocean. The second regulating and maintenance service identified for this CS is maintaining balance in oceanic ecosystems (3.3). Finally, the three cultural services identified are: the cultural value of endangered and threatened species (3.4), the cultural value of the tuna industry (3.5) and recreational tuna fisheries (3.6). The first one relies on the willingness of people to preserve endangered and threatened species such as sharks or turtles for example (Amuakwa-Mensah et al., 2018). As these species can be bycatches in the commercial fisheries made in this area, this ES has a negative interaction with the food provisioning ES (3.1). The second one arises from several valuable components such as combination of natural landscape and port fishing; performing arts; social, ritual and festive events; and tangible cultural heritage immovable.

A.1.1.4. CS 4: Atlantic Bluefin Tuna in Skagerrak (Denmark)

This CS comes from the publication Maar et al. (2022), supported by the EU interreg project MarGen II, Danish rod and net license funds, the Nordic Council of Ministers (project nos. 141-2016-Tuna; 180-2018-Tuna tagging), European Maritime and Fisheries Fund, and the Hempel Foundation. The expert consulted is Brian MacKenzie (DTU Aqua, Denmark).

This CS focuses on the recovery of the Atlantic Bluefin Tuna (denoted by ABFT) in Skagerrak (Denmark). After a collapse, during the 90s, of the ABFT biomass, and thus the commercial and recreative fisheries related, in Skagerrak waters, the implementation of management measures by ICCAT have permitted the recovery of the species in this area. At the moment, fishing bluefin tuna in Danish waters for either commercial or recreational purposes is generally forbidden because Denmark presently does not have a quota in place. There have been, however, exceptions to this regulation for research purposes. A capture-tag-release

program has been operated annually as part of a research collaboration between two universities in Denmark and Sweden (Technical University of Denmark [DTU Aqua] and Swedish Agricultural University [SLU Aqua]) since 2017 (Aarestrup et al., 2022; MacKenzie et al., 2020). In this program, volunteer recreational anglers have been allowed to catch bluefin tunas for tagging and release; the main objective of the program is to allow researchers and the general community to learn more about bluefin tuna migration and the factors affecting its spatial distribution, including the presence in waters near Denmark and Sweden. The participating anglers must meet several requirements to be allowed to participate, and the fishing is conducted in a restricted location and time period under the authority and control of local (Danish and Swedish) fishery management authorities. In that context, two ES are identified for this CS: the potential commercial future fishery (4.1) and the recreational fishery (4.2) (Maar et al., 2022). Indeed, first, Denmark's commercial fishing sector has expressed a willingness to develop a fishery for Atlantic bluefin tuna (ABFT) intended for human consumption, should a sufficient quota become accessible in the future. Secondly, historically, when bluefin tuna were present in Danish waters in the 1940s-1960s, foreign tourists came from e.g. UK and USA for recreational fishing and to participate in bluefin tuna fishing tournaments in the Øresund (MacKenzie & Myers, 2007). This could happen again if bluefin tuna fishing were allowed in Danish waters. Bluefin tuna have also become an eco-tour species for sighting tours in Danish waters (e. g., Øresund), indicating the emergence of another ES: Eco-tourism (4.3). The species commonly jumps partly or completely out of the water and swims near the surface when pursuing prey (e. g. garfish *Belone belone*); numerous photos and videos on social media document this behaviour since the species returned to Danish waters, and older images are available in historical reports (Svendsen, 1948). Several eco-tour operators in both Denmark and Sweden near the Øresund now take guests on tours to see this behavior. These tours are offered several times per day, almost daily during ca. 6-8 weeks in late summer – early autumn. Guests have the possibility to see this species and its prey behave in its natural environment (instead of e. g., in aquaria settings). Moreover, some of the tours include marine biologist guides who provide guests with information about tuna biology, marine ecosystems and ocean sustainability. As a result, ocean literacy and sustainability awareness of the guests also increases.

While a full economic valuation of such activities is not conducted for the moment, they do indicate that presence of the species in Danish waters is already generating new economic activity and has potential to generate even more in future.

A.1.1.5. CS 5: System seagrass-lucinids-bacteria along the Slovenian coast

Data for this CS come from the Italian PRIN2022 project ENGAGE (grant n. 20223R4FJK), funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU. The consulted experts are Jillian Petersen (CeMESS, Austria) and Ulisse Cardini (SZN, Italy).

This CS focuses on system formed by the seagrass species *Cymodocea nodosa*-associated lucinids, which themselves contain bacteria. Chemosymbiosis relation, defined as nutritional partnership (Sogin et al., 2020), occurs between the species of the system in this CS. Data provided by experts are lab data using material from Piran (Slovenia); in that context the economic assessments provided for this CS are supposed to be representative of the situation along the Slovenian coast. The identification is based on a review on the general literature on seagrass, however experts consulted advocate that the ES identified are also

provided by the system considered in this CS. Seven regulating and maintenance services and one cultural service are identified. Four of the seven regulating and maintenance services are provided by the system, while two are provided by the seagrass only and one by the bacteria inside the lucinids. Global system provide oxygen production (5.1) (Van Der Heide et al., 2012), carbon sequestration (5.2) (Van Der Heide et al., 2012) and storage (5.3) (Bañolas et al., 2020) and nutrient cycling (5.4) (Buonocore et al., 2020). Seagrasses provide nursery functions (5.5) (Tuya et al., 2014) as well as costal protection (5.6) (Campagne et al., 2015). Bacteria provide the oxidation of sulfide (5.7) (Van Der Heide et al., 2012). Finally, the cultural service identified, provided by seagrass, is recreation function (5.8) (Buonocore et al., 2020).

A.1.1.6. CS 6: Holobionts Sponges-microbes in Catalan Sea

This CS comes from the BIOcean5D project, funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement n°101059915. The experts consulted are José Montoya Terran (CNRS, France) and Pauline Narvaez (CNRS, France). In this CS, 10 SE provided by holobionts sponges-microbes are identified. As for the CS 5, this identification is based on a review of the general literature on sponges, however the experts consulted advocate that the ES identified are also provided by the specific sponges' species present in the Catalan Sea (*i.e.*: *Agelas oroides*, *Chondrosia reniformis*, *Dysidea avara*, *Crambe crambe*). While experts are able to identify sponge species, current knowledge does not allow for the identification of symbionts.

Three provisioning services are identified: provision of genetic material (6.1) (Krusberg et al., 2024, Taylor et al., 2007, Anjum et al., 2016) and cosmetics (6.2) (Esposito et al., 2021) and the aquaculture (6.3) (Amato et al., 2024). Regarding the regulating and maintenance services, 6 are identified: carbon sequestration (6.4) (Taylor et al., 2007, Bell, 2008), carbon cycling (including dissolved organic carbon uptake and conversion) (6.5) (Taylor et al., 2007, Bell, 2008, Thomas et al., 2016), nitrification (6.6) (Ribes et al., 2012, Jiménez and Ribes, 2007), water filtration (6.7) (Aguilo-Arce et al., 2023), provision of microhabitats (6.8) (Bell, 2008, Hultgren and Duffy, 2010) and sulfur cycling (6.9) (Taylor et al., 2007). Finally, some studies such as Anjum et al. (2016) or Ottaviani (2020) point out the possibility of creating new future material thanks to sponges (6.10).

A.1.1.7. CS 7: Plankton in three Gulfs in Italy

This CS comes from the project ISSPA—PO FEAMP Campania 2014–2020 (DRD n. 35 of 15th March 2018) and the BIOcean5D project, funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement n°101059915. The experts consulted are Luca Russo (SZN, Italy), Domenico D'Alelio (SZN, Italy) and Marina Chifflet (AZTI, Spain).

This CS examines the spatiotemporal socio-ecological variability of plankton food webs along the entire coast of the Campania Region (Tyrrhenian Sea, Mediterranean Sea). It focuses on three gulfs subject to significant anthropogenic pressures—the Gulfs of Gaeta, Naples, and Salerno (Tornerio and d'Alcalà, 2014) — during two different seasons (autumn 2020 and summer 2021). Specifically, the study investigates: i) the effects of varying environmental conditions (*i.e.*, seasons and river inputs) on the trophic structure and carbon fluxes occurring within the planktonic community (Bellardini et al., 2025); and ii) the identification and qualitative assessment of the main ES provided by planktonic organisms, as well as the relationship between plankton biodiversity and these services (Russo et al., 2025).

Plankton, i.e., organisms unable to swim against ocean currents (Hensen, 1887), comprise highly dynamic and strongly interacting groups, spanning from unicellular (e.g., phytoplankton) to metazoan organisms (e.g., zooplankton) (Sunagawa et al., 2020). Through a systematic literature review, Russo et al. (2025) identified the principal ES provided by plankton, covering all three major groups in the CICES. Among provisioning services, plankton is involved for example in providing food for humans (7.3). Plankton also provides biochemical products, such as antioxidants (7.1), biofuels (7.2), genetic resources (7.4), and medicinal compounds (7.5). Regarding the regulating and maintenance services, planktonic communities, through the activities of photosynthetic organisms like the phytoplankton, play a fundamental role for in primary production (7.6) and climate regulation (7.7) (Russo et al., 2025). They also contribute to maintaining biogeochemical cycles (7.8) and water quality (7.9) (Russo et al., 2025). Plankton also provide food for higher marine trophic levels (7.10). Finally, plankton delivers cultural ES such as cultural heritage (7.12), recreation (7.13), educational value (7.14), and aesthetic inspiration (7.15), with numerous examples of these communities influencing art and museum exhibitions (Russo et al., 2025).

Using this information, Russo et al. (2025) mapped the ES identified in the literature against plankton food webs within the Gulfs of Gaeta, Naples, and Salerno during autumn and summer. They found that environmental conditions affected the range and magnitude of ES potentially provided by these communities, with variations in food-web structure across gulfs and seasons corresponding to differences in ES provision (Russo et al., 2025). More information about this CS is available in Russo et al. (2025) and Bellardini et al. (2025).

A.1.1.8. References

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A.1.2. FG and fleets for CS 1

Table 11: Functional groups of EWE for CS 1

N°	Functional Group (FG)	Species
1	Diving and pursuit divers' seabirds	<i>Alca torda</i> , <i>Calonectris diomedea</i> , <i>Fratelurca arctica</i> , <i>Hydrobates pelagicus</i> , <i>Phalacrocorax aristotelis</i> , <i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i> , <i>Puffinus puffinus</i> , <i>Puffinus mauritanicus</i> , <i>Uria aalge</i>
2	Surface feeders seabirds	<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i> , <i>Larus argentatus</i> , <i>L. cachinnans</i> , <i>L. fuscus</i> , <i>L. marinus</i> , <i>L. michahellis</i> , <i>L. ridibundus</i> , <i>Morus bassanus</i> , <i>Rissa tridactyla</i>
3	Baleen whales	<i>Balaenoptera acutorostrata</i> , <i>B. borealis</i> , <i>B. musculus</i> , <i>B. physalus</i> , <i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i> <i>Physeter macrocephalus</i>
4	Toothed cetaceans	<i>Delphinus delphis</i> , <i>Globicephala macrorhynchus</i> , <i>Globicephala melas</i> , <i>Grampus griseus</i> , <i>Halichoerus grypus</i> , <i>Lagenorhynchus acutus</i> , <i>L. albirostris</i> , <i>Kogia breviceps</i> , <i>K. simus</i> , <i>Mesoplodon europaeus</i> , <i>M. mirus</i> , <i>Orcinus orca</i> , <i>Phoca vitulina</i> , <i>Phocoena phocoena</i> , <i>Pseudorca crassidens</i> , <i>Stenella coeruleoalba</i> , <i>Tursiops truncatus</i> , <i>Ziphius cavirostris</i>
5	Demersal sharks	<i>Mustelus asterias</i> , <i>M. mustelus</i> , <i>Squalus acanthias</i> , <i>Squalus blainville</i> , <i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i> , <i>Scyliorhinus stellaris</i>
6	Pelagic sharks	<i>Alopias vulpinus</i> , <i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i> , <i>Lamna nasus</i> , <i>Prionace glauca</i>
7	Deep water sharks	<i>Centrophorus squamosus</i> , <i>Centroscyrnus coelolepis</i> , <i>Chimaera monstrosa</i> , <i>Dalatias licha</i> , <i>Deania calcea</i> , <i>Deania profundorum</i> , <i>Etmopterus spinax</i> , <i>Galeorhinus galeus</i> , <i>Galeus atlanticus</i> , <i>Galeus melastomus</i> , <i>Hexanchus griseus</i> , <i>Scymnodon ringens</i>
8	Rays and skates	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i> , <i>Myliobatis aquila</i> , <i>Dipturus batis</i> , <i>Raja clavata</i> , <i>Leucoraja circularis</i> , <i>Leucoraja fullonica</i> , <i>Raja microocellata</i> , <i>Raja montagui</i> , <i>Leucoraja naevus</i>
9	Bluefin tuna	<i>Thunnus thynnus</i>
10	Albacore	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>
11	Other large pelagic fishes	<i>Belone belone</i> , <i>Brama brama</i> , <i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i> , <i>Pomatomus saltatrix</i> , <i>Sarda sarda</i> , <i>Scomberesox saurus</i> , <i>Thunnus obesus</i>
12	Mackerel	<i>Scomber colias</i> , <i>S. scombrus</i>
13	Horse mackerel	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i> , <i>T. mediterraneus</i>
14	Sardine	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>
15	Anchovy	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>
16	Other plantivorous fishes	<i>Alosa alosa</i> , <i>Alosa fallax</i> , <i>Argentina sphyraena</i> , <i>Boops boops</i> , <i>Capros aper</i> , <i>Clupea harengus</i> , <i>Gadiculus argenteus</i> , <i>Osmerus eperlanus</i> , <i>Sprattus sprattus</i> , <i>Scomberesox saurus saurus</i> , <i>Macroramphosus scolopax</i>
17	Mesopelagic fishes	<i>Alepocephalus bairdii</i>, <i>Arctozenus risso</i>, <i>Argyropelecus hemigymnus</i>, <i>Benthosema glaciale</i>, <i>Ceratoscopelus maderensis</i>, <i>Chlorophthalmus agassizi</i>, <i>Lampanyctus crocodilus</i>, <i>Maurollicus muelleri</i>, <i>Myctophum punctatum</i>
18	Anglerfish	<i>Lophius budegassa</i> , <i>L. piscatorius</i>
19	Sea Bass	<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>
20	Blue whiting	<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i>
21	Adult Hake	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i> (≥ 21 cm)
22	Juvenile Hake	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i> (< 21 cm)
23	Poor cod	<i>Trisopterus esmarkii</i> , <i>T. luscus</i> , <i>T. minutus</i>
24	Megrim	<i>Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis</i> , <i>L. boscii</i>
25	Common sole	<i>Solea solea</i>
26	Flatfishes	<i>Arnoglossus imperialis</i> , <i>Arnoglossus laterna</i> , <i>Arnoglossus thori</i> , <i>Bathysolea profundicola</i> , <i>Buglossidium luteum</i> , <i>Citharus linguatula</i> , <i>Dicologlossa cuneata</i> , <i>Glyptocephalus cynoglossus</i> , <i>Limanda limanda</i> , <i>Microchirus variegatus</i> , <i>Microstomus kitt</i> , <i>Platichthys flesus</i> , <i>Pegusa lascaris</i> , <i>Pleuronectes platessa</i> , <i>Scophthalmus maximus</i> , <i>Scophthalmus rhombus</i>
27	Mulletts	<i>Mullus barbatus</i> , <i>M. surmuletus</i>
28	Large demersal fishes	<i>Argyrosomus regius</i> , <i>Conger conger</i> , <i>Gadus morhua</i> , <i>Melanogrammus aeglefinus</i> , <i>Molva dypterygia</i> , <i>Molva macrophthalma</i> , <i>Molva molva</i> , <i>Phycis phycis</i> , <i>Pollachius pollachius</i> , <i>Pollachius virens</i> , <i>Zeus faber</i>
29	Medium demersal fishes	<i>Chelidonichthys lucerna</i> , <i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i> , <i>Lithognathus mormyrus</i> , <i>Merlangius merlangus</i> , <i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i> , <i>Pagrus pagrus</i> , <i>Phycis blennoides</i> , <i>Scorpaena scrofa</i> , <i>Sparus aurata</i>

N°	Functional Group (FG)	Species
30	Small demersal fishes	<i>Acantholabrus palloni</i> , <i>Ammodytes tobianus</i> , <i>Aphia minuta</i> , <i>Blennius ocellaris</i> , <i>Callionymus lyra</i> , <i>Callionymus maculatus</i> , <i>Callionymus reticulatus</i> , <i>Chelidonichthys obscurus</i> , <i>Chelidonichthys cuculus</i> , <i>Chelidonichthys lastoviza</i> , <i>Chelon labrosus</i> , <i>Ctenolabrus rupestris</i> , <i>Deltentosteus quadrimaculatus</i> , <i>Diplodus sargus</i> , <i>Diplodus vulgaris</i> , <i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i> , <i>Gaidropsarus macrophthalmus</i> , <i>Gaidropsarus vulgaris</i> , <i>Gobiidae</i> , <i>Labrus mixtus</i> , <i>Lepidotrigla dieuzeidei</i> , <i>Lesueurigobius friesii</i> , <i>Liza ramada</i> , <i>Malacocephalus laevis</i> , <i>Nezumia aequalis</i> , <i>Ophidion barbatum</i> , <i>Pagellus acarne</i> , <i>Pagellus erythrinus</i> , <i>Pomatoschistus minutus</i> , <i>Pomatoschistus pictus</i> , <i>Scorpaena loppei</i> , <i>Serranus cabrilla</i> , <i>SpondylIOSoma cantharus</i> , <i>Trachinus draco</i> , <i>Trigla lyra</i> , <i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>
31	Deep-sea fishes	<i>Beryx decadactylus</i> , <i>Cepola macrophthalma</i> , <i>Coelorinchus caelorrhincus</i> , <i>Hoplostethus mediterraneus</i> , <i>Lepidion lepidion</i> , <i>Mora moro</i> , <i>Notacanthus bonapartei</i> , <i>Synaphobranchus kaupii</i> , <i>Trachyrincus scabrous</i>
32	Benthic cephalopods	<i>Bathypolypus sponsalis</i> , <i>Eledone cirrhosa</i> , <i>Octopus vulgaris</i> , <i>Octopus salutti</i> , <i>Rondeletiola minor</i> , <i>Sepia elegans</i> , <i>Sepia officinalis</i> , <i>Sepia orbignyana</i> , <i>Sepietta oweniana</i>
33	Benthopelagic cephalopods	<i>Alloteuthis media</i> , <i>A. subulata</i> , <i>Illex coindetii</i> , <i>I. illecebrosus</i> , <i>Loligo forbesi</i> , <i>L. vulgaris</i> , <i>Todarodes sagittatus</i> , <i>Todaropsis eblanae</i>
34	Norway lobster	<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i>
35	Pelagic crab	<i>Polybius henslowii</i>
36	Zooplankton feeder shrimps	<i>Acanthephyra pelagica</i> , <i>Acanthephyra purpurea</i> , <i>Chlorotocus crassicornis</i> , <i>Eusergestes arcticus</i> , <i>Gnathophausia zoea</i> , <i>Pasiphaea sivado</i> , <i>Pasiphaea multidentata</i> , <i>Plesionika acanthonotus</i> , <i>Plesionika heterocarpus</i> , <i>Plesionika martia</i> , <i>Sergia robusta</i>
37	Benthos feeders decapods	<i>Alpheus glaber</i> , <i>Aristeus antennatus</i> , <i>Atelecyclus rotundatus</i> , <i>Bathynectes maravigna</i> , <i>Cancer pagurus</i> , <i>Crangon crangon</i> , <i>Dichelopandalus bonnieri</i> , <i>Galathea dispersa</i> , <i>Geryon trispinosus</i> , <i>Inachus dorsettensis</i> , <i>Homarus Gammarus</i> , <i>Liocarcinus depurator</i> , <i>Macropipus toberculatus</i> , <i>Macropodia longipes</i> , <i>Maja squinado</i> , <i>Penaeopsis serrata</i> , <i>Palaemon serratus</i> , <i>Palinurus mauritanicus</i> , <i>Pandalina brevisrostris</i> , <i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i> , <i>Penaeus kerathurus</i> , <i>Philocheras echinulatus</i> , <i>Polycheles typhlops</i> , <i>Pontophilus norvegicus</i> , <i>Pontophilus spinosus</i> , <i>Processa canaliculata</i> , <i>Rissoides desmaresti</i> , <i>Solenocera membranacea</i>
38	Detritus feeders decapods	<i>Anapagurus laevis</i> , <i>Goneplax rhomboides</i> , <i>Munida intermedia</i> , <i>M. iris</i> , <i>M. sarsi</i> , <i>M. tenuimana</i> , <i>Pagurus alatus</i> , <i>Pagurus bernhardus</i> , <i>Pagurus excavatus</i> , <i>Pagurus prideaux</i> , <i>Penaeus vannamei</i> , <i>Palaemon longirostris</i>
39	Bivalves	
40	Polychaetes	
41	Suprabenthos	<i>mysids, isopods, amphipods, cumaceans and copepods</i>
42	Echinodermata	
43	Other invertebrates	<i>gastropods, cnidarians, sponges</i>
44	Gelatinous plankton	<i>cubozoa, hydrozoa, scyphozoa and tunicata</i>
45	Macrozooplankton (>2000 µm)	
46	Mesozooplankton (<2000 and >200 µm)	
47	Microzooplankton (<200 µm)	
48	Benthic primary producers	<i>benthic macrophytes and microphytobenthos</i>
49	Small phytoplankton (<20µm)	
50	Large phytoplankton (>20 µm)	
51	Detritus	
52	Discards	

Table 12: Fleets of EWE for CS 1

N°	Fleet
1	Spanish, excluding Basque, demersal trawl
2	Spanish Basque demersal trawl
3	Spanish purse seine
4	Spanish coastal fishery
5	Spanish offshore fishery
6	French demersal trawl
7	French pelagic trawl
8	French Nephrops trawl
9	French purse seine
10	French coastal fishery
11	French offshore fishery
12	Spanish recreational fishery
13	French recreational fishery

A.1.3. FG and fleets for CS 3

Table 13: Functional groups of EwE for CS 3.

Nº	Functional Group (FG)	Species	Carbon sequestration
1	Seabirds	<i>Anous stolidus</i> , <i>A. minutus</i> , <i>Bulweria bulwerii</i> , <i>Calonectris borealis/diomedea</i> , <i>C. edwardsii</i> , <i>Fregetta tropica</i> , <i>Hydrobates pelagicus</i> , <i>H. leucorhoa</i> , <i>H. castro</i> , <i>Oceanites oceanicus</i> , <i>Onychoprion fuscatus</i> , <i>Phaethon aethereus</i> , <i>Ardenna gravis</i> , <i>A. grisea</i> , <i>Puffinus puffinus</i> , <i>Stercorarius pomarinus</i> , <i>Sula dactylatra</i> , <i>S. leucogaster</i>	No
2	Sea turtles	<i>Caretta caretta</i> , <i>Chelonia mydas</i> , <i>Dermochelys coriacea</i> , <i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i> , <i>Lepidochelys kempii</i> , <i>L. olivacea</i>	No
3	Baleen whales	<i>Balaenoptera borealis</i> , <i>B. brydei</i> , <i>B. musculus</i> , <i>B. physalus</i> , <i>Megaptera novaengliae</i>	No
4	Toothed whales	<i>Deplhinus delphis</i> , <i>Feresa attenuata</i> , <i>Globicephala macrorhynchus</i> , <i>Grampus griseus</i> , <i>Kogia sima</i> , <i>Lagenodelphis hosei</i> , <i>Mesoplodon densirostris</i> , <i>M. europaeus</i> , <i>Orcinus orca</i> , <i>Peponocephala electra</i> , <i>Physeter macrocephalus</i> , <i>Pseudorca crassidens</i> , <i>Stenella attenuata</i> , <i>S. clymene</i> , <i>S. coeruleoalba</i> , <i>S. frontalis</i> , <i>S. longirostris</i> , <i>Steno bredanensis</i> , <i>Tursiops truncatus</i>	No
5	Whale shark	<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	Yes
6	Mantas	<i>Mobula birostris</i> , <i>M. mobular</i> , <i>M. thurstoni</i> , <i>M. tarapacana</i>	No
7	Pelagic rays	<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i>	No
8	Blue shark	<i>Prionace glauca</i>	Yes
9	Shortfin mako	<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	Yes
10	Silky shark	<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i>	Yes
11	Pelagic sharks	<i>Alopias vulpinus</i> , <i>A. superciliosus</i> , <i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i> , <i>C. obscurus</i> , <i>C. signatus</i> , <i>Carcharodon carcharias</i> , <i>Centrophorus granulosus</i> , <i>Dalatias licha</i> , <i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i> , <i>Galeorhinus galeus</i> , <i>Ginglymostoma cirratum</i> , <i>Heptranchias perlo</i> , <i>Hexanchus griseus</i> , <i>Isistius brasiliensis</i> , <i>Isurus paucus</i> , <i>Lamna nasus</i> , <i>Pseudocarcharias kamoharai</i> , <i>Sphyrna lewini</i> , <i>S. mokarran</i> , <i>S. zygaena</i> , <i>Squalus acanthias</i>	Yes
12	Swordfish	<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Yes
13	Billfishes	<i>Makaira nigricans</i> , <i>Kajikia albida</i> , <i>Istiophorus albicans</i> , <i>Tetrapturus pfluegeri</i>	Yes
14	Yellowfin adult	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yes
15	Yellowfin juvenile	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	No
16	Bigeye adult	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Yes
17	Bigeye juvenile	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	No
18	Skipjack adult	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Yes
19	Skipjack juvenile	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	No
20	Albacore	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Yes
21	Bluefin tuna	<i>Thunnus thynnus</i>	Yes
22	Small tunas and other scombrids	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i> , <i>Auxis rochei</i> , <i>A. thazard</i> , <i>Euthynnus alletteratus</i> , <i>Orcynopsis unicolor</i> , <i>Sarda sarda</i> , <i>Scomberomorus brasiliensis</i> , <i>S. cavalla</i> , <i>S. tritor</i> , <i>Thunnus atlanticus</i>	Yes
23	Carangidae	<i>Caranx crysos</i> , <i>C. hippos</i> , <i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i> , <i>Lichi amia</i> , <i>Naucrates ductor</i> , <i>Seriola rivoliana</i> , <i>Uraspis secunda</i>	Yes
24	Epipelagic fishes I	<i>Belone belone</i> , <i>Coryphaena equiselis</i> , <i>C. hippurus</i> , <i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	Yes

Nº	Functional Group (FG)	Species	Carbon sequestration
25	Epipelagic fishes II	<i>Aluterus monoceros</i> , <i>Balistes capriscus</i> , <i>B. punctatus</i> , <i>Canthidermis maculata</i> , <i>Canthigaster</i> sp., <i>Diodon hystrix</i> , <i>Echeneis naucrates</i> , <i>Kyohosus sectatrix</i> , <i>Lagocephalus lagocephalus</i> , <i>Lobotes surinamensis</i> , <i>Masturus lanceolatus</i> , <i>Mola mola</i> , <i>Ranzania laevis</i> , <i>Remora remora</i> , <i>Shoeroides</i> sp.	Yes
26	Small epipelagic fishes	<i>Cheilopogon cyanopterus</i> , <i>C. furcatus</i> , <i>C. milleri</i> , <i>Exocoetus volitans</i> , <i>Hirundichthys affinis</i> , <i>Scomberesox saurus</i> , <i>Oxyporhamphus micropterus/similis</i> , <i>Dactylopterus volitans</i> , <i>Decapterus punctatus</i>	No
27	Large mesopelagic fishes	<i>Alepisaurus ferox</i> , <i>Brama brama</i> , <i>B. caribbea</i> , <i>Taractichthys longipinnis</i> , <i>Gempylus serpens</i> , <i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i> , <i>Ruvettus pretiosus</i> , <i>Lampris guttatus</i> , <i>Trachipterus trachipterus</i> , Trichiuridae	No
28	Small mesopelagic fishes	<i>Cubiceps pauciradiatus</i> , <i>Neoscopelus macrolepidotus</i> , <i>Vinciguerria nimbaria</i> , Gonostomatidae, Myctophidae, Paralepididae, Sternoptychidae	No
29	Pelagic cephalopods	Argonautidae, Cranchiidae, Enoploteuthidae, Ommastrephidae, Onychoteuthidae	No
30	Gelatinous plankton	Salpida, Scyphozoa, Siphonophorae	No
31	Macrozooplankton (20-200 mm)	Amphipoda, Decapoda, Euohasiacea, Ichthyoplankton, Polychaeta	No
32	Mesozooplankton (0.2-20 mm)	Atlantidae, Cavoliniidae, Copepoda, Decapoda larvae, Stomatopoda larvae, Tonnidae	No
33	Microzooplankton (0.02-0.2 mm)	Ciliophora, Foraminifera, Radiolaria, Rotifera	No
34	Phytoplankton		No
35	Detritus		No
36	Discards		/

Table 14: Fleets of EwE for CS 3. Acronyms used for gears are based on ICCAT Data Code System: PS: Purse Seine, FAD: Fish Aggregating Device, FSC: Free School Catching, BB: Bait Boat, LL: Longline, HL: Hand Line, GN: Gillnet, TW: Trawl, TP: Trap, TR: Trolling Line, HS: Haul Seine, RR: Rod and Reel, UN: Unknown Gear

Nº	Gear	Country
1	PS- FAD	Spain
2	PS- FSC	
3	PS- FAD	France
4	PS- FSC	
5	PS+BB- FAD	Ghana
6	PS+BB- FSC	
7	PS-FAD	Angola, Belize, Brazil, Cape Verde, Côte d'Ivoire, Curaçao, El Salvador, Equatorial Guinea, Guatemala, Guinea, Liberia, Mauritania, Morocco, Panama, Russia, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, São Tomé and Príncipe, Senegal, Seychelles and Venezuela
8	PS- FSC	
9	LL	Spain and Portugal
10	LL	Angola, Barbados, Belize, Brazil, Cape Verde, China, Cuba, Côte d'Ivoire, Guyana, Japan, Liberia, Libya, Mauritania, Morocco, Namibia, Panama, Philippines, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Senegal, Sierra Leone, South Korea, Taiwan, Trinidad and Tobago, United States, Unknown, Venezuela and Vanuatu
11	BB	France, Portugal, Spain
12	BB	Angola, Brazil, Cape Verde, Curaçao, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Senegal and Venezuela
13	HL	Angola, Brazil, Cape Verde, Côte d'Ivoire, Equatorial Guinea, Morocco, São Tomé and Príncipe and Senegal
14	GN	Angola, Côte d'Ivoire, Gabon, Ghana, Guyana, Liberia, Mauritania, Morocco, Senegal, Togo and Venezuela
15	TW, TP, TR, HS, RR, UN	Angola, Barbados, Cape Verde, Côte d'Ivoire, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Latvia, Liberia, Morocco, Mauritania, Netherlands, Nigeria, Russia, São Tomé and Príncipe, Senegal, Trinidad and Tobago, Ukraine, United Kingdom- Sta Helena

A.1.4. FG for CS 7

Table 15: FG of Ecopath for CS 7. Notations (s) and (d) stand for surface layer (from 0 to 10m of depth) and deep layer (more than 10m of depth), respectively.

N°	Functional Group (FG)	Small description
1	Bacteria (s)	
2	Pico-Phytoplankton (s)	
3	Nano-Phytoplankton (s)	Dinoflagellates genus (Naked dinoflagellates)
4	Micro-Phytoplankton (s)	Diatom genus (Leptocylindrus danicus-Bacteriastrum furcatum)
5	Heterotrophic tintinnids (s)	Codonellopsis schabi - Rhabdonella spiralis
6	Mixotrophic dinoflagellates (s)	Protopteridinium spp. - Thecate dinoflagellates
7	Mixotrophic ciliates (s)	Tontonia spp - Strombidium spp.
8	Radiolarians (s)	Acantharia
9	Bacteria (d)	
10	Pico-Phytoplankton (d)	
11	Nano-Phytoplankton (d)	Dinoflagellates genus (Naked dinoflagellates)
12	Micro-Phytoplankton (d)	Diatom genus (Leptocylindrus danicus-Bacteriastrum furcatum)
13	Mixo. <i>M. rubrum</i> (d)	
14	Heterotrophic tintinnids (d)	Codonellopsis schabi - Rhabdonella spiralis
15	Mixotrophic dinoflagellates (d)	Protopteridinium spp. - Thecate dinoflagellates
16	Mixotrophic ciliates (d)	Tontonia spp - Strombidium spp.
17	Radiolarians (d)	Acantharia
18	Herbivorous-Omnivorous cop. cal.	Paracalanus Parvus - Temora stylifera - Centropages ponticus - Clausocalanus
19	Omnivorous cop. cal. L	Labidocera wollastoni - Pleuromamma spp.
20	Carnivours cop. cyc. M	Corycaeus
21	Omnivorous cop. cyc. S	Oithona
22	Carnivours cop. cal. L	Candacia
23	Carnivours cop. cyc. S-L	Farranula - Sapphirina spp
24	Omnivorous-Detritivorous cop. har. M	Oncaeidae
25	Copepodites I-IV	Temora stylifera - Clausocalanus spp.

N°	Functional Group (FG)	Small description
26	Hydrozoans	
27	Chaetognaths	
28	Meroplankton	
29	Pteropods	
30	Amphipods	
31	Cladocerans	Penilia avirostris
32	Appendicularians	
33	Doliolids	
34	Salps	
35	Detritus	

A.1.5. Parameters of ZTCM for CS 4

Table 16: Summary of regression model diagnostics.

Parameters	Values
R ²	0.9342
R ² _adj	0.8157
Durbin-Watson (p-value)	1.9867 (0.7762)
F_stat (p-value)	7.886 (0.0175)
Residual min	-3.89 * 10 ⁻⁵
Residual max	9.02 * 10 ⁻⁵

Table 17: Estimated regression coefficients with their Generalized Variance Inflation Factor scaled by degrees of freedom, $GVIF^{(1/(2 \times Df))}$. Significance levels are indicated using R's standard codes: (***) $p < 0.001$, (**) $p < 0.01$, (*) $p < 0.05$.

	Estimated coefficients β	$GVIF^{(1/(2 \times Df))}$
Intercept (β_0)	5.158 * 10 ⁻⁰⁴ (**)	/
TC (β_1)	4.496 * 10 ⁻⁰⁸ (**)	2.314
Year2019 (β_2)	4.902 * 10 ⁻⁰⁴ (**)	2.993
Year2020 (β_3)	4.557 * 10 ⁻⁰⁴ (**)	
(TC.Year2019) (β_4)	-2.854 * 10 ⁻⁰⁸ (*)	2.462
(TC.Year2020) (β_5)	-1.549 * 10 ⁻⁰⁸	
Days_targeting_tunas (β_6)	6.761 * 10 ⁻⁰⁵ (*)	2.006
Days_prevented_from_fishing (β_7)	-3.745 * 10 ⁻⁰⁵ (*)	2.186
Nautical_miles_saied (β_8)	-2.716 * 10 ⁻⁰⁶ (***)	2.198
Km_driven (β_9)	-1.709 * 10 ⁻⁰⁷ (**)	1.506

